

Peruvian Mormons

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Entry tags: Religious Group, (The) Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints, Christian Traditions, Latter Day Saints (Mormons)

Peruvian Mormons identify as members of the largest sect of Mormonism, The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints. They identify as Peruvian either because they were born in Peru or because one or more of their parents or grandparents were. Peru is a highly diasporic nation, and though most Peruvian Mormons live in Peru, many live in the U.S. state of Utah where their church is headquartered. There may be Peruvians who identify as members of sects of Mormonism other than The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints, however, none of the participants in the principal anthropological study from whence this data set emerges identify with these sects nor do they know of any Peruvians who do. Importantly, most Peruvian Mormons do not identify as "Peruvian Mormons." This is partially because their church, on August 16, 2018, expressly directed its membership to eschew the "Mormon" moniker from self-identification, but mostly because the general membership of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints desires to be seen as a global fellowship, not as a set of nationally situated religions with local, syncretic practices. Designating Mormons who happen to also be Peruvian, "Peruvian Mormons" is part of a theoretical intervention that separates the Mormonism happening among Peruvian Mormons in Peru and Utah from the sorts of Mormonism happening among the people Peruvians call "Anglos" in order to highlight the unique challenges Peruvians face in navigating a decidedly non-Peruvian organization that was founded upon early colonial U.S. (Anglo) conceptions of race and kinship.

Date Range: 1956 CE - 2020 CE

Region: Peru and Utah

Region tags: South America, Peru, United States, Utah

This region symbolizes the transnational zone of migration between Utah and Peru that increasing amounts of Peruvian Mormons have been navigating since 1980.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Marín Benítez, Ciro. 2015. *Filosofía Tawantinsuyana: Una Perspectiva Epistémica*. Lima, Perú: Juan Gutemberg Editores Impresores.
- Source 2: Cannell, Fenella. 2013. "The Blood of Abraham: Mormon Redemptive Physicality and American Idioms of Kinship." *Journal of the Royal Anthropological Institute*, Blood will out: essays on liquid transfers and flows, 19 (May): 77-94.
- Source 3: Taylor, Lori Elaine. 2000. "Telling Stories about Mormons and Indians." PhD diss., State University of New York at Buffalo.

Notes: Source 1 sets an important foundation for understanding what philosophies existed in Peru and the Andes in general before the arrival of Mormonism. Source 2 is one of the few anthropological studies published on Mormonism. Fenella Cannell is also one of the world's most preeminent anthropologists of Christianity in general. Source 3 is vital to understanding the Mormon conceptions of indigeneity that affect the way Peruvians are made legible as actors in The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints and the way Peruvian Mormons come to identify themselves. The fact that none of these sources deal with Peruvian Mormonism directly points to the importance of the contributor's forthcoming dissertation at

the University of California, Irvine entitled *Peruvian Mormon: Cosmologies of Race and Relatedness at Zion's Border*.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://sudamericanoeste.laiglesiadejesucristo.org/sanwchurchhistory/peru>
- Source 1 Description: This is the official history of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints in Peru from the faith-promoting perspective of the church.
- Source 2 URL: <http://cuzcoeats.com/mines-railroads-mormons-story-pisco-sour/>
- Source 2 Description: This site is run by David Knowlton, the only person other than the contributor who could be classified as an anthropologist of Peruvian Mormonism. Dr. Knowlton is a professor at Utah Valley University and, though he has written extensively on Mormonism in the Andes, now focuses mostly on other Andean cultural forms, such as foodways.
- Source 3 URL: <https://lamanitetruth.com/>
- Source 3 Description: This site is run by Sarah Newcomb, a member of the Tsimshian nation (a group of people indigenous to the Pacific Northwest coast of North America) and a former Mormon. Lamanite identity is an important aspect of Peruvian Mormonism in that it is an identity that stems from the belief that the protagonists of the Book of Mormon were the progenitors of some or all of the indigenous inhabitants of the Americas. This website's purpose is to shed light on Lamanite identity from a scholarly (not faith-based) perspective.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.josephsmithpapers.org/>
- Source 1 Description: This site contains digitized copies of many early Mormon documents, such as a first edition Book of Mormon. Since the separation of Peruvian Mormonism from The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints represents a theoretical construct rather than the deliberate development of a new religious tradition with its own founding documents, Peruvian Mormons do not have their own set of scriptures apart from those used by their official church.
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/history/topics/lamanite-identity?lang=eng>
- Source 2 Description: This link leads to a document on the official website of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints that is important for understanding the precarious position that many Peruvian Mormons hold within their Anglo-controlled religious organization. Many Anglo Mormon missionaries in Peru, backed by the top leaders of the church, taught that Peruvians with indigenous ancestry are biological descendants of a Book of Mormon character named Laman who was cursed and given a dark skin tone. "Laman-ite" identity became an integral part of many Peruvian Mormons' sense of self and personal conviction as to the historical accuracy of the Book Of Mormon. At approximately the turn of the 21st century, the church leaders began to see the political incorrectness and genetic impossibility of Lamanite identity. The linked essay represents their retreat from their original claims that the Book Of Mormon contains the literal history and genealogy of the Amerindians. The linked essay also represents the church's double bind. In retreating from the race-based theology that Lamanite identity requires, they are also retreating from the hundreds of thousands of Latin American Mormons for whom Lamanite identity has become an inextricable part of self. The linked essay also represents the wealth of primary source information found on the church's official website. Unfortunately for historical purposes, the church frequently does not provide author names or dates for their treatises. This particular essay was posted sometime in 2018. Of course, the official church and its affiliates provide primary source material for the purpose of faith-building, not critical thinking.
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/c/Mormonsudorg/search?query=Peru>
- Source 3 Description: Though not officially affiliated with The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints, the media organization MasFe, led by Peruvian Mormon Isaac Angulo, has covered many Mormon-related events in Peru including the construction and dedication of the Arequipa, Peru temple, one of the contributor's points of anthropological focus.

Notes: There are few online repositories of primary sources directly related to the academic study of

Peruvian Mormonism known to the contributor that are not owned by the corporation of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints or its affiliates. This entry itself, as a result of the attached files, is perhaps the principal online repository of Peruvian Mormonism's primary source material currently available to the non-Mormon public. Files with the initial descriptor of "Anti-Mormon Collection" are part of a collection of largely anti-Mormon literature gifted to the contributor by the Gospel Doctrine Sunday School teacher of the Mormon congregation in Arequipa, Peru that he joined in 2018 in order to carry out his ethnographic research of Peruvian Mormonism. The Gospel Doctrine teacher received this collection from one of the first Peruvians to be baptized into The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints in Peru. That early Peruvian Mormon sought to collect local arequipeño press excerpts and pamphlets about Mormonism, but only occasionally included information as to provenance. The citation information included for each document, therefore, is often incomplete.

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The texts that members of the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints generally consider "scripture" are their four "canonical" books: The Book of Mormon, The King James Bible (both Old and New Testaments), The Doctrine and Covenants (a religious history of early frontier Anglo Mormonism), and The Pearl of Great Price, a short text that includes a number of documents including Joseph Smith's "translation" of ancient papyri <https://www.josephsmithpapers.org/paper-summary/egyptian-papyri-circa-300-bc-ad-50/1> from Egypt that a mummy exhibit brought to Kirtland, Ohio in 1835, see: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Book_of_Abraham . The contemporary versions of these books in Spanish that Peruvian Mormons in Peru and Utah use during their Sunday church services and personal scripture study are available online at the church's official website <https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/scriptures?lang=spa> as well as through an app that most Peruvian Mormons have on their smartphones <https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/pages/mobileapps/gospellibrary?lang=eng> . However, the original first editions and, in some cases, the manuscript copies are available here: <https://www.josephsmithpapers.org/paper-summary/book-of-mormon-1830/1> . Interestingly, though the church does not have an official Quechua-speaking mission in Peru (Quechua is Peru's most common language other than Castilian Spanish), it has translated the Book of Mormon into a variant of Bolivian Quechua (quite different from the many variants and registers of Quechua spoken in Peru) <https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/scriptures/bofm?lang=quh>

Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: Technically, everything that is spoken by the servants of God is God's voice and, as such, scripture. As God himself stated in The Doctrine and Covenants section 1, verse 38: "whether by mine own voice or by the voice of my servants, it is the same." Some Mormons interpret this to mean that whatever the prophets and apostles of the church speak orally becomes automatic scripture. Not only that, but they believe this automatic, oral scripture overrides all previous scripture (written or otherwise) that it might happen to contradict. The church broadcasts what is known as its General Conference from The Conference Center in Salt Lake City, Utah biannually (every October and April). The speeches that the upper echelons of the church give during these conferences are transcribed (and sometimes significantly changed or "toned down") and

published in the church's November (for the October conference) and May (for the April conference) issues of its monthly magazine published in Spanish as the *Liahona* (The Ensign, in English). <https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/magazines/liahona?lang=spa> These issues of the *Liahona*, along with the articles written by the prophet or the apostles for the other monthly issues, are considered "scripture." Though they are considered scripture, they are not "enacted" as such, at least not among Peruvian Mormons in Perifericos Ward in 2018. These particular Mormons often motivated each other to read the *Liahona* by hyping it up as "living scripture" from the mouth of "modern prophets," however the words from the four canonical books always held much more sway than any recent materials published by the church. Technically, the Salt Lake City, Utah-distributed manuals of the church, in as much as they are written by "modern prophets" are also considered "scripture." However, even Peruvian Mormons who would never downplay the importance of the four canonical books sometimes openly disparage the manuals. The contributor has heard many Peruvian Mormons say things like, "the manual can say whatever it wants to say, but this is what we are going to do." Most Mormons, Peruvian or otherwise, would not be so dismissive of the four canonical books even though everything published by the church is equally "scripture" according to God's logic that "whether by mine own voice or by the voice of my servants, it is the same." Though non-canonical church publications may not be quite as holy as the canonical publications, there still forms a palpable energy among Peruvian Mormons every October and April when General Conference time approaches. Many chapels in Arequipa receive closed circuit broadcasts of these conferences, which are projected onto a large screen that suddenly bathes the otherwise Peruvian space in the dazzling light of Salt Lake City, Utah. General Conference speeches from the church president and the apostles are intermingled with hymns sung by the (99% Anglo) Mormon Tabernacle Choir, with images of the Salt Lake City temple, and with live feeds deliberately showing the more ethnically diverse of the wholesome, Utah Mormon nuclear families wandering around the Temple Square gardens during intermission. Having Salt Lake City always be the fount from which scripture springs orally to the membership creates a profound, global Mormon cultural archetype wherein only Anglo-dominated places can truly be holy places, only European music can be sacred music, and only Anglo words can be God's words. Incidentally, many Peruvian Mormons time their permanent immigration to Utah to coincide with the semi-annual General Conference so that they can use their tickets to said conference as solid evidence of the purpose for which they need a temporary tourist visa, which they will then overstay.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

— Yes

Notes: The Book Of Mormon depicts a light-skinned, Israelite family led by a prophet named Lehi who is of the subtribe of Manasseh. He, his wife Sariah, their four sons (Laman, Lemuel, Nephi and Sam) and their unnamed daughters fled the Babylonian captivity of Jerusalem to arrive at what many Peruvian Mormons argue was an almost completely uninhabited American continent in 600 BCE. After Lehi's family inhabited the Americas, Laman and Lemuel became cursed because they did not practice proper kinways. Their skin was darkened (apologists who want to downplay the church's foundational racism attempt to argue that the curse and the darkening of the skin were completely unrelated events, as this fascinating comic demonstrates:

<https://www.facebook.com/MakingsbyMeikah/photos/a.1448055688715448/1448054165382267>). Nephi prophesied that, though his siblings' brown-skinned descendants—the Lamanites—would end up killing off all his light-skinned descendants—the Nephites—the Lamanites would one day be restored to the true kinways as contained in the Book Of Mormon, and their skin would be restored to whiteness. Nephi also prophesied that the mechanism of this restoration would include European conquistadors. Their propitious removal of the more wicked among the Lamanites (the Amerindians) would prepare the way for a Euro-American nation-state, "lifted up by the power of God above all other nations," (

<https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/scriptures/bofm/1-ne/13.30?lang=eng&clang=eng#p30>) that would one day allow for the religious freedom necessary to bring the Book Of Mormon out of its hidden New York repository and into the heathen hands of the Amerindian descendants of its dark-skinned antagonists. After writing all this down, Nephi handed off the task of writing the religious history of his people to a new prophet who in turn bequeathed the responsibility to another, and that other to another down the generations until 1000 years later, in about 400 CE,

the prophet Mormon had inherited a whole cave full of records. He summarized these onto gold plates and gave them to his son Moroni who engraved a few closing remarks at the end. Moroni, the last Nephite prophet of the Americas (depicted as light-skinned in the illustrations that accompany the free edition of the Book of Mormon to which most Peruvian Mormons were first exposed), witnessed the dark-skinned Lamanites completely destroy his people. Since he had no descendants to whom he could bequeath the records, Moroni hid them under a rock (along with other talismans that had been passed down through the ages, such as an interpretation device known as the Urim and Thumim) in what would one day become Upstate New York. In 1820, as a resurrected, supernatural being of flesh and bone, Moroni appeared to a 14-year-old Anglo settler-colonist named Joseph Smith and told him where to find the gold plates. Joseph Smith translated a portion of these into English through the power of the Urim and Thumim and through inspiration from Iroquois legends and Seneca grave goods he called "seer stones" that he had become adept at pilfering, (see file:///E:/lit%20review/Mormon%20specific/Latter-day_Saint%20Rhetoric,%20Religion,%20and%20Repatriation.pdf). He published this inspired translation as *The Book Of Mormon* in 1830. In the 1830's, in the midst of the U.S. government's Indian Removal Act, this book provided Anglo settler-colonists—who, according to the book, were members of the scattered Israelite subtribe of Ephraim, Manasseh's older brother—an answer to Musa Dube's question in her feminist reading of Exodus, "Does this text encourage travel to distant and inhabited lands, and if so, how does it justify itself?" (2000, 57). In other words, the theme from Exodus surrounding the justified genocide of the Canaanites as expressed in the Book of Mormon, and later in the actual Mormon exodus to Utah, provided Anglo Mormons (Ephraim) one justification for their expropriation of the lives and lands of the Ute, Diné, Shoshone, and Paiute (Manasseh) that later became the U.S. state of Utah. From an anthropological perspective, the Book of Mormon represents an ingeniously insidious addition to the "Indianist" literature common during U.S. imperial conquest designed to give Anglo settler-colonists a sense of indigeneity, of being the oppressed "people of the land" instead of being the oppressors. From a Peruvian Mormon perspective, the Book of Mormon represents the literal history of the people who once inhabited the ruins they see around them in places like Machu Picchu today. Many Peruvian Mormons consider themselves to be Lamanites and, as such, biological descendants of Israel. From the church's contemporary PR-focused, colorblind-racist perspective, *The Book of Mormon* should no longer be read as the ancestral history of a cursed/blessed people, the Lamanites, who still exist today. The church once held fast to this idea of Lamanite identity and utilized it to convince thousands of Peruvians to become Mormons. But Lamanite identity is now seen as anti-modern and overtly racist in the U.S., and so the church, as a U.S-centric organization, is backing away from it. In so doing, it is betraying hundreds of thousands of Peruvian Mormons who have deep, strong, generational ties to that identity. Work Cited Dube, DR Musa W. 2000. *Postcolonial Feminist Interpretation of the Bible*. St. Louis, Mo: Chalice Press.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

— Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

— Yes

Notes: Moroni was a supernatural being when he revealed the location of the gold plates to Joseph Smith.

↳ Inspired by high god:

— Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

— Yes

Notes: There are stories in the Book of Mormon wherein people are "inspired" by Satan,

another supernatural being.

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: In a sense, God the Father himself is a human being who has evolved into divinity.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: The prophets in the Book of Mormon are considered non-divine humans, as is Joseph Smith.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

Notes: There have been many additions and deletions in the Book of Mormon to make it sound less racist. Also, after DNA evidence came out in 2002 that there was no Israelite “blood” among isolated Amerindian groups (Murphy 2003), the church changed its text yet again. In 1981, the introduction to the book had read, “After thousands of years, all were destroyed except the Lamanites, and they are the principal ancestors of the American Indians.” (Fletcher Stack 2007). This was already a slightly watered down version of the idea that many Peruvian Mormons have of the book, which is that not only are the Lamanites the principal ancestors, they are the sole ancestors. However, in 2007, in direct reaction to mounting DNA evidence, that line was qualified even more to read, “they are among the ancestors of the American Indians” (<https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/scriptures/bofm/introduction?lang=eng&clang=eng>). The single word “among” seems insignificant. In fact, most Peruvian Mormons do not know about its addition to their holy text. Nevertheless, the word “among” dilutes their descendancy from Israel and demonstrates the church’s capitulation to a U.S.-centric notion of relatedness that has outsourced its kinship system to geneticists. The addition of the word “among” demonstrates that authority over story can be weaponized to disrupt identity. Works Cited Murphy, Thomas W. 2003. “Simply Implausible: DNA and a Mesoamerican Setting for the Book of Mormon.” *Dialogue: A Journal Of Mormon Thought* 4 (36): 109-31. Fletcher Stack, Peggy. 2007. “Single Word Change in Book of Mormon Speaks Volumes.” *The Salt Lake Tribune*, 2007, November 8 edition. <http://archive.slttrib.com/article.php?id=7403990&itype=NGPSID>.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The largely male, largely Anglo committees that write the scripture study manuals and guides in the Church Office Building in Salt Lake City, Utah decide not only how to interpret scriptures, but which parts of the scriptures deserve focus and which parts should best be skipped. Little is known about who makes up these closed committees of paid, church corporation employees and how much oversight the ecclesiastical leaders of the church have over the products they publish. What little is known can be found in anthropologist Daymon Smith's unique book, *The Book of Mammon: A Book About A Book About The Corporation That Owns The Mormons*. Recently an interpretation of the dark skin “curse” of the Lamanites was published in one of these committee-written, Book of Mormon study guides that apparently included “erroneous” information damaging to the church ecclesiastical leaders’ antiracist facade. The church had to issue an embarrassing correction (see attached newspaper article), which only served to draw attention to the anachronistic racism that pervades the Book of Mormon rather than distract from it. The Peruvian Mormons known to the contributor did not notice that the original, uncorrected version of the manual contained a mistake. In other words, it did not strike them as being any more racist than what they were already used to seeing in church manuals and in the Book of Mormon itself.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– No

Notes: There are many groups of people who consider themselves faithful members of the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints who have unofficial ways of interpreting its foundational scriptures. For example, even though antiblackness is foundational to Mormonism, there are Black Mormons in the U.S. who have found ways to interpret scripture that create a space for them within Mormonism (<https://www.facebook.com/sistasinzion>)

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: In some sense, Mormons consider themselves to be the select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures to the rest of the world. They believe that the Bible only provides half of the evidence necessary to establish Jesus Christ as the one and only source of salvation. The Book of Mormon is the keystone of their religion because it provides the other half, the half that the rest of the Christian world does not have and that it so desperately needs. Within Mormonism there are many special training programs for scriptural transmission. One is the Missionary Training Center, which all full-time missionaries attend for intensive foreign language and proselyting training for 3 weeks to 2 months before they enter their mission areas. As Mormonism has no paid, full-time clergy, there is nothing equivalent to a Catholic seminary meant to train a person who wishes to become a pastor as a full-time profession or vocation. However, there is something called the Church Education System or CES. The aspect of CES that Peruvian Mormons seem to cherish most is not its training in the transmission of the scriptures, but its inculcation of Puritanical time thrift, something they do not get during the non-Mormon aspect of their regular school day. In Periféricos Ward, the most talked-about of the CES's many programs is simply called "Seminary." It is designed to be concurrent with the four years of U.S.-style high school, and each year's curriculum focuses on one of Mormonism's four canonical books. In Utah, most public high schools and junior highs have a church-owned, dedicated Seminary building on their campuses. Seminary for these students is incorporated as just another period of their regular school schedule and is designated as "released time" on their transcripts. Seminary teachers in Utah are CES employees and are usually paid a much higher salary than their secular high school teaching counterparts next door. Seminary teachers (and their university counterparts known as Institute teachers) receive professional development training, many have PhDs in scriptural linguistics, and since scriptural teaching is their profession, they probably represent Mormonism's most elite, select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures (other than perhaps the religious studies faculty at Brigham Young University, the church's own private university with campuses in Utah, Idaho, Hawaii, and Jerusalem). To be a professional seminary teacher in Utah one must be male and one must be married. If a seminary teacher gets divorced, he loses his job. In Peru (and most places outside of Utah) on the other hand, Seminary teaching is an unpaid "calling" like any other, and lessons are held early in the morning before regular school starts, usually in the home of the teacher. Seminary seniors are often asked to stand before their congregations and "bear testimony" of their Seminary experiences to motivate incoming freshmen. The contributor has witnessed many of these testimonies in Periféricos Ward, and they almost always gloss over what was learned in Seminary in order to elaborate on the character-building aspects of getting up early enough to attend it. The typical testimony begins with a comical description of the lethargy that made attendance impossible in the beginning. This is made even more comical to the contributor's Anglophone ears by the fact that Spanish has a special verb meaning "to unfortunately have to wake up early" (*madrugar*) which almost carries enough of a negative connotation in Peru to be a swear word. The testimony will then shift to the hateful tactics to which parents resorted, usually involving ice water, in order that students might develop the austere habitus of early rising. Finally, testimonies unanimously end with expressions of gratitude, not for what was taught in Seminary, but for its unlocking of a

brand new time of day, a time that promises to forever provide an edge over sleeping competitors in the battle for entry into a time-disciplined, capitalist future of scarcity. Ofelia is a seminary teacher in Periféricos Ward. When one of her potential students convinced Nailah, that student's mother, that she really could not get up early, the subordination of scriptural curriculum to early rising was made explicit. OFELIA: It is not correct that Seminary be taught in the afternoon. Nevertheless, Nailah and her daughter didn't want to get up early. Ever since last year Nailah has been pestering me, saying, "Hermana, I want you to teach it in the afternoon." So I consulted with the supervisor [another "called" position], and the supervisor consulted with the brother who is in charge of seminary in all of Arequipa [a CES paid position] and he said that the Area Presidency had prohibited afternoon Seminary because the youth, One—must learn to sacrifice, to get up early, and to get themselves to the places where Seminary is taught; and Two—when youth take Seminary in the morning they start the day with the Spirit because they pray and read the scriptures. So, last year, I told Nailah that, but she didn't give up. She kept insisting and insisting, and since she has some kind of calling in the Young Women, she felt she could just start teaching her daughter seminary in the afternoons without consulting with the supervisor or anyone. One day, another mother approached the supervisor to ask for the registration forms for her daughter and she says, "my daughter is going to take night Seminary," "but, Hermana, there is no night teacher." "Isn't Hermana Nailah teaching it?" And so the supervisor got angry and accused Nailah of attributing to herself the calling of Seminary teacher. Nailah essentially called herself, and that is why the supervisor is constantly checking on that class because as soon as other youth who lived near Nailah found out about it, they were like, "oh yeah, it's in the afternoon?! We don't have to madrugar anymore! We're there!" Now she has a decent-sized group, like six students. So we're going to see what happens with that group. How will they end up? Nobody knows. Even though Nailah's students are receiving the same Utah-designed, manual-driven education as Ofelia's own Seminary students, Ofelia worries about how the time difference will affect their future. Mormon Seminary taught in the afternoon may not be enough to counteract the relatively time-undisciplined education that students receive during the rest of their day in arequipeño schools. It certainly will not be enough to prepare students to compete with the intense future centrism of the Utah-style education embodied in the 18 to 20-year-old Anglo missionaries for whom Ofelia cooks every day and with whom her Seminary students will someday be paired when they go on their own missions. Seminary is such an important, foundational aspect of the formation of young Mormon selves that the committee that designs CES curriculum probably holds the greatest power over scriptural interpretation in Mormonism. This is ironic because, unlike the highest leaders of the church whose words are taken to be automatic scripture, almost nobody knows who the members of this Utah-based committee are. Nevertheless, they are the ones who decide which verses of the Book of Mormon the youth in Peru will memorize, which verses they will summarize, and, importantly, which verses they will conveniently skip.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

— Yes

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

— Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

— Yes

Notes: 95% of Peruvians consistently identified as Catholic from 1910 to 1970. This number dropped to 76% by 2014 (Pew Research Center. 2014. Religion in Latin America). Most Peruvians who stop identifying as Catholic adopt other religious identities, many of which were founded in the U.S., such as Pentecostal, Seventh-Day Adventist, Jehovah's Witness, and of course, Mormon. This creates a competitive environment among all these religions, but it creates a special tension with Catholicism, the only religion taught in Peruvian public schools and the only religion that the Peruvian government subsidizes. The cultural contact between Mormonism and the Catholic

church remains mildly competitive, but when The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints first entered Peru in earnest in 1956, the opposition of the Catholic church was reportedly quite fierce. Evidence for this is included in "Relevant Online Primary Textual Corpora" under the descriptor "Anti-Mormon Collection" and includes some of the myriad forms of anti-Mormon propaganda the Catholic church published and distributed in Arequipa, Peru in the early 1960's. To give an idea of the threat that the Mormon church represented in the imagination of Archbishop of Arequipa, Leonardo Rodriguez Ballon, a lengthy letter he read aloud in Arequipa's main cathedral in the Plaza de Armas meant to prepare his parishioners for Vatican II was solely about the evils of Mormonism. The letter (included in its entirety above) is simply titled, "In Defense of the Faith."

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

— Yes

Notes: The cultural contact between the Catholic church and the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints in Arequipa, Peru vacillates between antagonistic and accommodating. For example, in 1962, the Archbishop of Arequipa read the aforementioned, anti-Mormon letter and had it published in installments throughout all of Arequipa's major news outlets. In 2017, on the other hand, Archbishop of Arequipa, Javier del Rio Alba was a VIP guest at the groundbreaking ceremony of the Mormon church's Arequipa temple dedication in the staunchly Catholic town of Carmen Alto. This Archbishop was instrumental in convincing the local parishioners of Carmen Alto to stop protesting the construction of a Mormon temple in their vicinity. According to a private conversation between the Arequipa temple construction site manager (an Anglo Mormon from Colorado, U.S.A) and the contributor that took place on March 23, 2018, Archbishop Javier del Rio Alba has discoursed together with Mormon apostle Dallin H. Oaks at "religious freedom" conferences in the U.S. and elsewhere. For Oaks, "religious freedom" is a euphemism for the freedom to discriminate against LGBTQI+ communities, and his partnership with a Catholic archbishop is representative of the greater ideological common ground the Mormon church has discovered that it has with the Catholic church regarding gender and what both churches consider to be its fixed, binary, and god-given nature. In other words, the Mormons and the Catholics have recently formed a united front against a common enemy: what is known in Peru as "ideologia del genero" (gender ideology).

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

— No

Notes: Though the contact between the Mormons and the Catholics in Arequipa, Peru has never been seriously violent, it has never been exactly neutral either. It has involved the threat of violence. The following translated and transcribed interview excerpt that provides evidence for this comes from a conversation between the contributor and an elderly married couple who were among the first 50 Peruvians to become Mormons in Arequipa. Ronal was baptized in 1960 and Leticia in 1966. The interview took place in their home in Arequipa on March 2, 2018. JASON: What image do you have of Utah? RONAL: I think of the history that we have of the church growth with Joseph Smith the prophet, and so much persecution that they didn't know how to escape it, and here in Arequipa we've also had persecution. The newspapers warred against us. They were always picking at our prohibition against alcohol. I remember in the very first days, when I was baptized, the membership started to grow and we would travel to thermal pools for baptism. The press would follow us. One time at a kiosk, a man with a bottle of beer and a cup stood next to a member [of the Mormon church] who happened to be drinking soda out of a bottle. They snapped a photo. In the newspaper the next day the headline read, "There They Are, These Are The Mormons!" "Supposedly these Mormons don't drink, but look what we saw." What didn't they say about us? Uy! They would even say that in our chapels we had many rooms where men would hook up with women. All lies. The Catholic priests would wait for us on the corner, throng around us and say, "where is that book?" And they would snatch our Books of Mormon away, "these must be burned, these are worthless." But the Catholics are more accepting now. LETICIA: Even my niece has accepted. She hasn't accepted baptism yet, but one can still hope. When my mother died, my niece had never before seen how temple-endowed members were buried. She was with me, since she is the oldest of my mother's granddaughters, and Hermana

Maribel from the church was there. I told them, "help me dress my mother." My mother had her little temple envelope of clothing ready for her death, all new. And my niece was impacted upon seeing how we dressed and cleaned, and she helped us put on the little shoes. Even though she wasn't a member, she was her granddaughter, so I couldn't prohibit her from helping with the sacred temple clothing. It impacted her to see that a man and a woman who are sealed in the temple go to the tomb in their ceremonial robes. And ever since then, my niece--- hopefully, hopefully, we are-- RONAL: ---We are waiting for the Arequipa temple open house so that she can go. And for us as well, it has been a surprise, what with the groundbreaking and all that. (The endowment is a temple ritual wherein subjects are endowed with power from on high and are granted the keywords, signs, and tokens necessary for passing the angels who stand as sentinels guarding the highest of the three heavens, the Celestial Kingdom. The endowment involves changing into special robes including white slippers. Some might say that the endowment is the penultimate temple rite and that marriage is the ultimate. This is not completely accurate. Being resurrected from the dead can be considered the ultimate temple rite, which is why Mormons are buried in their temple robes. Leticia takes the time to justify allowing a non-Mormon to touch temple clothing because Mormons are extremely careful with what they allow the uninitiated to know about temple practices. A temple's pre-dedication open house is the only time non-Mormons and "unworthy" Mormons can enter. In the case of the Arequipa temple, this happened in November 2019. Ronal did not live to see it.)

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

— Yes

Notes: There has been violent conflict between Peruvian Mormons and the Maoist Guerrilla movement of the 1980's and 90's called the Sendero Luminoso. The following translated and transcribed interview excerpt that provides evidence for this stems from a conversation between the contributor and an employee of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints, Simon, who was an ecclesiastical leader over many congregations (a "stake president") in Arequipa, Peru during the height of Sendero violence. Simon was also born and raised in Arequipa. This interview took place on December 26, 2017 at a shopping mall in Provo, Utah. JASON: You've seen the difference between the establishment of Zion in Utah and the establishment of Zion in Arequipa and many other parts of the world. What does Utah still need in order to truly become Zion? SIMON: I think that here [in Utah] they had the blessing of receiving the gospel firsthand, and it was marvelous. The pioneers did an incredible job in these lands, but my impression is that, as the years have gone by, the younger generations has forgotten a bit of what the pioneer sacrifice meant. Us over there [in Peru], we saw a little of what the pioneers saw here [in the U.S.] when they started their new religion with all the opposition in Missouri, Kirtland, etcetera. Well, that same opposition was felt by us in Arequipa in the beginning. The Catholic priests would come and attack the first Mormons there. They took a procession with their virgin to the first chapel built in Arequipa—Umacollo—and they stoned us, they threw rocks at us. Then the Sendero Luminoso [Shining Path] came in the 80s and 90s when I was a stake president. I received a letter that I'm going to show you, a threat letter where they gave me thirty days to get out and if I didn't, they were going to kill me and my family, and they were also going to attack our chapels. They did it, Jason. In Ica they destroyed two chapels. I was with my wife one day driving my car. We passed by the chapel and it exploded, right where I worked. I was seeing all the dust from the roof that caved in and the glass. A young man came and told me, "President, they destroyed the stake center [larger chapel] too." They exploded both at the same time. I saw that myself. Personally. But also in other places, they attacked chapels, they destroyed, they killed Peruvian missionaries. In Arequipa, after I introduce you to the pioneer of Cuzco, I am going to introduce you to the father of one of the missionaries who died, murdered by the Sendero Luminoso. JASON: Did the Sendero have something specifically against the Mormon church? SIMON: No, they were basically against all religions of foreign origin. They related the church to North American interests—Pizza Hut, McDonald's, and the Mormons ... At first we had a lot of Catholic opposition, but with time, we had the communist opposition. Now the Catholics love us. There has been a change and they have seen that we are not purely Yankees. We are a people of North American origin, yes; a very U.S. religion, but it goes further than simply politics. It offers you a change of life. We have won respect from the Catholics, and a little from the communists as well [laughs]. (Establishing Zion is a complex concept, but in some sense it can be read simply

as "establishing Mormonism." Notice how in both this and in the previous interview with Ronal and Leticia, the contributor does not ask about the persecution of early Peruvian Mormons, he asks only about Utah. This recounting of violence comes completely unprompted and is perhaps symptomatic of the self-perception of being a persecuted people that Mormonism enshrined in its origin myths and that it perpetuates through continual reminders, such as the annual July 24th celebration of "Pioneer Day" in Utah, an official state holiday.)

- ↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):
– No

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

- ↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 1

Notes: 1% is the lowest number allowed in the field. If the question is asking what percentage of the entire square footage of the city of Arequipa, Peru is covered with facilities owned and operated by The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints, the answer is far less than 1%. However, there is one area in Arequipa that is a major exception to this. In the outskirts of the city, there sits an ancient settlement that has been continuously inhabited for the past 3,000 years and that, in the 16th century, the Spanish organized into a small set of dwellings around a central town square. That town is called Carmen Alto. Though not a single one of its approximately 1,000 residents was Mormon before the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints began construction of the Arequipa Temple there in 2017, 37% of Carmen Alto is now owned by the church (see attached map). Though the church owns a much larger percentage of Utah's buildings than it does of Peru's, the "percentage of area" taken up by religious monuments in the average Utah city would still be less than 1% simply because Utah settlements often include vast areas of open space.

- ↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 31457

Notes: This was calculated by using the polygon feature of Google Earth on the above image. 31,457 square meters represents the area of the entire plot of land that the Arequipa temple takes up, not the square meters of floor space inside the temple itself. According to <https://churchofjesuschristtemples.org/statistics/dimensions/> the square footage of the Arequipa temple's actual floor space is 26,969. In square meters that is 2,505.

- ↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 25

Notes: This is an estimate, see photo.

- ↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 3239

Notes: 3,239 square meters is the area of the polygon of land covered by the Mormon meeting house that the contributor attended every Sunday in 2018 in Arequipa, Peru. There are about 20 such meeting houses in Peru which are shared by approximately 45 separate congregations. This square footage includes a concrete soccer court which usually takes up about half of each meeting house's land space. Mormon church meeting houses in Utah usually do not have

outdoor soccer courts, instead they have large parking lots and indoor basketball courts. The size of the land of the meeting house that the contributor attended in 2017 in Utah, which was average-sized for a Mormon meeting house in Utah, is 13,756 square meters, about 4 times larger than the largest comparable meeting house in Arequipa. This is not counting the 9,421 square meter baseball field right next to the meeting house which, though it is not precisely owned by the church, has no fence between it and the church and is often used for church events.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 7

Notes: Most Mormon meeting houses in both Peru and Utah are single story buildings, however, especially in Utah, they often have high vaulted ceilings which add to their height. Most Mormon meeting houses in Peru and Utah also have decorative steeples that increase this average height estimate.

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage of area: 1

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 600000

Notes: The church itself has a statistic page for each country in South America, and for that matter, most countries in the world. As of August 3, 2020 there are 619,045 members of record of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints in Peru (see <https://newsroom.churchofjesuschrist.org/facts-and-statistics/country/peru>), which according to that same page, represents 1.94% of the population of Peru. According to a 2017 interview the contributor conducted with the Peruvian Consul in Utah, himself a Peruvian Mormon, of the approximately 8,000 Peruvians in Utah, 5,000 are Mormon. Estimates vary, but approximately 60% of Utahans are Mormon. There are, however, cities in Utah that are upwards of 90% Mormon. Despite the fact that Peruvians make up less than one percent of the population of Utah, Utah still has the seventh highest per capita population of Peruvians in the U.S. The other six states are all on the Eastern Seaboard. Just because Peru has around 600,000 Mormons, does not mean that all of these Mormons identify as such. Part of the proof Mormonism uses for its claim to be "the only true and living church upon the face of the whole earth, with which I, the Lord, am well pleased," (<https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/scriptures/dc-testament/dc/?lang=eng>) is its numbers. The church has prophesied that its numbers will grow and grow until it they fill the whole earth. Its growth, therefore, is thought to be a sign of its truthfulness. The extent to which its membership numbers reflect the way people actually identify is a reality that the church does not like to publish. The church tends to inflate its numbers so that its members can feel that they are part of a healthy, growing organization. If the amount of members on the Perifericos Ward's records who actually identify as members of Perifericos Ward is any indication, only about 1/3 of Peruvians whom the church identifies as members actually identify themselves as members. This means there are about 200,000 Peruvians who identify as Mormon in Peru. That only 1/3 of the church's reported membership in a country would identify as such actually reflects quite favorably on the Peruvian church. 1/3 is a high fraction compared to other countries in the world, and even other countries in South America. Peruvian Mormons are the most "active" Mormons in South America. One measure of this is the number of temples in Peru. Temples are the most holy and most expensive edifices in Mormonism and their construction is usually only justified in areas where there is a large concentration of full tithe-paying members (Mormons who pay a full ten percent of their monthly income to the church). Peru has 4 temples. Chile, where Mormons supposedly make up over 3% of the country's population, only has 2 temples. This means that Chile has a higher concentration of Mormons than Peru, but a lower concentration of "active" Mormons. In most countries throughout the world, only about 1/4 of the church's reported membership wants anything to do with the church. Effectively, this means that, though the church boasts of its 16 million members throughout the world, only 4 million actually consider themselves to be members. Census data from various countries demonstrates that this sort of statistical inflation is not the case among other U.S.-based

Christianities. For example, the membership numbers that the Jehovah's Witnesses report are consistently lower, not higher, than the numbers of people in the census who identify as Jehovah's Witnesses. In the case of Mormonism, the numbers the church reports are consistently four times higher than what censuses show (Stewart 2008). In short, people who were baptized Mormon on a whim as youth and don't even remember ever setting foot in a Mormon church are included in the church's numbers right along with the 150 active members of Perifericos Ward in Arequipa, Peru who participate in church activities on an almost daily basis. As part of the contributor's ethnographic investigations, he accompanied many pairs of Mormon missionaries in both Peru and Utah during their proselyting efforts. On more than one occasion, missionaries became excited when an "investigator" decided to be baptized only to become disappointed later upon finding out that the investigator had already been baptized years prior and simply did not remember the occasion. Work Cited Stewart, David G. 2008. "Growth, Retention, and Internationalization." In *Revisiting Thomas F. O'Dea's The Mormons: Contemporary Perspectives*, edited by Cardell K. Jacobson, John P. Hoffmann, and Tim B. Heaton, 328-62. Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

— Yes

Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

— Yes

Notes: Regarding the system of religious affiliation, the practice of Peruvian Mormons is similar to the official practice of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints. The church keeps very thorough records, which it curates both in local congregations and in centralized databases. Local leaders have access to these databases, now online, and are able to see the contact information, age, gender, and "activity level" (a measure of church attendance and religiosity) of each person, and, importantly, each "household," under their jurisdiction. As part of the contributor's study of Peruvian Mormonism, he officially joined a congregation in Arequipa, Peru in 2018. He was able to do so because his name was already in the church's central database as a "member of record," meaning he was baptized by immersion by a "worthy" male officiator of what is known as the "Aaronic priesthood," a lesser priesthood preparatory to the greater priesthood known as the "Melchizedek priesthood." He had been baptized at age 8 by his own father, a situation considered ideal among Mormon families the world over. Baptized members of the church are also members of the specific, cartographically bounded congregation within which their residence happens to fall. The contributor, upon moving to Arequipa, Peru, found through the church's website that his residence fell inside the boundaries of the Perifericos Ward. Ward is another word for congregation. He found out that the ward met in a church-built and church-owned meeting house (chapel) in central Arequipa every Sunday from 10:00 a.m. to 1:00 p.m. He attended church and was later interviewed by the bishop of the ward, Bishop Paucar. The interview had many purposes, foremost of which was to ask the contributor's name and birth date so that his records could be transferred from his previous congregation, a Spanish-speaking congregation near the University of California, Irvine, to Perifericos Ward. Another purpose of the interview was to see if the contributor was "worthy" to accept a "calling" or a leadership responsibility within the congregation. Worthiness largely involves avoiding certain activities (fornication, dishonesty, breaking the law of tithing, breaking the health code) and believing certain things (that God the Father and his son Jesus Christ are two separate, corporal beings and that the president of the corporation of the church, "the prophet" is their mouthpiece on the earth today). Often, worthiness interviews involve the bishop reading a list of specific questions to which the interviewee must answer affirmatively to be considered "worthy." In this case, the bishop merely assumed that the contributor was worthy because of the contributor's self-report that he had served a mission for the church in Bolivia 20 years prior. Many Peruvian Mormons consider being a "returned missionary" or "retornado" (in Spanish) to be a sure sign of worthiness. Most Peruvian Mormons who attend church regularly have "callings." Callings are responsibilities thought to come from the mind and will of God himself. God communicates the calling to a leader, and the leader "extends" the calling to the person meant to accept it. The position of "bishop," the highest leadership position in a "ward," is itself a calling rather than a chosen, paid vocation. Theoretically, any adult male in the ward could suddenly be "called" to be

bishop regardless of ecclesiastical training. The contributor was given the calling to be the "First Councilor" in the "Elders Quorum Presidency." Eventually he became the "Elders Quorum President." The Elders Quorum is the organization for males in a congregation above the age of 18. The female counterpart to the Elders Quorum is the Relief Society. From this position, the contributor was able to access different data points of every member of record in the ward, including those "members" who were not yet baptized, which finally gets to the point of this entry. Baptism and subsequent "confirmation" (a ritual conferral of the Gift of the Holy Ghost) are the official rites that bestow church membership to any "worthy" person above age 8. However, a certain level of membership in the church can be assigned shortly after birth if a Mormon parent decides to have his or her child given "a name and a blessing" in a ritual called "a baby blessing." The ideal for this ritual in Peru is that the father of a cohabiting, heteronormative, U.S.-defined nuclear family living in a single-family home take his newborn baby to the front of the sacrament hall shortly after the congregational opening hymn is sung during Sunday worship services, form a circle around the baby with other priesthood-holding males (females cannot hold the priesthood) who will become important in its life (such as uncles and church leaders) and pronounce the words: "Heavenly Father, by the authority of the Melchizedek priesthood which we hold we bring this baby before you to pronounce a name and a blessing. The name by which she/he will be known upon the records of the church is _____, (full name of the baby)." The speaker then often switches from speaking to Heavenly Father in his own voice to talking directly to the baby in the voice of Jesus Christ and blessing it with the fulfillment of all the hopes the father has for it, which often include serving a mission for the church at age 18 or 19 (depending on gender) and finding a "worthy mate" for marriage shortly thereafter. Though this is the ideal among Peruvian Mormons, it is rarely the reality because a nuclear family consisting of a married couple and their young children living in their own home is extremely uncommon in Peru. Many Peruvian "households" involve large, multiplanar, labyrinthine brick and concrete complexes that house married and unmarried adult siblings and their children, in-laws, ageing parents, and other kin without English-equivalent kin terms. Many of these large familial complexes in Peru, and among Peruvian Mormons in Utah, are headed by a central matriarch whereas Mormonism is headed by a central patriarch. This causes an important cultural tension within Peruvian Mormonism. One result of this tension is that, in Peru and among Peruvian Mormons in Utah, there often is no father figure to perform the baby naming ritual, and so it is often conducted by the bishop or other male leader. Children under the age of 8 who attend church and who have been given a "name and a blessing" through the aforementioned ritual appear on the records of the church as unbaptized members of the church and their names are listed on the attendance rolls of either "The Nursery" or "The Primary" organizations for children in their ward.

Assigned by personal choice:

— Yes

Notes: In Mormonism, the idea of "personal choice" is itself a foundational doctrine that creates conflict within Peruvian Mormon congregations. The contributor has written a book chapter about this very issue here: Palmer, Jason. 2020. "Peruvian Mormon Matchmaking: The Limits of Mormon Endogamy at Zion's Border." In *The Routledge Handbook of Mormonism and Gender*, edited by Amy Hoyt and Taylor G. Petrey, 1 edition, 419–31. New York, NY: Routledge. Below is an adapted excerpt of that chapter about the pre-earth nature of the individual and of individual personal choice in Mormonism. It focuses on a Peruvian Mormon single mother named Ofelia whom the contributor met in Perifericos Ward. Ofelia grew up in Arequipa as a Catholic and had a daughter out of wedlock. When her daughter was three, Ofelia met Anglo Mormon missionaries and chose to be baptized into the Mormon church. The excerpt mentions a ritual called a temple "sealing." Sealing is a ritual that can only be performed inside a Mormon temple, which is not to be confused with a chapel (meeting house). Anyone who desires may enter any one of about 20 luxurious, U.S.-style Mormon meeting houses around Arequipa, Peru, but only worthy Mormons with current, valid "temple recommend" cards may enter the multi-million dollar, Anglo Mormon-designed Arequipa temple. Being "sealed" to someone inside the temple means being ritually bound to that person in a relationship that will exist after death. The temple only seals two types of heteronormative, Eurocentric kin relationships: husband-wife, and couple-child. No other relationships, including mother-child, can be sealed in the temple unless they can first be linked to the conjugal couple. This means that Ofelia, being single, cannot be sealed

to her own daughter in what is the most vital of Mormon rituals. This further means she will not be able to be together with her daughter after death unless she can find herself a temple-worthy Mormon husband before death. Excerpt: Mormons, especially when finding a mate for someone they care about, want someone who is not only a Mormon, but a “full” Mormon. In the eyes of many, Ofelia herself does not meet this ambiguous criterion. By virtue of her being baptized at age 24, already a single mother, she was late for the rite of passage most directly connected to the paradox at Zion’s heart—her own birth. She was not “born in the covenant.” In other words, her parents had not been sealed in the temple before she was born. Mormons born to temple-sealed parents come into the world already sealed to those parents. No future sealing rite is necessary. Ofelia missed this rite because she is a first-generation Mormon, or a *conversa* (convert). In much the same way that Indians under British colonialism were seen as “the effect of a flawed colonial mimesis, in which to be Anglicized, is emphatically not to be English” (Bhabha, 1984, 128) *conversos* are sometimes seen as more Mormonized than Mormon. Ofelia rejects this view. OFELIA: A lot of times, before I understood such things, members of the church would always ask us that question, “hey, um, are you of the covenant?” And I would say, “what do you mean ‘of the covenant?’” “I’m just asking if your parents were sealed in the temple and then you were born from them.” “Oh, no then. No, I’m not of the covenant.” “Oh, so you are of the baptized.” “Ah, yes, I guess you’re right because I just got baptized.” And so time went on and during a lot of years they’d always ask that question, “are you of the covenant?” or, “is your daughter of the covenant, was she born in the covenant?” And with sadness or sometimes even shame I would say, “no, my daughter is not of the covenant.” But then I started wondering, “why do they ask that?” And when I studied about it, I said, “what!?” I mean, how dare they make me think that I’m not of the covenant when I’m just as much of the covenant as they are. Those who have been chosen as people of the covenant who have been born in the covenant, and those who accept the gospel after repenting and entering into the baptismal waters, are all equal. Don’t give me any talk about difference and, “we are the real people of the covenant, but since you were baptized it means you were only adopted by us,” it’s not like that. We are all part of the covenant, right? So I don’t see why they have to make differences like that. It’s a stupid question that they start asking ... Sometimes the parents of my seminary students tell me, “my kids were born in the covenant so they already know everything.” Mistake. Right? Gargantuan mistake! Why? Because there are many brothers and sisters, Shannon’s contemporaries, who, while it is true that their parents were sealed in the temple, born in the covenant themselves even, and I guess from inside the womb they were grasping gospel concepts [laughs], BUT their kids have been dishonorably discharged from missions, sometimes not even gone on missions, and their daughters have gone astray and all that, right? So that is why I say emphatically, “no.” I mean, it is not an indispensable requirement that one be of the covenant people, right? What matters is how one goes about guiding one’s kids, whether they were born in the covenant or not. JASON: Is it possible that they think they were born in the covenant because their spirits were more valiant in the preexistence? OFELIA: Of course. It’s not just possible, that is precisely what they think. They think they are more choice spirits, “the elect,” right? They think they’ve been chosen, but—MISTAKE! Ofelia jokes about the womb in her statement against those who look down on her *conversa* status. She makes fun of the idea that one could exercise agency before birth because she knows that this notion is partially from whence the doctrine of “the elect” emerges. Ironically, however, stories of humanity’s pre-birth existence also provide her with pride in being a *conversa*; in using agency to choose Mormonism. After all, Mormonism’s original sibling rivalry, Lucifer versus Jesus, was about agency. Heavenly Father and Heavenly Mother’s second-born spirit son, Lucifer, planned to force human beings to be good inhabitants of the new planet Earth. The first born, Jesus, wanted goodness to be a choice. The two brothers could not find a compromise and fought a primordial war over this question of agency. Those on Earth today with physical bodies fought on the winning side. The losers never got bodies; they are Satan’s demons. There is a divide in Barrio Periféricos between those who think that the more valiant soldiers in the war were rewarded with birth into an already-Mormon family and those who think that choosing Mormonism during Earth-life represents true valiance. In this debate, generational Mormonism becomes a contested requirement for “full” Mormonism. Work Cited: Bhabha, Homi K. 1984. “Of Mimicry and Man: The Ambivalence of Colonial Discourse.” October 28 (Discipleship: A Special Issue on Psychoanalysis): 125-33.

↳ Assigned by class:

— Yes

Notes: Though membership is not deliberately assigned by class, it turns out that most Peruvian Mormons who remain "active" in the church after a few years are upwardly mobile, middle-class urbanites. The reasons for this are complex and have to do with the Mormon ontology of the Western individuated self. One of the four parts of the church's modern mission statement is to preach the gospel to every inhabitant of the earth. However, like any capitalistic enterprise with a mission statement, the church's missionizing program revolves around efficiency and cost-benefit analyses. Its baptisms-per-missionary rate needs to remain high in order for the church to justify opening a new mission in a region. If a person hears about the church through the missionaries, but does not quickly "accept the gospel," that person is often considered to not be "the elect" because, according to one of Mormonism's four canonical books, *The Doctrine and Covenants*, "ye are called to bring to pass the gathering of mine elect; for mine elect hear my voice and harden not their hearts," (section 29 verse 7, <https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/scriptures/dc-testament/dc/29.7?lang=eng&clang=eng#p7>). Speed of gospel acceptance is thus often thought to be a sign of predestination for Mormon membership. Mormonism was founded on the Kantian idea of the self as being an individual subject who thinks and therefore is. In the Andes, on the other hand, my subjecthood only emerges through you. You are connected to me through *ayni* (cyclical reciprocity), therefore I am. In the Andes, whether a human or non-human person is a subject or an object depends on the relational situation, which is neither fixed nor unambiguous. An Andean's personhood did not exist prior to her relationships. A Mormon's personhood (and binary gender) existed prior even to her relationship to God. In order for Andeans to convert to Mormonism, they first have to convert to the conceptions of individuality and subject/object permanence common to Western modernity and eschew their lifeways of collectivity and subject/object ambiguity common to the Andes. This is a slow process. In a Mormon economy focused on scarcity and efficiency, its slowness equates to non-elect status. Since Western modernity is currently hegemonic in much of the world's globalized system of capitalism controlled largely by the U.S., accepting Western modernity is not only the key to Mormon conversion, it is the key to financial success and class ascension in Peru. People in Peru who have accepted Western modernity tend to migrate to cities, stop speaking Quechua, and desire upward mobility and wealth accumulation rather than cyclical reciprocity and wealth diffusion. Since these people have already accepted Western modernity, they accept Mormonism much more quickly than their Quechua-speaking, village-dwelling counterparts. And since these middle-class, Spanish-speaking Peruvians accept Mormonism more quickly, Anglo Mormons consider them "the elect" and focus their missionizing efforts accordingly. When contrasted with Mormonism's conception of indigeneity, this conflation of middle-class status with elect status creates an irony wherein the very people that Mormons are most likely to identify as literal biological descendants of Book Of Mormon prophets are the least likely to hear about that book.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

— Yes

Notes: The ideal age for baptism into the Mormon church is age 8. Children younger than 8 cannot be baptized, though they are still considered members if their parents are members. Age 8 is thought to be "the age of accountability," before which a child is incapable of understanding a law of God and therefore incapable of breaking it (committing sin). Since one of the purposes of baptism is to wash away sins, and since young children are thought to be incapable of sin, young children do not need baptism in order to qualify for heaven. This doctrine is another instantiation of the intensity with which U.S. individualism influenced early Mormonism. It is a reaction to the more collectivist Catholic doctrine that though young children are incapable of committing sin as individuals, they are caught under the collective human sinfulness that the first human, Adam brought into existence when he ate the forbidden fruit. In the Catholic conception, since this sinfulness bars all humans from heaven in the afterlife, and since baptism during this life is the only way to wash away this sinfulness, babies should be baptized as soon after birth as possible just in case they die before getting the chance. Mormonism, in its existential individualism, rejects the notion that the entire family of humans should be forced to face the consequences of actions that each individual in that family did not personally carry out. In fact, the second of the church's 13 articles of faith states: "We believe that men will be

punished for their own sins, and not for Adam's transgression." This question of whether or not children with no personally committed sin should be baptized in order to enter heaven was a common aspect of the anti-Catholic religious discussions happening among the early U.S. frontier religious revival movements from which Mormonism emerged in the early 1800's. The fact that The Book of Mormon projects this specific doctrinal discussion onto the ancient inhabitants of the Americas is often cited as one of the book's many anachronisms by those who seek to disprove its authenticity as a literal translation of ancient text. According to the book, the ancient American prophet, Mormon thought this issue of baptismal age was so important that he wrote about it in a letter to his son, Moroni who, in turn, engraved the letter in its entirety upon one of the few remaining golden plates he was using to summarize the millennial history of pre-Hispanic America. In the letter, almost as an afterthought, Mormon foresees the dawn of an apocalyptic, genocidal war that would eventually take his life and the lives of his entire nation, but the thrust of the letter--a message apparently more important than his people's collective, impending doom--included an angry tirade against child baptism. Mormon wrote (Moroni chapter 8, verses 5-14), 5 For, if I have learned the truth, there have been disputations among you concerning the baptism of your little children. 6 And now, my son, I desire that ye should labor diligently, that this gross error should be removed from among you; for, for this intent I have written this epistle. 7 For immediately after I had learned these things of you I inquired of the Lord concerning the matter. And the word of the Lord came to me by the power of the Holy Ghost, saying: 8 Listen to the words of Christ, your Redeemer, your Lord and your God. Behold, I came into the world not to call the righteous but sinners to repentance; the whole need no physician, but they that are sick; wherefore, little children are whole, for they are not capable of committing sin; wherefore the curse of Adam is taken from them in me, that it hath no power over them; and the law of circumcision is done away in me. 9 And after this manner did the Holy Ghost manifest the word of God unto me; wherefore, my beloved son, I know that it is solemn mockery before God, that ye should baptize little children. 10 Behold I say unto you that this thing shall ye teach--repentance and baptism unto those who are accountable and capable of committing sin; yea, teach parents that they must repent and be baptized, and humble themselves as their little children, and they shall all be saved with their little children. 11 And their little children need no repentance, neither baptism. Behold, baptism is unto repentance to the fulfilling the commandments unto the remission of sins. 12 But little children are alive in Christ, even from the foundation of the world; if not so, God is a partial God, and also a changeable God, and a respecter to persons; for how many little children have died without baptism! 13 Wherefore, if little children could not be saved without baptism, these must have gone to an endless hell. 14 Behold I say unto you, that he that supposeth that little children need baptism is in the gall of bitterness and in the bonds of iniquity; for he hath neither faith, hope, nor charity; wherefore, should he be cut off while in the thought, he must go down to hell.

↳ Assigned by gender:

— No

Notes: Anglo Mormonism is a highly patriarchal and phallogocentric religion, so there are, of course, levels of power within basic church membership that are available only to males (Peruvian Mormonism is somewhat less patriarchal in complex ways that have to do with the predominance of women in Peruvian Mormon congregations and their role as breadwinners in Peruvian Mormon homes). However, basic, official membership is available to both males and females and even, in 2020, to transgender individuals. The 2020 clarification of a transgender individual's standing in the church comes from the same source of most of the church's changes that it considers "administrative" rather than "doctrinal:" what it used to call its Handbook Of Instructions when it was in print form, but what it now calls its General Handbook, which it constantly updates (often without notifying the membership) and makes available here: <https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/manual/general-handbook/title-page?lang=eng> . The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints is designed to be an extremely "modular" religion much like a franchise business, meaning it is designed to be duplicatable in most parts the world and largely impervious to "local culture." One way it achieves this modularity is through its centrally distributed manuals, which run the thematic gamut from financial self-reliance to baptismal interview questions. Anglo Mormons often consider these manuals to be straightforward teachings with no cultural subtext that will have to be deciphered by their non-

Anglo coreligionists throughout the world. However, since the church is centered in Utah and since these manuals are written by situated Utahans influenced by their own local settler-colonist cultures and white logics, the ideas that end up getting duplicated throughout the world as benign "instructions" or even as divine "doctrines" are actually Anglo Mormon cultural norms, constructs, and preferences that are anything but benign when applied to non-Anglo cultural contexts. (listen to this podcast conversation between prominent Mormon scholars Gina Colvin and Caroline Kline as an example: <https://www.athoughtfulfaith.org/caroline-kline-mormon-feminist-theology/>) As such, in the attached manual excerpt, the church uncritically projects the word "transgender" through an Anglo Mormon lens that can only conceive of gender in binary terms. Interestingly, Peruvian Mormons tend to be even more "socially conservative" than their Anglo Mormon church leaders when it comes to questions of gender. Many Peruvian Mormons known to the contributor disagreed vehemently with the very idea of allowing transgender people to even attend church, let alone be baptized. Now that their church has accepted transgender individuals into the waters of baptism, these Peruvian Mormons publicly swallow their disagreement so as not to go against the authority of the church they know to be "true," but they silently suffer through serious cognitive dissonance, feelings of betrayal, feelings of having no control over their own religion, feelings of fear over what change the church is going to make next, and feelings of confusion over how a religion led by an unchangeable God could change so constantly and abruptly. The contributor witnessed many outbursts of this social conservatism among Peruvian Mormons in their Sunday School meetings in both Peru and Utah. One example took place in 2017 during his fieldwork in the Spanish-speaking Pioneer Trail Ward of Salsands, Utah, a congregation that has an usually high percentage of Peruvians (about 30%) among its predominantly Latinx membership. One Sunday, during what is known as the Gospel Principles course taught to new adult members in their first year after baptism, the topic shifted towards abortion. The teacher, a Peruvian female, read from the lesson manual that abortion in the church is allowed, but only in cases of rape. A new member, a Peruvian male, asked how abortion could possibly be justifiable even in cases of rape. Discussion spread to the rest of the class, about 10 students, and revealed that many male and female students felt torn between what they thought was wrong under any circumstances and what their new religion was suddenly telling them was sometimes permissible.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

— Yes

Notes: Membership is achieved through the rite of baptism and, more specifically, through the rite of confirmation that often immediately follows baptism. The correct protocol for baptism is stipulated in manuals published in Utah. However, the Peruvian Mormon rite of baptism, at least in Arequipa, varies slightly from the Anglo Mormon rite. This is a mere technicality, not a huge piece of evidence that a new religion is forming in Peru from the syncretism of Andean Catholicism and Mormonism. Nevertheless, Anglo Mormons in Peru use the Peruvian Mormon addition to the rite as one more piece of ammunition for their case that Peruvians are not capable of self-government. The argument of these Anglo Mormons is that even after 60 years of experience running the church in Peru, Peruvian Mormons still need Anglo supervision, which is why both the Arequipa temple construction site manager and the Arequipa Mission President during the contributor's fieldwork in 2018 were Anglo Mormons flown in from Utah. About 8 of the 20+ Mormon chapels in Arequipa are equipped with a small classroom with shutters that open to reveal a small rectangular baptismal font flanked by steps on either side leading to it from the male and female restrooms. Someone in one of the congregations that uses one of these chapels will have the job ("calling") of scheduling the baptismal font. When the full-time missionaries (often an 18-year-old Utahan paired with an 18-year-old Peruvian) who are temporarily assigned to the congregation have an "investigator" who wishes to be baptized, they confer with the font scheduler and fix a baptismal date. In Perifericos Ward in Arequipa, baptisms invariably took place on Saturdays. There were about two adult baptisms per month during the time the contributor was in Arequipa. Baptismal ceremonies in Perifericos Ward were often very impromptu events. The only vital aspect of the rite is that a baptizer ordained to the office of "priest" say the correct prayer and submerge the baptizee completely under the water in the presence of two adult witnesses. It is not necessary that the baptism be conducted inside a Mormon chapel at all. In fact, early baptisms in Arequipa in the 60's took place in outdoor

thermal pools in nearby Yara. However, as baptism is an important personal life stage event, many other "cultural" additions to the rite itself usually take place. These are fairly standard throughout Mormonism and include a photo shoot with the participants dressed in their white clothing, a gathering of family, friends and congregation members in the small classroom overlooking the font, an opening hymn, a prayer, a speech about baptism by one of the local members, and a speech about the Holy Ghost by another. The baptism itself then takes place and all the people in the small classroom watch. The baptism must be redone if a single hair or piece of clothing from the baptizee does not submerge completely. Once the witnesses give the approving nod that the rite was done correctly, the shutters on the font are closed and the wet participants go change into their dry, Sunday best. While they are changing, the gathered assembly sings Mormon hymns to the tune of European folk songs. Upon the new member's return to the classroom, the bishop of the congregation welcomes the new member as do the presidents of every age and gender-specific sub-organization to which the new member now belongs, such as the Relief Society if the member is a female over the age of 18. As these meetings are often organized by the young full-time missionaries at the last minute, attendance is usually extremely low and it is often difficult for the Bishop or Relief Society president to attend. Nevertheless, since the occasion is a great missionizing tool in that it gives the non-Mormon family members and friends of the baptizee a sacred, solemn experience inside a Mormon edifice, the missionaries always manage to pull off a successful event that culminates in some sort of refreshments usually involving cheese puffs and crackers hastily bought from a nearby kiosk. All of the aforementioned details are practically the same between Anglo Mormonism and Peruvian Mormonism. The principal difference, which is something that was pointed out to the contributor by the Anglo Mormon mission president of Arequipa when he appeared unannounced to supervise a Perifericos Ward baptism (see attached photo), is that Peruvian Mormons tend to close the shutters on the font immediately after the baptism. On this particular occasion, when the Mission President saw them do this he interrupted the proceedings and had his missionaries reopen the shutters saying that it would be nice for people to get photos of the baptizee while she (significantly, the baptizee was female) was fresh out of the water wearing white, wet (and thus sheer) clothing. In a later conversation about this and other similar incidents, another prominent Anglo Mormon in Arequipa explained to the contributor that this font-hiding behavior on the part of Peruvian Mormons was symptomatic of their inability to spiritually discern the difference between Mormon "culture" and Mormon "doctrine," and that this inability was why Anglo Mormons needed to be in Peru. According to him, Peruvians are incapable of understanding the aspects of holiness that make a baptism valid. From the Peruvian Mormon perspective, however, closing the doors on the font is required to meet the demands of corporal modesty that are common sense under Andean norms of decency (see De La Cadena, Marisol. 2000. *Indigenous Mestizos: The Politics of Race and Culture in Cuzco, Peru, 1919-1991*. Durham, NC: Duke University Press Books) regardless of religion. White, wet clothing becomes sheer. So, it is only common sense in the Andes that the font shutters be closed to preserve the baptizee's dignity and modesty. Again, this difference may seem silly, but it is an example of how Peruvians are infantilized for being unable to do the impossible: separate the "vital" from the "cultural" in a religion wherein only Anglo culture determines what is "vital." Peruvians are deemed incapable of self-government because Anglos see them as being unduly influenced by "culture," whereas Anglos see themselves, and their church's doctrine, as being immune to "culture." Anglos do not see themselves as coming from a cultural standpoint at all. Anglos, in their own estimation, come from the standpoint of universal truth, something every competent adult should be able to recognize.

Assigned by some other factor:

—Yes [specify]: contact with Mormon missionaries

Notes: Though official membership on the records of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints is only granted through baptism and subsequent confirmation (a simple ritual wherein a holder of the Melchizedek Priesthood places his hands upon the head of the recent baptizee, says the baptizee's full name and states, "having authority of the Melchizedek priesthood, I confirm you a member of the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints and say unto you, receive the Holy Ghost," then continues with whatever words of encouragement and fortune-telling he feels inspired to say), many people in the Andes consider themselves to be "Mormon"

simply because they had a single encounter with Mormon missionaries or because they happen to have a Book of Mormon in their residence. In this way, they often also consider themselves to be Catholic, Adventist, Jehovah's Witness, and any number of other "religions" along with Mormon. This demonstrates that "religious membership" means something rather different in the Andes than it does for the official Mormon missionaries.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: The Arequipa temple was the global church's 167th dedicated temple and Peru's 3rd. The Lima, Peru temple, dedicated in 1986, was South America's 3rd temple and the world's 38th. Mormon temples must not be confused with every-day Mormon meeting-houses (chapels). Mormon temples are the only places that offer the rites of eternal exaltation (the highest form of salvation), rites that culminate in marriage and that depend on heteronormative, Utah-centric definitions of kinship. For the prophet and president of the church corporation to have selected Arequipa as a temple site and center of a "temple district," local Mormons in the city must have first established an administrative "Zion" to the extent that most of their small congregations (branches) meeting in rented buildings had graduated into larger congregations (wards) meeting in relatively luxurious chapels, architecturally designed in and funded by church headquarters in Salt Lake City, Utah. These wards must have further multiplied enough to be geographically bounded into many, relatively self-governing "stakes of Zion" rather than remaining under one large, Utah-controlled "mission." The conglomeration of these "stakes" (Arequipa has seven) each with their seven or eight wards, must have enough "worthy families" to warrant the multimillion-dollar construction of a temple. Adult Mormons who are "temple worthy" are privileged to make an oath inside their holy temples as part of a ritual called the endowment. They pledge to sacrifice everything, "for the building up of the Kingdom of God on the earth and for the establishment of Zion" (Mormons In Transition 2011, 30). They are then left to define Zion for themselves. On the one hand, Zion claims to be open to all and is supposed to ceremonially bind all humans into a universal kinship. On the other, its ultimate symbol, its architectural culmination, and the only spot of earth where such binding—"sealing"—can be done is the temple, the same temple that is only open to the most "worthy" of Saints. The pinnacle of Zion's inclusiveness lies inside one of the most exclusive buildings on the planet. This foundational paradox does not exist without ramifications for Peruvian Mormon lives. Work Cited Mormons in Transition. 2011. "[1990] The Mormon Temple Endowment Ceremony." Institute for Religious Research. 2011. <http://mit.irr.org/mormon-temple-endowment-ceremony>.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: Every temple has at least two altars.

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: The sites of important occurrences in Anglo Mormon history throughout their series of exoduses from New York to Utah are marked with commemorative plaques, buildings, monuments, and even temples, all owned by the church and often deemed holy or sacred. For example, the Sacred Grove where Joseph Smith is thought to have seen his first vision is owned by the church. On the other hand, the sites of important occurrences in the Book of Mormon that happened in what is now Peru are not marked at all nor does the church officially consider them holy despite the fact that most Peruvian Mormons recognize these sites as sacred places and cite ethnoarchaeological evidence to establish their Book of Mormon authenticity and historicity. Basilio Corimayta, a Peruvian known to the contributor from a small town near Arequipa who has lived in Utah since 1983, knew the Book of Mormon was a true history of Peru the moment he saw it because “there was a TON of coincidence, too much coincidence to not be true.” When asked what some of those coincidences were, he said that in Machu Picchu there is a place called Intihuatana. It looks like a sundial and it is the place where the Inca king tied the sun in the sky for 36 hours so that the people could finish building Cuzco. This night without darkness matches the cosmic sign of Christ’s birth that the Americas received according to the Book of Mormon. Such ethnoarchaeological proofs of the Book of Mormon’s historicity, however, are part of a narrative that is increasingly at odds with the official church which, ironically, desires to distance itself from the idea that the Book of Mormon is a history of the Amerindians with a verifiable geography and sacred places that still exist. The church seeks this distance because the racist paternalism implicit in Lamanite identity is currently clashing with the colorblind, post-racial modernity the church is striving to embrace. Lamanite identity—the very identity the church helped create—has become a public relations problem; something to be mitigated and, if possible, ignored until it goes away. True Lamanites, however, as owners of the Book of Mormon, are not going away. They are adding details to the story, connecting the end of the written narrative to what they see in the ruins of civilizations around them today. As Jacoba Arriátegui, a Peruvian Mormon who has lived in Utah for over 40 years, told the contributor in an interview in December 2017 in the basement of her daughter’s large home in Salsands, Utah: I brought my kids over here [to the U.S. from Peru] when they were very little. They didn’t know Peru. But little by little I am taking them back and teaching them what Peru is and what the ruins are and all the things that are over there. Three years ago I took Arcadio H., my son. We went to Trujillo and he just stood there agape, looking. “Mamá,” he said. “This is [the Book of Mormon city of] Zarahemla.” “Zarahemla?” [I asked]. “What did Zarahemla look like, Mamá? It was a walled city, and what was the width of the walls, Mamá? Because it describes them right there in the Book [of Mormon],” he said. They were almost one meter thick, and the city was right next to the sea. “This is it.” He tells me. “Here you have the ruins of Zarahemla. Look at the walls. Look at the height of the parapets that are so high, and look at how they were described as terminating vertically one by one. It is all here.” ... So I go about teaching my kids little by little and every time I go to Peru I take one with me, or some grandkids, and I go about teaching them the story of the Book of Mormon, “here it is,” I tell them, “Look.” Her husband, Arcadio Costa, was sitting close to her and the contributor watching TV during this interview, but he could not contain himself and chimed in, ARCADIO: Frankly, I had a book. I don’t remember where I left it, but it tells of Incas named Viracocha and Pachacutec. Their God tells them, “here my God was sitting.” The God, what did they call him? He had a name, and with his finger he drew many worlds—and that is a book that is not Mormon—and it says that those many worlds were his. So, what is it that the Book of Mormon teaches us? JASON: That God made many worlds before this one? ARCADIO: Of course. So, how did this Inca know that God had many worlds? It must be that when the Lord came here to the Americas, he arrived over there [in Peru] and not here [in North America]. And he spoke with the Incas and with the Indigenous people that were over there ... So after that, it says that four brothers arrived ... so these were the four Brothers Ayar that it talks about, and one of them stayed in Peru and one went to Mexico in order to establish what they brought, which was much more advanced than what the Incas had. Do you see? The history of Peru is a vast history and it is similar to the Book of Mormon. JASON: Meaning the four brothers would be Nephi, Sam, Laman, and Lemuel? ARCADIO: Yep, but they call them the four Brothers Ayar in their Quechua language, see? JASON: And why do you think that artists of Book of Mormon scenes always depict only Mexico? I mean, you can see Aztec temples in that famous painting with Jesus descending from heaven, as if it all only happened in Mesoamerica, but not in Peru. JACOBA: Because they only know what it’s like close around here: Mexico. The artists only know Mexico but they haven’t exactly studied Peru. They can’t even imagine the grandeur that exists in Peru. They can’t fathom it. Because if they went, they would remember the descriptions of

Zarahemla, what it was like ... And they would enter, and if they relived the scenes of Zarahemla they would find that it is a walled city close to the sea as described. ARCADIO: And in Machu Picchu, we saw with our own eyes the--- JACOBA: ---the baptismal fonts. Jacoba and Arcadio's discussion does not sound like speculation. They are sure that some of the Book of Mormon's events happened in Peru. However, Arcadio and Jacoba are not white. Their surety does not count as official church knowledge. As such, the following 2018 statement from the church—one of the few times an official church publication has used the word "Lamanite" since 1999 to imply contemporary people—came to them as a slap in the face: Just as the history of the northern ten tribes of Israel after their exile in Assyria is a matter of speculation rather than knowledge, the history of the Lamanites after the close of the Book of Mormon record is a matter of speculation. The Church asserts that all members are part of the covenant house of Israel either by descent or adoption but does not take a position on the specific geography of the Book of Mormon or claim a complete knowledge about the origins of any specific modern group in the Americas or the Pacific. (<https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/history/topics/lamanite-identity?lang=eng>) The problem with this declaration's parsing of the terms "speculation" and "knowledge" is that, for the church, white people's speculation is knowledge and Peruvian knowledge is speculation. Were it not so, Peru would be riddled with as many official Mormon devotional markers as the U.S.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

— Yes

Notes: These are Mormon meeting houses, also known as chapels.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

— Yes [specify]: conference centers, institute buildings, etc.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

— Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 1.94

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

— Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

— No

Notes: The term "religious professionals" does not exactly coincide with how Mormons consider church leadership to work, mostly because "professional" implies training and payment. As previously mentioned, church leaders are "called" to hold positions to which they did not apply and for which they are often completely unprepared. The majority of these positions are not exactly paid positions, though members who have received the calling to the "General Authority" level or above on the church's general administration hierarchy do receive extremely lucrative "living stipends" of upwards of 120,000 USD annually. Even these high level officials do not exactly proselyte, so there is certainly no "professional" proselyting force in the church, however, since missionary work is part of the church corporation's official mission statement, all members regardless of their leadership position are expected to "share the gospel" in some way with their family and friends. The church is constantly attempting to market different slogans to motivate its membership to do this. One recent slogan is "every member a missionary." The closest thing to a professional proselyting force would of course be the massive "volunteer" army of full-time Mormon missionaries who proselyte daily throughout the world despite their lack of theological training and lack of remuneration. These missionaries, distinguished from the general membership by being deemed "full-time missionaries" do, in fact, apply to be placed in the

position of full-time missionary, which is but one of many factors that make their "calling" different than any other in the church.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

— No

Notes: This answer represents a salient component of the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints' foundational patriarchy and contemporary misogyny. "Mandated" is a strong word, but for all intents and purposes, young males who are "worthy" and "able" are mandated to serve a full-time proselyting mission for two years sometime between the ages of 18 and 26. Full-time missionaries are not considered to be "paid" because they receive a living stipend instead of a wage. That living stipend comes from a fund that they themselves, their parents, or their congregations pay into along with all the other missionaries, their parents, and their congregations throughout the world. For this reason, the full-time Mormon mission is always considered "self-funded" though some missionaries put far more into the fund than they get out and some get out far more than they put in. Females are not mandated to serve a full-time mission and, in fact, do not even have the option to serve until age 19, one year after their male counterparts. If they do serve, they may only serve 1.5 years. In many local instances of Mormonism, such as that observed by the contributor in 2018 in Perifericos Ward in Arequipa, Peru, the mandate for males to serve a mission one year younger than females and return a half year later implies that a female's true mission is to marry one of these males once he becomes a "returned missionary" (retornado) at age 20. In this sort of cultural context, the hope is that, in the extra year she waits to serve a mission, a female will marry a retornado instead of serving a mission herself. The result is that, in Peru even more than in Utah, retornadas (female returned missionaries) are stigmatized. Retornadas in Arequipa, Peru are always surrounded by the unasked, yet palpable question, "why did you go on a mission instead of getting married?" While mission service is stigmatizing to females, the failure to serve a mission is stigmatizing to males. In Peruvian Mormonism, males who are not retornados are not considered full persons in their religious society, even when the reason for their lack of retornado status stems from their finding out about Mormonism in the first place after age 26 when it was too late for them to serve a full-time mission. The result is a paradoxical situation wherein retornados do not want to marry retornadas and retornadas only want to marry retornados. This situation represents one of the many unintended consequences of the social engineering to which the church resorts in order to enforce the nuclearization of family and delegitimize the traditional Peruvian notion of family. Importantly, the only other time when Mormons can serve full-time proselyting missions also points to the church's delegitimization of the Peruvian family. Mormons can serve full-time proselyting missions as elderly, retired couples with no dependent kin living at home (an "empty nest"). The church places great importance and emphasis on these elderly "couples missions" and so Peruvians, who almost never have the type of nuclear familial situation that results in an "empty nest," feel like they come up short of full "Saint" status within Mormonism's global community. Also, "couples missions" do not get to tap into the church's global missionary fund, meaning they must truly be self-funded, which also disqualifies most Peruvians.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

— No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

— No

Notes: As previously mentioned, conducting missionary work in one's day to day life outside of one's time as a full-time missionary is highly encouraged, but not mandated. For example, questions involving one's missionary efforts are not found on the list of questions to which one must answer affirmatively if one wishes to be considered "worthy" to enter a Mormon temple. The things that are required for temple worthiness are the things that many Mormons would consider "mandated." Mormons who have this temple worthiness hold a physical "temple recommend," a card with an expiration date, a bar code, and the signature of their local

ecclesiastical leader, which the male gatekeeper of each temple uses to quickly verify temple worthiness.

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– Yes

Notes: Since the majority of proselyting in Peru is carried out by small cohesive groups of young, Anglo Mormon males who are out of their parents' home for the first time in their lives, a sort of militaristic, "Lord Of The Flies" group mentality often develops that can make proselyting highly coercive and corrosive in much the same way that a similar mentality can make individual military platoons highly callous towards the suffering of non-combatants (see <https://apps.dtic.mil/dtic/tr/fulltext/u2/a490174.pdf>.) Since the proselyting efforts of young, full-time missionaries often involve extended periods with little to no oversight from their new parental figures--the often elderly, often Anglo, mission president "and his wife," (the position of "Mission President" is a male-only, three year "calling," which often requires the candidate to uproot himself from Utah and move with his wife, and sometimes coresident children, to the same foreign country where he served a full-time mission as a youth)--these missionaries sometimes channel the latent racism and misogyny of their church into overtly racist and misogynistic practices of psychological coercion. This can be especially troubling when two male Anglo missionaries target a female Peruvian for conversion. In one such instance known to the contributor, Anglo Mormon missionaries in Arequipa stalked a young arequipeña woman for weeks. She finally succumbed to baptism just so that they would stop stalking her. Her nominal membership seemed to satisfy them as they never bothered her after that even though she never attended church. However, through a miraculous experience involving two different Anglo Mormon missionaries twenty years later who were not at all coercive, she became an "active" member of a Mormon congregation. The first set of missionaries were probably satisfied at merely baptizing her without actually "converting" her because of the pressure in some missions, often fomented by specific mission presidents, to increase "mission stats" such as baptisms, hours of proselyting, and hours spent teaching in the homes of "investigators." For more tactics that Mormon missionaries have used in the past to meet the demands of the pressure to increase statistics, see this article about "baseball baptisms" wherein, unbeknownst to them, youth joined the U.S. religion of Mormonism when what they thought they were doing was joining a league for the U.S. sport of baseball (<https://www.sunstonemagazine.com/pdf/093-30-44.pdf>)

↳ Does the coercion take the form of physical force:

– No

↳ Does the coercion take the form of economic sanctions:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: Under the sense of "official" that the Peruvian government reserves for the Catholic church, Peru does not "officially" support the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints and neither does the state government of Utah. In practice however, the church exerts powerful influence over the governments of both places. In Utah, the church is so rooted in the government that law makers can essentially do nothing without its tacit permission (as this LA Times article attests: <https://www.latimes.com/archives/la-xpm-1993-03-21-mn-13641-story.html>). In Peru, the church seeks a similar relationship to the one it has with Utah and it constantly works towards this through periodic public displays of charitable donations, which generate a debt of gratitude, and through widely publicized meetings with Peruvian heads of state (see attached article). It is known to the contributor through a conversation with the Arequipa temple construction site manager that Peru's Ministry of Culture changed a nation-wide law regarding zoning restrictions in archaeological sites just so that the Arequipa temple could be built atop ancient pre-Incan terracing.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Some public spaces

Notes: As to iconography in homes: Family home evening, also called “Family Night” was an initiative started by the church in the 1960’s—complete with a manual—wherein nuclear families are supposed to drop social, professional, and even ecclesiastical affairs one night a week, preferably Monday, and spend time together singing, studying scriptures, and, most of all, having “wholesome recreational activities” (<https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/scriptures/the-family-a-proclamation-to-the-world/the-family-a-proclamation-to-the-world?lang=eng> , incidentally, that link will take you to a document that is perhaps the most common form of iconography on the walls of Peruvian Mormon homes. It is a single-page document called THE FAMILY A PROCLAMATION TO THE WORLD and it can be found framed or pinned up in the homes of most Peruvian Mormons, see photo). In Utah this has become a consumerist extravaganza. Not only do most movie theaters, bowling alleys, and “fun zones” advertise Monday “Family Night” specials, but LDS bookstores, such as the church-owned Deseret Book, sell all kinds of Book of Mormon-themed Family Night games and supplies. One popular Deseret Book item the contributor has seen on the walls of many Peruvian Mormons in Utah is a peg board whereupon the hand-painted names of family members are cycled weekly through Family Night’s different roles. Any visitor to the home during the week will see that it is Tatiana’s turn to say the opening prayer, Mamá’s turn to decide on the activity, Junior’s turn to give the lesson, and Papá’s turn to provide the refreshments. Family Night, therefore, not only gives Utah businesses a chance to demonstrate their Mormon-friendliness, it gives Mormon families a material way (home décor) to show off their dedication to achieving the only social grouping that is legible in Mormonism as “family.” Peruvians in Peru—who are constantly being joined by new converts to Mormonism—feel they come up short in catching the spirit of this nuclear family culture, so they often combine many families together for Family Night in order to teach the new and potential members among them how it is to be done.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Church iconography runs a wide gamut. Everything is fare game from replicas of Book of Mormon objects, such as the animate brass compass Lehi used to navigate from the Middle East to the Americas, to the mark of the compass sewn into Mormon sacred, white undergarments. However, as far as church meeting houses go, the church recently (May 2020) mandated that only a few dozen paintings would be approved for display on foyer walls. Every single one of the approved paintings depicts a white, Nordic-looking Jesus.

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):
– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:
– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):
– Yes

↳ Humans:
– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:
– Yes

Notes: One distinguishing characteristic of Peruvian Mormon iconography is that Jesus is depicted as strikingly, anachronistically white. This of course stems from the church's official representations of Jesus. As Kwame Ture said, the church takes its racism "to such ludicrous heights that it paints Jesus Christ white even though he never put his foot in Europe" (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yQrDBZfDjZA>). It is interesting to note that Mormon depictions of Jesus by successful Anglo Mormon artists in Utah sometimes become so popular in Peru that their art is used by other churches, even ones that are quite antagonistic to Mormonism. The Anglo artist does not know his art is being used in Peru and the Peruvian does not know that the art is Mormon. In a particularly ironic example, the contributor noted that in Arequipa, many Catholic homes have stickers on their windows with different phrases and imagery warning any oncoming missionaries that they are Catholic and will not be baptized into any new sect. One such door posted "we are Catholic here" under the image of a Nordic Jesus painted by famous Mormon artist Greg Olson. <https://www.google.com/search?hl=EN&gl=US&tbm=isch&q=Greg%20Olson%20Jesus>

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In theory, Peruvian Mormonism's stance on apostasy is the same as that of the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints' official stance, which can be found on its web page here: <https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/manual/gospel-topics/apostasy?lang=eng> . The church's definition of apostasy is far broader than that which this database gives for apostasy: the complete, public abandonment of the religion. According to the church, apostasy can involve straying from the laws of Mormonism even while faithfully believing in those laws. Under this definition, all Mormons are in constant danger of apostasy and the line at which a Mormon has crossed over into apostasy changes positions almost as often as the church's General Handbook. In 2015, a handbook change stipulated that a believing, practicing Mormon who entered into a same-sex marriage was suddenly an apostate. There are punishments meted out for cases of apostasy by official church courts convened at the "stake level," a local level of ecclesiastical hierarchy made up of leaders who oversee seven or eight congregations. This means that the punishments for different apostasies can be catered to local circumstances. However, at the worldwide church level, the "mandatory minimum" punishment for this sort of same-sex marriage apostasy was that the children of the offending parties could not be baptized until age 18 and until they officially renounced their parents' lifeways. Many congregations throughout Peru, which usually tend to

ignore changes in church policy, celebrated this new stance against homosexuality by printing out the Spanish translation of the new handbook change and displaying it on hallway bulletin boards inside Mormon chapels. However, due to the U.S. public outcry against the church and the hit it took in the U.S. media over what the media took to be an arcane display of homophobia, the church softened its stance on same-sex marriage, calling it a "serious transgression" instead of "apostasy" (see attached article from The Atlantic). In the Perifericos Ward that the contributor joined in 2018 in Arequipa, Peru in order to study Peruvian Mormonism ethnographically, he became privy to the apostasy sentences that a few male members of the congregation were serving. The congregation had about 400 people of all ages and genders on its membership roles, but only about 150 of these participated in congregational activities with any regularity. Of those 150 "active" members of the congregation, about 25 were males above the age of 18. These 25 made up the Elder's Quorum. As the contributor was the "Elder's Quorum President," he came to know the personal situations of 4 of his quorum members who were undergoing punishments for varying levels of apostasy. At the time, the official church had two basic terms for apostasy-court sentencing: disfellowshipment and excommunication. Disfellowshipment, as interpreted by the bishop of Perifericos Ward, could include any number of punishments ranging from not being able to take the sacrament (the Eucharist) to not being able to volunteer to give the opening prayer to begin a Sunday School class. Excommunication, on the other hand, is a much more serious verdict in official Mormonism and precludes participation of any kind in church services, including paying tithing or even asking a question during Sunday School. The excommunicant's priesthood is rescinded as is his/her official membership in the church. At the end of an ambiguous length of time, the excommunicant must be rebaptized into the church in order to leave the state of apostasy. Seeing a congregation wherein 4 out of 25 males are paying the official price for apostasy (usually because of matrimonial infidelity) is common in Peru but almost unheard of in Utah. The reason for this is not so much that serious transgressions are not being committed by Mormon males in Utah, but because Peruvian church leaders in Peru do not feel it is appropriate to read between the lines or "bend" the rules stipulated in church handbooks and manuals. Anglos, on the other hand, since they come from the culture that wrote these manuals, feel much more comfortable giving the rules a lenient interpretation when it suits them. And, in the gentleman's club that is the Anglo Mormon Elders Quorum (of which the bishop is technically also a member), it does not suit leaders to mete out heavy punishments against their buddies whom, at any moment, might be called to replace them as leaders. Recently, there have been a few high-profile excommunications in the church for the sin of "apostasy." For example, Kate Kelly was excommunicated for her advocacy of female priesthood ordination (<https://www.nytimes.com/2014/06/24/us/Kate-Kelly-Mormon-Church-Excommunicates-Ordain-Women-Founder.html> .) Many Mormons become "apostates" simply because they no longer believe in the church. In many such cases, though they cannot be officially punished because the church no longer holds any authority over them that they personally recognize as legitimate, they remain as members of companies, families, or governments wherein their church does wield significant power. These apostates often lose their jobs (many Peruvian Mormons in Peru are employed by the corporation of the church, and such employment is often contingent not only upon their continued orthodoxy, but upon their continued temple worthiness), civic positions, and even families. In addition to this, former Mormons are collectively punished through continual church discourses espoused at locally, regionally, and globally broadcast conferences communicated to them through their Mormon friends and family. These discourses trivialize the reasons Mormons leave the church and even, in the case of a July 26, 2020 Facebook Live broadcast meant for Mormon youth in Chile, Argentina, Uruguay, and Paraguay, insult the intelligence of Mormons and former Mormons whose value systems do not precisely match those outlined in the General Handbook (for a particularly blatant example of this, see Brad Wilcox's contribution to the conference beginning at minute 43 https://www.facebook.com/NoticiasIglesiaDeJesucristo/videos/647636839178816/?notif_id=1595797254670376¬if_t=live_video_explicit&ref=notif)

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Yes

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– Yes

Notes: Apostates can lose membership in their families. If an apostate is an employee of the church, as many Peruvian Mormons are, he or she could lose wealth.

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– Yes

↳ Punished in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Cursed by "high god":

– Yes

↳ Cursed by other supernatural being(s):

– No

↳ Other divine punishment:

– Yes [specify]: inability to exist in a "whole" family after death

Notes: This serves to not only punish the apostate, but to punish the apostate's entire family and lineage of antecedents and descendants. Such a familial disruption causes staunchly Mormon families to place even more stigma upon apostates during life.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints has an extremely complex organizational system that includes hierarchies within hierarchies and other hierarchies that don't quite fall within hierarchies. Part of this complexity stems from the fact that the church is both a religion and a multi-billion dollar corporation. Another part of the complexity stems from the fact that the male-controlled "priesthood" or the power and authority to act in the name of God on the earth, has its own confusing hierarchy that is somewhat different from the church administration hierarchy and that works with hierarchies of other organizations, such as the female-led Relief Society, that are seen as mere appendages to it. Males who come to church fairly regularly for one year pretty much automatically become priesthood holders whereas females with degrees in theology who strive their hardest every day to be the best Mormons they can be cannot hold

the priesthood at all. In broad strokes, every congregation with enough Melchizedek priesthood holders to be considered a "ward" rather than a "branch" is led by a male bishop and his two male councilors. Seven or eight wards, each led by their respective bishops, fall under the jurisdiction of a stake president, his councilors, and his High Council made up of 12 men who also make up a church disciplinary court in cases of suspected apostasy. In Arequipa, Peru, all of these positions are usually occupied by Peruvians. To understand the higher levels of the hierarchy, it is perhaps best to focus on a particular person. Let us take the Peruvian Mormon named Simon as an example. Simon was an "Area Authority Seventy" meaning he was in the administrative rung that liaises between stake presidents in Peru (currently mostly Peruvians) and the three "General Authority Seventies" (currently one Mexican-American, one Anglo-American, and one Italian-Guatemalan) who preside over the South America Northeast Area (Bolivia, Colombia, Ecuador, Peru, and Venezuela). These General Authority Seventies report directly to the Quorum of the Twelve Apostles in Salt Lake City (currently ten Anglo Americans, one German American, and one German Brazilian) who, in turn, report to The First Presidency (currently all Anglo Americans) made up of the prophet (who is also the president of the church corporation) and his two councilors (also considered apostles along with the prophet, meaning that at any one time, there are technically 15 apostles). All these roles are ecclesiastical "callings," not paid church corporation posts, however, those at or above the General Authority Seventy level receive extremely hefty "living stipends" while those at or below the Area Authority Seventy level do not. Aside from these "unpaid" ecclesiastical positions, there are thousands of paid positions within the church corporation. For example, there is a research division within the church that gainfully employs around 40 social scientists with PhD's.

↳ A single leader of a local community:

— No

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

— No

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

— Yes

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

— No

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

— Yes

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

— Number of levels [numeric value]: 8

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

— Yes

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– Yes

Notes: Mormonism has a strong sense that males who currently hold the priesthood, which comes with power, were preordained to it through the laying on of hands in a pre-Earth life that Mormons call the preexistence. As the ancient American prophet Alma proclaimed in the Book of Mormon (Alma chapter 13 verse 3): "And this is the manner after which they were ordained—being called and prepared from the foundation of the world according to the foreknowledge of God, on account of their exceeding faith and good works; in the first place being left to choose good or evil; therefore they having chosen good, and exercising exceedingly great faith, are called with a holy calling, yea, with that holy calling which was prepared with, and according to, a preparatory redemption for such."

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

Notes: Though this common Mormon belief is not at all supported by Mormon scripture and is, in fact, often contradicted by it, many Mormons of all nationalities believe that the highest of their church's leaders, namely the prophet and president of the church, his councilors, and the 12 apostles, were "called" to occupy those positions as a result of their "righteousness." Righteousness in Mormonism tends to be a complex amalgamation of obedience to Mormon commandments, a strong work ethic, a faithfulness to U.S.-defined nuclear family values and relationships, and modest, but significant, displays of financial success.

↳ Powers are inherited:

– Yes

Notes: This is a very complex aspect of Mormon kinship, but yes, there is a sense that leadership positions and the powers that come with them can be inherited. For example, it is thought that those who are literal biological descendants of the Israelite tribe of Levi are destined to become bishops. Also, regardless of the mysteries of Mormon lineages that are simultaneously both biological and spiritual, the fact is that the upper hierarchies of the church, and the powers inherent to them, are often kept within a few of Utah Mormonism's founding families.

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– Yes

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– Yes

Notes: This is the most definitive of the many complex "yes" answers in this section. Technically, upon the death of the current prophet and president of the church (who, at the time of writing, is 94 years old), any ordinary "worthy" Mormon male could suddenly be "called" to be the prophet. Once in the position of prophet, he will take upon himself the "mantle" of his office and become a seer and a revelator, suddenly able to see into the future and predict calamities. In reality, this has never happened. A standing member of the quorum of the 12 apostles as always been called to be the next prophet, and, arguably, no prophet since Joseph Smith, Mormonism's first, has really ever prophesied. However, seeing a man ascend from the ordinary to the extraordinary does occasionally happen in the case of the calling of a bishop. He who is in the position of bishop,

regardless of his complete lack of supernatural powers prior to becoming bishop, will suddenly have what Mormons call the "power of discernment." This power comes to men who are bishops and leaves them when they are no longer bishops. The power involves the ability to essentially read an interviewee's mind and discern whether or not the person is lying in their answers to the temple recommend interview questions. Incidentally, Peruvian Mormon would-be immigrants to Utah often consider the U.S. embassy official in charge of granting them a tourist visa to also have this same power of discernment.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: They are chosen by God.

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

Notes: It may appear to unbelievers that this is the case, but from a faithful perspective, the leader is chosen by God.

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– No

Notes: God is thought to choose the leaders.

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

Notes: Again, God chooses the leader, however local and global bodies of church members occasional "sustain" their leaders in a ritual that serves as a symbolic unanimous vote. Members raise their right hands in favor of the leader's election. Members are then asked if there are "any opposed" to the leader's election. In answer, they keep their hands down. The leader asking for the vote then reports to all present that the election has been unanimous. In the extremely rare cases where there are "any opposed," the opposing party is supposed to be called aside after the meeting and asked the grounds of their opposition. To the knowledge of the contributor, never once have these grounds actually precluded the election of a local or global leader in the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints.

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

Notes: This is believed to be the primary part of the selection process.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: Technically, they are considered fallible, especially at the local level. However, there is a strong sense that the men who occupy the upper three echelons of the church (the quorum of the 12 apostles, the prophet's two councilors, and especially the prophet himself) are infallible and that they speak the direct word of God. Church scriptures promise that church leaders will never lead members astray. Some members take this literally and some do not. Here is an example from one of the contributor's interviews with the Peruvian Mormon named Ofelia Dominguez in Arequipa in 2018. OFELIA: They called Shannon [Ofelia's daughter] in to an interview. The bishop was bothered because she is going out with Ayzo. Not just the bishop either, his councilors, everyone is against her going out with him, and so she came back from her interview badly affected. And she expressed to me her sadness and said, "Mamá, I don't understand why so much resentment against Ayzo on the part of my leaders. They told me roundly, 'we want you to stop seeing him completely.' But what I feel--- Mamá, I have prayed and I feel like he is a good young man and I want to go out with him." And I took this opportunity and said, "what do you think now after hearing from the bishop and listening to his councilors?" And she is a little close-minded at times, "no, if my leader tells me something, it is for a reason, Mamá, so I am going to pay heed." "Oh, really? Okay, so you are going to tell him that you aren't going to see him anymore?" "Yes, Mamá, I have to because my leader told me so." "Oh, really? And how do you feel about that, I mean, what do you feel inside yourself?" "But it's that, Mami, I really like him, I feel something very special." "Okay then, even though you feel something very special for him, you are going to throw that all away just because your bishop and his councilors told you to? You are going to stop going out with him?" "Yes, I know it is for the best because they are my leaders and they are counseling me for my benefit." "Alright, sounds perfect then," I told her, "but, you know what? The leaders are human beings, and they make mistakes and sometimes we as humans judge based on certain things, and we judge people as well. And do you know that they don't know Ayzo perfectly? Do you think for one second that if I knew that he was a disobedient young man and that he was really bad for you, that I would permit you to go out with him? I am your mother," I told her. "I know that young man, and you know it." "But my bishop said!" And she started to cry. I told her, "look. Pray. The bishop can tell you many things, but tell the Lord. What will the Lord tell you? You are forgetting that you are a missionary, that you have been a missionary, so make your decision, pray to the Lord. The leaders make mistakes, Hijita." And so she started to study, and she prayed and the next day when she woke up, I asked her, "And? What did you think?" She said, "Mami. I am going to keep going out with him." "Alright, are you sure?" "Yes, Mamá." The above interview excerpt was also published here: Palmer, Jason. 2020. "Peruvian Mormon Matchmaking: The Limits of Mormon Endogamy at Zion's Border." In *The Routledge Handbook of Mormonism and Gender*, edited by Amy Hoyt and Taylor G. Petrey, 1 edition, 419–31. New York, NY: Routledge.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and

unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Notes: The contributor has chosen to mark "no" only because "required" is a strong word as is "all matters." But, effectively, disciples are required to--as they say and as their children sing--"follow the prophet, he knows the way." https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/music/library/childrens-songbook/follow-the-prophet?lang=eng&_r=1

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Obligatory for some

Notes: The full-time Mormon mission (obligatory for "worthy" "able" males between the ages of 18 and 26) is a pilgrimage in every anthropological sense of the term. From the opening of the "mission call" envelope wherein Mormon teenagers discover together with their family the exotic or familiar world city God has reserved specifically for their evangelizing impact, the Mormon mission is both a pilgrimage and a rite of passage. For Catholics, sites are often considered sacred because a localized miracle is an announcement that "worship is to be rendered in a place" (Weibel 2005, 116). For followers of the New Age, "the planet Earth gives off energy that is stronger in some places than in others" (116). The founders of anthropological pilgrimage studies, Edith and Victor Turner, consider pilgrimage to these sacred sites a ritualistic and "liminal phenomena" (Turner 1979) in that it fosters *communitas*, or the space between the structures of society. Pilgrims seek the liminoid, or some kind of contact in the sacred center beyond social structure. Pilgrimage is, among other things on the Turners' list, "movement from a mundane center to a sacred periphery which suddenly, transiently, becomes central for the individual, an axis mundi of his faith" (Turner & Turner 2011, 34). The central purpose of sending Mormon youth to serve missions in places not of their choosing, places peripheral to their experience, is to give the missionaries, not the missionized, an axis mundi of faith. These missionaries, as pilgrims, achieve "direct contact with the sacred" (Winkelman & Dubisch 2005, xxiii) "unmediated by holy church powers and representatives" (xxii). In fact, one of God's mouthpieces on earth today, a member of The Quorum of The Twelve Apostles, tried to explain his lack of mediation in the process whereby full-time Mormon missionaries (his audience for the following quotation) are assigned their own personal sacred place to missionize. In those sessions when I ... participate in deciding [which missionary] the Lord would call [to which mission], I simply would say this to you: That you be careful. If there is anyone in this room who is saying, "I wonder if I was called by mistake," or "I wonder if that's really the place for me," I just warn you: You be careful! I'll just tell you, no member of The Twelve called you. It was not a human choice. It was not a computer that did it. I'll just tell you that of all the experiences I've had of having the mind of the Lord made fairly clear—or VERY clear—nothing compares to the experience of those moments of missionaries being assigned. (Eyring 2011, min. 0:49) God himself selects the place where each missionary is to go, meaning that the mission area is an intimately personal holy land for each missionary. This makes the mission a pilgrimage. However, the Mormon mission is also a textbook rite of passage as if lifted directly from the pages of Arnold Van Gennep's (1961) book *The Rites of Passage* where "the liminal period" between "rites of separation" and "rites of incorporation" was coined. The young missionary is first put through a ritual, called the "setting apart," after which the missionary remains apart until being ritually "released" post mission. During this "apart" time they may not embrace members of the opposite sex, even kin, and their telecommunication with kin is severely restricted. The entire 1.5 to 2-year mission (depending on gender) is the liminoid in many of the ways Victor Turner (1979) outlines: The neophytes are empty vessels into which the doctrine of their society (in this case, church) is poured, if they do not "return with honor" (see attached photo) after having completed their full mission period (tour of duty) they become nonpersons in their society (especially if they are male, see Doty et. al. 2015), they are at the complete mercy of their mission president, and (again, similar to the military) they have nothing "to demarcate them structurally from their fellows" (234). Mormon missionaries must stay with their assigned "companion" at all times except to go to the restroom.

Companion assignments change every few months. Today, Peruvians are almost always called to serve missions within Peru where they are likely to have ten different companions during their mission. Five of those will likely be from Peru, Bolivia or Chile, five will likely be from the U.S., and two or three of those five will likely be from Utah (see attached photo). Often, in interviews with the contributor, Peruvian Mormons who live in Utah include in their migration story the fact that they had "friends" in Utah with whom they stayed when they first arrived from Peru. Pedro is a case in point. The Anglo friends Pedro mentioned having in Utah were his former mission companions who, having gone through the same rite of passage, became his blood-brothers (soldiers from the same platoon). Companionships receive identical living stipends and eat and dress the same though one companion be from cosmopolitan Sundance, Utah and the other be, as Pedro was, from a *barriada* (ghetto) in Lima without running water. This temporarily equalizing aspect of the mission fosters *communitas* in the world-wide "Mormon supranation" (Knowlton 2008) through the liminality of missionary work and the "homogeneity and comradeship" (Turner 1969, 82) it engenders. However, the *communitas* in a mission companionship consisting of a Utahan and a *limeño* is not created from an equitable fusion of U.S. and Peruvian cultures. The culture of Mormonism's global "imagined community" (Anderson 2006, title) or universal supranation—what Mormons unironically call "gospel culture" (Oaks 2012, title)—is seen by outsiders as essentially the culture of 1950's rural Utah (O'Dea 1957), of U.S. settler-coloniality (Taylor 2000) and of capitalist ambition (Ong 2003). In this sense, there is nothing "Peruvian" about it. Nevertheless, since Mormons imagine gospel culture to be a placeless, divine construct, they believe it accrues as "cultural capital" (Bourdieu 1994) in the socio-spiritual bank accounts of all Mormons regardless of nationality. This placeless universality does not mean gospel culture is not implicitly centered around the place of Utah in the minds of many Mormons, it simply means that all Mormons, marked and unmarked, should, in theory, be able to fully live gospel culture even though doing so may, in practice, require immigrating to Utah. When Pedro returned from his mission, the shock of inequality from sudden re-entry into Peruvian structure motivated him to immigrate to Utah wherein the bulk of his blood-brotherhood and cultural capital had now coalesced.

Works Cited (in order of appearance)

Weibel, Deana L. 2005. "Of Consciousness Changes and Fortified Faith: Creativist and Catholic Pilgrimage at French Catholic Shrines." In *Pilgrimage and Healing*, edited by Jill Dubisch and Michael Winkelman, 111–34. Tucson, AZ: University of Arizona Press.

Turner, Victor. 1979. "[1967] *Between and Between: The Liminal Period in Rites de Passage*." In *Reader in Comparative Religion: An Anthropological Approach*, edited by William Armand Lessa and Evon Zartman Vogt, 234–43. New York: Harper & Row.

Turner, Victor, and Edith Turner. 2011. [1978] *Image and Pilgrimage in Christian Culture*. New York: Columbia University Press.

Winkelman, Michael, and Jill Dubisch. 2005. "Introduction: The Anthropology of Pilgrimage." In *Pilgrimage and Healing*, edited by Jill Dubisch and Michael Winkelman, ix–xxxvi. Tucson, AZ: University of Arizona Press.

Eyring, Henry. 2011. *Poderoso Mensaje a Los Misioneros*. Presidente Eyring. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3c8fQM9vsiU>.

Van Gennep, Arnold. 1961. [1908] *The Rites of Passage*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Doty, Kristine J., S. Zachary Bullock, Harmony Packer, Russell T. Warner, and James Westwood. 2015. "Return with Trauma: Understanding the Experiences of Early Returned Missionaries." *Issues in Religion and Psychotherapy* 37 (1, article 9): 33–45.

Knowlton, David. 2008. "Go Ye to All the World: The LDS Church and the Organization of International Society." In *Revisiting Thomas F. O'Dea's The Mormons: Contemporary Perspectives*, edited by Cardell K. Jacobson, John P. Hoffmann, and Tim B. Heaton, 390–412. Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press.

Turner, Victor. 1969. *The Ritual Process: Structure and Anti-Structure*. Aldine.

Anderson, Benedict. 2006. [1983] *Imagined Communities: Reflections on the Origin and Spread of Nationalism*. London ; New York: Verso.

Oaks, Dallin H. 2012. "The Gospel Culture." *The Ensign of the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter Day Saints*, 2012.

O'Dea, Thomas F. 1957. *The Mormons*. 1st Edition edition. The University of Chicago Press.

Taylor, Lori Elaine. 2000. "Telling Stories about Mormons and Indians." PhD diss., State University of New York at Buffalo.

Ong, Aihwa. 2003. *Buddha Is Hiding: Refugees, Citizenship, the New America*. Berkeley: University of California Press.

Bourdieu, Pierre. 1994. "Social Capital: Preliminary Notes." In P. Bourdieu: *Sociological Texts*, edited by Nikos Panagiotopoulos, 91–95. Athens: Delfini.

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: 95% of Peruvians consistently identified as Catholic from 1910 to 1970. This number dropped to 76% by 2014 (Pew Research Center. 2014. Religion in Latin America). Most Peruvians who stop identifying as Catholic adopt other religious identities, many of which were founded in the U.S., such as Pentecostal, Seventh-Day Adventist, Jehovah's Witness, and of course, Mormon. This creates a competitive environment among all these religions, but it creates a special tension with Catholicism, the only religion taught in Peruvian public schools and the only religion that the Peruvian government subsidizes. The cultural contact between Mormonism and the Catholic church remains mildly competitive, but when The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints first entered Peru in earnest in 1956, the opposition of the Catholic church was reportedly quite fierce. Evidence for this is included in "Relevant Online Primary Textual Corpora" under the descriptor "Anti-Mormon Collection" and includes some of the myriad forms of anti-Mormon propaganda the Catholic church published and distributed in Arequipa, Peru in the early 1960's. To give an idea of the threat that the Mormon church represented in the imagination of Archbishop of Arequipa, Leonardo Rodriguez Ballon, a lengthy letter he read aloud in Arequipa's main cathedral in the Plaza de Armas meant to prepare his parishioners for Vatican II was solely about the evils of Mormonism. The letter (included in its entirety above) is simply titled, "In Defense of the Faith."

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The cultural contact between the Catholic church and the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints in Arequipa, Peru vacillates between antagonistic and accommodating. For example, in 1962, the Archbishop of Arequipa read the aforementioned, anti-Mormon letter and had it published in installments throughout all of Arequipa's major news outlets. In 2017, on the other hand, Archbishop of Arequipa, Javier del Rio Alba was a VIP guest at the groundbreaking ceremony of the Mormon church's Arequipa temple dedication in the staunchly Catholic town of Carmen Alto. This Archbishop was instrumental in convincing the local parishioners of Carmen Alto to stop protesting the construction of a Mormon temple in their vicinity. According to a private conversation between the Arequipa temple construction site manager (an Anglo Mormon from Colorado, U.S.A) and the contributor that took place on March 23, 2018, Archbishop Javier del Rio Alba has discoursed together with Mormon apostle Dallin H. Oaks at "religious freedom" conferences in the U.S. and elsewhere. For Oaks, "religious freedom" is a euphemism for the freedom to discriminate against LGBTQI+ communities, and his partnership with a Catholic archbishop is representative of the greater ideological common ground the Mormon church has discovered that it has with the Catholic church regarding gender and what both churches consider to be its fixed, binary, and god-given nature. In other words, the Mormons and the Catholics have recently formed a united front against a common enemy: what is known in Peru as "ideologia del genero" (gender ideology).

Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: Though the contact between the Mormons and the Catholics in Arequipa, Peru has never been seriously violent, it has never been exactly neutral either. It has involved the threat of violence. The following translated and transcribed interview excerpt that provides evidence for this comes from a conversation between the contributor and an elderly married couple who were among the first 50 Peruvians to become Mormons in Arequipa. Ronal was baptized in 1960 and Leticia in 1966. The interview took place in their home in Arequipa on March 2, 2018. JASON: What image do you have of Utah? RONAL: I think of the history that we have of

the church growth with Joseph Smith the prophet, and so much persecution that they didn't know how to escape it, and here in Arequipa we've also had persecution. The newspapers warred against us. They were always picking at our prohibition against alcohol. I remember in the very first days, when I was baptized, the membership started to grow and we would travel to thermal pools for baptism. The press would follow us. One time at a kiosk, a man with a bottle of beer and a cup stood next to a member [of the Mormon church] who happened to be drinking soda out of a bottle. They snapped a photo. In the newspaper the next day the headline read, "There They Are, These Are The Mormons!" "Supposedly these Mormons don't drink, but look what we saw." What didn't they say about us? Uy! They would even say that in our chapels we had many rooms where men would hook up with women. All lies. The Catholic priests would wait for us on the corner, throng around us and say, "where is that book?" And they would snatch our Books of Mormon away, "these must be burned, these are worthless." But the Catholics are more accepting now. LETICIA: Even my niece has accepted. She hasn't accepted baptism yet, but one can still hope. When my mother died, my niece had never before seen how temple-endowed members were buried. She was with me, since she is the oldest of my mother's granddaughters, and Hermana Maribel from the church was there. I told them, "help me dress my mother." My mother had her little temple envelope of clothing ready for her death, all new. And my niece was impacted upon seeing how we dressed and cleaned, and she helped us put on the little shoes. Even though she wasn't a member, she was her granddaughter, so I couldn't prohibit her from helping with the sacred temple clothing. It impacted her to see that a man and a woman who are sealed in the temple go to the tomb in their ceremonial robes. And ever since then, my niece--- hopefully, hopefully, we are-- RONAL: --We are waiting for the Arequipa temple open house so that she can go. And for us as well, it has been a surprise, what with the groundbreaking and all that. (The endowment is a temple ritual wherein subjects are endowed with power from on high and are granted the keywords, signs, and tokens necessary for passing the angels who stand as sentinels guarding the highest of the three heavens, the Celestial Kingdom. The endowment involves changing into special robes including white slippers. Some might say that the endowment is the penultimate temple rite and that marriage is the ultimate. This is not completely accurate. Being resurrected from the dead can be considered the ultimate temple rite, which is why Mormons are buried in their temple robes. Leticia takes the time to justify allowing a non-Mormon to touch temple clothing because Mormons are extremely careful with what they allow the uninitiated to know about temple practices. A temple's pre-dedication open house is the only time non-Mormons and "unworthy" Mormons can enter. In the case of the Arequipa temple, this happened in November 2019. Ronal did not live to see it.)

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

— Yes

Notes: There has been violent conflict between Peruvian Mormons and the Maoist Guerrilla movement of the 1980's and 90's called the Sendero Luminoso. The following translated and transcribed interview excerpt that provides evidence for this stems from a conversation between the contributor and an employee of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints, Simon, who was an ecclesiastical leader over many congregations (a "stake president") in Arequipa, Peru during the height of Sendero violence. Simon was also born and raised in Arequipa. This interview took place on December 26, 2017 at a shopping mall in Provo, Utah. JASON: You've seen the difference between the establishment of Zion in Utah and the establishment of Zion in Arequipa and many other parts of the world. What does Utah still need in order to truly become Zion? SIMON: I think that here [in Utah] they had the blessing of receiving the gospel firsthand, and it was marvelous. The pioneers did an incredible job in these lands, but my impression is that, as the years have gone by, the younger generations has forgotten a bit of what the pioneer sacrifice meant. Us over there [in Peru], we saw a little of what the pioneers saw here [in the U.S.] when they started their new religion with all the opposition in Missouri, Kirtland, etcetera. Well, that same opposition was felt by us in Arequipa in the beginning. The Catholic priests would come and attack the first Mormons there. They took a procession with their virgin to the first chapel built in Arequipa—Umacollo—and they stoned us, they threw rocks at us. Then the Sendero Luminoso [Shining Path] came in the 80s and 90s when I was a stake president. I received a letter that I'm going to show you, a threat

letter where they gave me thirty days to get out and if I didn't, they were going to kill me and my family, and they were also going to attack our chapels. They did it, Jason. In Ica they destroyed two chapels. I was with my wife one day driving my car. We passed by the chapel and it exploded, right where I worked. I was seeing all the dust from the roof that caved in and the glass. A young man came and told me, "President, they destroyed the stake center [larger chapel] too." They exploded both at the same time. I saw that myself. Personally. But also in other places, they attacked chapels, they destroyed, they killed Peruvian missionaries. In Arequipa, after I introduce you to the pioneer of Cuzco, I am going to introduce you to the father of one of the missionaries who died, murdered by the Sendero Luminoso. JASON: Did the Sendero have something specifically against the Mormon church? SIMON: No, they were basically against all religions of foreign origin. They related the church to North American interests—Pizza Hut, McDonald's, and the Mormons ... At first we had a lot of Catholic opposition, but with time, we had the communist opposition. Now the Catholics love us. There has been a change and they have seen that we are not purely Yankees. We are a people of North American origin, yes; a very U.S. religion, but it goes further than simply politics. It offers you a change of life. We have won respect from the Catholics, and a little from the communists as well [laughs]. (Establishing Zion is a complex concept, but in some sense it can be read simply as "establishing Mormonism." Notice how in both this and in the previous interview with Ronal and Leticia, the contributor does not ask about the persecution of early Peruvian Mormons, he asks only about Utah. This recounting of violence comes completely unprompted and is perhaps symptomatic of the self-perception of being a persecuted people that Mormonism enshrined in its origin myths and that it perpetuates through continual reminders, such as the annual July 24th celebration of "Pioneer Day" in Utah, an official state holiday.)

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

— No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

— Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

— Yes

Notes: Regarding the system of religious affiliation, the practice of Peruvian Mormons is similar to the official practice of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints. The church keeps very thorough records, which it curates both in local congregations and in centralized databases. Local leaders have access to these databases, now online, and are able to see the contact information, age, gender, and "activity level" (a measure of church attendance and religiosity) of each person, and, importantly, each "household," under their jurisdiction. As part of the contributor's study of Peruvian Mormonism, he officially joined a congregation in Arequipa, Peru in 2018. He was able to do so because his name was already in the church's central database as a "member of record," meaning he was baptized by immersion by a "worthy" male officiator of what is known as the "Aaronic priesthood," a lesser priesthood preparatory to the greater priesthood known as the "Melchizedek priesthood." He had been baptized at age 8 by his own father, a situation considered ideal among Mormon families the world over. Baptized members of the church are also members of the specific, cartographically bounded congregation within which their residence happens to fall. The contributor, upon moving to Arequipa, Peru, found through the church's website that his residence fell inside the boundaries of the Perifericos Ward. Ward is another word for congregation. He found out that the ward met in a church-built and church-owned meeting house (chapel) in central Arequipa every Sunday from 10:00 a.m. to 1:00 p.m. He attended church and was later interviewed by the bishop of the ward, Bishop Paucar. The interview had many purposes, foremost of which was to ask the contributor's name and birth date so that his records could be transferred from his previous congregation, a Spanish-speaking congregation near the University of California, Irvine, to Perifericos Ward. Another purpose of the interview was to see if the contributor was "worthy"

to accept a "calling" or a leadership responsibility within the congregation. Worthiness largely involves avoiding certain activities (fornication, dishonesty, breaking the law of tithing, breaking the health code) and believing certain things (that God the Father and his son Jesus Christ are two separate, corporal beings and that the president of the corporation of the church, "the prophet" is their mouthpiece on the earth today). Often, worthiness interviews involve the bishop reading a list of specific questions to which the interviewee must answer affirmatively to be considered "worthy." In this case, the bishop merely assumed that the contributor was worthy because of the contributor's self-report that he had served a mission for the church in Bolivia 20 years prior. Many Peruvian Mormons consider being a "returned missionary" or "retornado" (in Spanish) to be a sure sign of worthiness. Most Peruvian Mormons who attend church regularly have "callings." Callings are responsibilities thought to come from the mind and will of God himself. God communicates the calling to a leader, and the leader "extends" the calling to the person meant to accept it. The position of "bishop," the highest leadership position in a "ward," is itself a calling rather than a chosen, paid vocation. Theoretically, any adult male in the ward could suddenly be "called" to be bishop regardless of ecclesiastical training. The contributor was given the calling to be the "First Councilor" in the "Elders Quorum Presidency." Eventually he became the "Elders Quorum President." The Elders Quorum is the organization for males in a congregation above the age of 18. The female counterpart to the Elders Quorum is the Relief Society. From this position, the contributor was able to access different data points of every member of record in the ward, including those "members" who were not yet baptized, which finally gets to the point of this entry. Baptism and subsequent "confirmation" (a ritual conferral of the Gift of the Holy Ghost) are the official rites that bestow church membership to any "worthy" person above age 8. However, a certain level of membership in the church can be assigned shortly after birth if a Mormon parent decides to have his or her child given "a name and a blessing" in a ritual called "a baby blessing." The ideal for this ritual in Peru is that the father of a cohabiting, heteronormative, U.S.-defined nuclear family living in a single-family home take his newborn baby to the front of the sacrament hall shortly after the congregational opening hymn is sung during Sunday worship services, form a circle around the baby with other priesthood-holding males (females cannot hold the priesthood) who will become important in its life (such as uncles and church leaders) and pronounce the words: "Heavenly Father, by the authority of the Melchizedek priesthood which we hold we bring this baby before you to pronounce a name and a blessing. The name by which she/he will be known upon the records of the church is _____, (full name of the baby)." The speaker then often switches from speaking to Heavenly Father in his own voice to talking directly to the baby in the voice of Jesus Christ and blessing it with the fulfillment of all the hopes the father has for it, which often include serving a mission for the church at age 18 or 19 (depending on gender) and finding a "worthy mate" for marriage shortly thereafter. Though this is the ideal among Peruvian Mormons, it is rarely the reality because a nuclear family consisting of a married couple and their young children living in their own home is extremely uncommon in Peru. Many Peruvian "households" involve large, multiplanar, labyrinthine brick and concrete complexes that house married and unmarried adult siblings and their children, in-laws, ageing parents, and other kin without English-equivalent kin terms. Many of these large familial complexes in Peru, and among Peruvian Mormons in Utah, are headed by a central matriarch whereas Mormonism is headed by a central patriarch. This causes an important cultural tension within Peruvian Mormonism. One result of this tension is that, in Peru and among Peruvian Mormons in Utah, there often is no father figure to perform the baby naming ritual, and so it is often conducted by the bishop or other male leader. Children under the age of 8 who attend church and who have been given a "name and a blessing" through the aforementioned ritual appear on the records of the church as unbaptized members of the church and their names are listed on the attendance rolls of either "The Nursery" or "The Primary" organizations for children in their ward.

Assigned by personal choice:

— Yes

Notes: In Mormonism, the idea of "personal choice" is itself a foundational doctrine that creates conflict within Peruvian Mormon congregations. The contributor has written a book chapter about this very issue here: Palmer, Jason. 2020. "Peruvian Mormon Matchmaking: The Limits of

Mormon Endogamy at Zion's Border." In *The Routledge Handbook of Mormonism and Gender*, edited by Amy Hoyt and Taylor C. Petrey, 1 edition, 419–31. New York, NY: Routledge. Below is an adapted excerpt of that chapter about the pre-earth nature of the individual and of individual personal choice in Mormonism. It focuses on a Peruvian Mormon single mother named Ofelia whom the contributor met in Perifericos Ward. Ofelia grew up in Arequipa as a Catholic and had a daughter out of wedlock. When her daughter was three, Ofelia met Anglo Mormon missionaries and chose to be baptized into the Mormon church. The excerpt mentions a ritual called a temple "sealing." Sealing is a ritual that can only be performed inside a Mormon temple, which is not to be confused with a chapel (meeting house). Anyone who desires may enter any one of about 20 luxurious, U.S.-style Mormon meeting houses around Arequipa, Peru, but only worthy Mormons with current, valid "temple recommend" cards may enter the multi-million dollar, Anglo Mormon-designed Arequipa temple. Being "sealed" to someone inside the temple means being ritually bound to that person in a relationship that will exist after death. The temple only seals two types of heteronormative, Eurocentric kin relationships: husband-wife, and couple-child. No other relationships, including mother-child, can be sealed in the temple unless they can first be linked to the conjugal couple. This means that Ofelia, being single, cannot be sealed to her own daughter in what is the most vital of Mormon rituals. This further means she will not be able to be together with her daughter after death unless she can find herself a temple-worthy Mormon husband before death. Excerpt: Mormons, especially when finding a mate for someone they care about, want someone who is not only a Mormon, but a "full" Mormon. In the eyes of many, Ofelia herself does not meet this ambiguous criterion. By virtue of her being baptized at age 24, already a single mother, she was late for the rite of passage most directly connected to the paradox at Zion's heart—her own birth. She was not "born in the covenant." In other words, her parents had not been sealed in the temple before she was born. Mormons born to temple-sealed parents come into the world already sealed to those parents. No future sealing rite is necessary. Ofelia missed this rite because she is a first-generation Mormon, or a *conversa* (convert). In much the same way that Indians under British colonialism were seen as "the effect of a flawed colonial mimesis, in which to be Anglicized, is emphatically not to be English" (Bhabha, 1984, 128) *conversos* are sometimes seen as more Mormonized than Mormon. Ofelia rejects this view. OFELIA: A lot of times, before I understood such things, members of the church would always ask us that question, "hey, um, are you of the covenant?" And I would say, "what do you mean 'of the covenant?'" "I'm just asking if your parents were sealed in the temple and then you were born from them." "Oh, no then. No, I'm not of the covenant." "Oh, so you are of the baptized." "Ah, yes, I guess you're right because I just got baptized." And so time went on and during a lot of years they'd always ask that question, "are you of the covenant?" or, "is your daughter of the covenant, was she born in the covenant?" And with sadness or sometimes even shame I would say, "no, my daughter is not of the covenant." But then I started wondering, "why do they ask that?" And when I studied about it, I said, "what!?" I mean, how dare they make me think that I'm not of the covenant when I'm just as much of the covenant as they are. Those who have been chosen as people of the covenant who have been born in the covenant, and those who accept the gospel after repenting and entering into the baptismal waters, are all equal. Don't give me any talk about difference and, "we are the real people of the covenant, but since you were baptized it means you were only adopted by us," it's not like that. We are all part of the covenant, right? So I don't see why they have to make differences like that. It's a stupid question that they start asking ... Sometimes the parents of my seminary students tell me, "my kids were born in the covenant so they already know everything." Mistake. Right? Gargantuan mistake! Why? Because there are many brothers and sisters, Shannon's contemporaries, who, while it is true that their parents were sealed in the temple, born in the covenant themselves even, and I guess from inside the womb they were grasping gospel concepts [laughs], BUT their kids have been dishonorably discharged from missions, sometimes not even gone on missions, and their daughters have gone astray and all that, right? So that is why I say emphatically, "no." I mean, it is not an indispensable requirement that one be of the covenant people, right? What matters is how one goes about guiding one's kids, whether they were born in the covenant or not. JASON: Is it possible that they think they were born in the covenant because their spirits were more valiant in the preexistence? OFELIA: Of course. It's not just possible, that is precisely what they think. They think they are more choice spirits, "the elect," right? They think they've been chosen, but—MISTAKE! Ofelia jokes about the womb in her statement against those who look down on her *conversa* status. She makes fun of the idea that one could exercise agency before birth because she knows that this

notion is partially from whence the doctrine of "the elect" emerges. Ironically, however, stories of humanity's pre-birth existence also provide her with pride in being a conversa; in using agency to choose Mormonism. After all, Mormonism's original sibling rivalry, Lucifer versus Jesus, was about agency. Heavenly Father and Heavenly Mother's second-born spirit son, Lucifer, planned to force human beings to be good inhabitants of the new planet Earth. The first born, Jesus, wanted goodness to be a choice. The two brothers could not find a compromise and fought a primordial war over this question of agency. Those on Earth today with physical bodies fought on the winning side. The losers never got bodies; they are Satan's demons. There is a divide in Barrio Periféricos between those who think that the more valiant soldiers in the war were rewarded with birth into an already-Mormon family and those who think that choosing Mormonism during Earth-life represents true valiance. In this debate, generational Mormonism becomes a contested requirement for "full" Mormonism. Work Cited: Bhabha, Homi K. 1984. "Of Mimicry and Man: The Ambivalence of Colonial Discourse." *October* 28 (Discipleship: A Special Issue on Psychoanalysis): 125-33.

Assigned by class:

— Yes

Notes: Though membership is not deliberately assigned by class, it turns out that most Peruvian Mormons who remain "active" in the church after a few years are upwardly mobile, middle-class urbanites. The reasons for this are complex and have to do with the Mormon ontology of the Western individuated self. One of the four parts of the church's modern mission statement is to preach the gospel to every inhabitant of the earth. However, like any capitalistic enterprise with a mission statement, the church's missionizing program revolves around efficiency and cost-benefit analyses. Its baptisms-per-missionary rate needs to remain high in order for the church to justify opening a new mission in a region. If a person hears about the church through the missionaries, but does not quickly "accept the gospel," that person is often considered to not be "the elect" because, according to one of Mormonism's four canonical books, *The Doctrine and Covenants*, "ye are called to bring to pass the gathering of mine elect; for mine elect hear my voice and harden not their hearts," (section 29 verse 7, <https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/scriptures/dc-testament/dc/29?lang=eng&clang=eng#p7>). Speed of gospel acceptance is thus often thought to be a sign of predestination for Mormon membership. Mormonism was founded on the Kantian idea of the self as being an individual subject who thinks and therefore is. In the Andes, on the other hand, my subjecthood only emerges through you. You are connected to me through *ayni* (cyclical reciprocity), therefore I am. In the Andes, whether a human or non-human person is a subject or an object depends on the relational situation, which is neither fixed nor unambiguous. An Andean's personhood did not exist prior to her relationships. A Mormon's personhood (and binary gender) existed prior even to her relationship to God. In order for Andeans to convert to Mormonism, they first have to convert to the conceptions of individuality and subject/object permanence common to Western modernity and eschew their lifeways of collectivity and subject/object ambiguity common to the Andes. This is a slow process. In a Mormon economy focused on scarcity and efficiency, its slowness equates to non-elect status. Since Western modernity is currently hegemonic in much of the world's globalized system of capitalism controlled largely by the U.S., accepting Western modernity is not only the key to Mormon conversion, it is the key to financial success and class ascension in Peru. People in Peru who have accepted Western modernity tend to migrate to cities, stop speaking Quechua, and desire upward mobility and wealth accumulation rather than cyclical reciprocity and wealth diffusion. Since these people have already accepted Western modernity, they accept Mormonism much more quickly than their Quechua-speaking, village-dwelling counterparts. And since these middle-class, Spanish-speaking Peruvians accept Mormonism more quickly, Anglo Mormons consider them "the elect" and focus their missionizing efforts accordingly. When contrasted with Mormonism's conception of indigeneity, this conflation of middle-class status with elect status creates an irony wherein the very people that Mormons are most likely to identify as literal biological descendants of Book Of Mormon prophets are the least likely to hear about that book.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

— Yes

Notes: The ideal age for baptism into the Mormon church is age 8. Children younger than 8 cannot be baptized, though they are still considered members if their parents are members. Age 8 is thought to be "the age of accountability," before which a child is incapable of understanding a law of God and therefore incapable of breaking it (committing sin). Since one of the purposes of baptism is to wash away sins, and since young children are thought to be incapable of sin, young children do not need baptism in order to qualify for heaven. This doctrine is another instantiation of the intensity with which U.S. individualism influenced early Mormonism. It is a reaction to the more collectivist Catholic doctrine that though young children are incapable of committing sin as individuals, they are caught under the collective human sinfulness that the first human, Adam brought into existence when he ate the forbidden fruit. In the Catholic conception, since this sinfulness bars all humans from heaven in the afterlife, and since baptism during this life is the only way to wash away this sinfulness, babies should be baptized as soon after birth as possible just in case they die before getting the chance. Mormonism, in its existential individualism, rejects the notion that the entire family of humans should be forced to face the consequences of actions that each individual in that family did not personally carry out. In fact, the second of the church's 13 articles of faith states: "We believe that men will be punished for their own sins, and not for Adam's transgression." This question of whether or not children with no personally committed sin should be baptized in order to enter heaven was a common aspect of the anti-Catholic religious discussions happening among the early U.S. frontier religious revival movements from which Mormonism emerged in the early 1800's. The fact that The Book of Mormon projects this specific doctrinal discussion onto the ancient inhabitants of the Americas is often cited as one of the book's many anachronisms by those who seek to disprove its authenticity as a literal translation of ancient text. According to the book, the ancient American prophet, Mormon thought this issue of baptismal age was so important that he wrote about it in a letter to his son, Moroni who, in turn, engraved the letter in its entirety upon one of the few remaining golden plates he was using to summarize the millennial history of pre-Hispanic America. In the letter, almost as an afterthought, Mormon foresees the dawn of an apocalyptic, genocidal war that would eventually take his life and the lives of his entire nation, but the thrust of the letter--a message apparently more important than his people's collective, impending doom--included an angry tirade against child baptism. Mormon wrote (Moroni chapter 8, verses 5-14), 5 For, if I have learned the truth, there have been disputations among you concerning the baptism of your little children. 6 And now, my son, I desire that ye should labor diligently, that this gross error should be removed from among you; for, for this intent I have written this epistle. 7 For immediately after I had learned these things of you I inquired of the Lord concerning the matter. And the word of the Lord came to me by the power of the Holy Ghost, saying: 8 Listen to the words of Christ, your Redeemer, your Lord and your God. Behold, I came into the world not to call the righteous but sinners to repentance; the whole need no physician, but they that are sick; wherefore, little children are whole, for they are not capable of committing sin; wherefore the curse of Adam is taken from them in me, that it hath no power over them; and the law of circumcision is done away in me. 9 And after this manner did the Holy Ghost manifest the word of God unto me; wherefore, my beloved son, I know that it is solemn mockery before God, that ye should baptize little children. 10 Behold I say unto you that this thing shall ye teach--repentance and baptism unto those who are accountable and capable of committing sin; yea, teach parents that they must repent and be baptized, and humble themselves as their little children, and they shall all be saved with their little children. 11 And their little children need no repentance, neither baptism. Behold, baptism is unto repentance to the fulfilling the commandments unto the remission of sins. 12 But little children are alive in Christ, even from the foundation of the world; if not so, God is a partial God, and also a changeable God, and a respecter to persons; for how many little children have died without baptism! 13 Wherefore, if little children could not be saved without baptism, these must have gone to an endless hell. 14 Behold I say unto you, that he that supposeth that little children need baptism is in the gall of bitterness and in the bonds of iniquity; for he hath neither faith, hope, nor charity; wherefore, should he be cut off while in the thought, he must go down to hell.

↳ Assigned by gender:

— No

Notes: Anglo Mormonism is a highly patriarchal and phallogocentric religion, so there are, of course, levels of power within basic church membership that are available only to males (Peruvian Mormonism is somewhat less patriarchal in complex ways that have to do with the predominance of women in Peruvian Mormon congregations and their role as breadwinners in Peruvian Mormon homes). However, basic, official membership is available to both males and females and even, in 2020, to transgender individuals. The 2020 clarification of a transgender individual's standing in the church comes from the same source of most of the church's changes that it considers "administrative" rather than "doctrinal:" what it used to call its Handbook Of Instructions when it was in print form, but what it now calls its General Handbook, which it constantly updates (often without notifying the membership) and makes available here: <https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/manual/general-handbook/title-page?lang=eng> . The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints is designed to be an extremely "modular" religion much like a franchise business, meaning it is designed to be duplicatable in most parts the world and largely impervious to "local culture." One way it achieves this modularity is through its centrally distributed manuals, which run the thematic gamut from financial self-reliance to baptismal interview questions. Anglo Mormons often consider these manuals to be straightforward teachings with no cultural subtext that will have to be deciphered by their non-Anglo coreligionists throughout the world. However, since the church is centered in Utah and since these manuals are written by situated Utahans influenced by their own local settler-colonist cultures and white logics, the ideas that end up getting duplicated throughout the world as benign "instructions" or even as divine "doctrines" are actually Anglo Mormon cultural norms, constructs, and preferences that are anything but benign when applied to non-Anglo cultural contexts. (listen to this podcasted conversation between prominent Mormon scholars Gina Colvin and Caroline Kline as an example: <https://www.athoughtfulfaith.org/caroline-kline-mormon-feminist-theology/>) As such, in the attached manual excerpt, the church uncritically projects the word "transgender" through an Anglo Mormon lens that can only conceive of gender in binary terms. Interestingly, Peruvian Mormons tend to be even more "socially conservative" than their Anglo Mormon church leaders when it comes to questions of gender. Many Peruvian Mormons known to the contributor disagreed vehemently with the very idea of allowing transgender people to even attend church, let alone be baptized. Now that their church has accepted transgender individuals into the waters of baptism, these Peruvian Mormons publicly swallow their disagreement so as not to go against the authority of the church they know to be "true," but they silently suffer through serious cognitive dissonance, feelings of betrayal, feelings of having no control over their own religion, feelings of fear over what change the church is going to make next, and feelings of confusion over how a religion led by an unchangeable God could change so constantly and abruptly. The contributor witnessed many outbursts of this social conservatism among Peruvian Mormons in their Sunday School meetings in both Peru and Utah. One example took place in 2017 during his fieldwork in the Spanish-speaking Pioneer Trail Ward of Salsands, Utah, a congregation that has an usually high percentage of Peruvians (about 30%) among its predominantly Latinx membership. One Sunday, during what is known as the Gospel Principles course taught to new adult members in their first year after baptism, the topic shifted towards abortion. The teacher, a Peruvian female, read from the lesson manual that abortion in the church is allowed, but only in cases of rape. A new member, a Peruvian male, asked how abortion could possibly be justifiable even in cases of rape. Discussion spread to the rest of the class, about 10 students, and revealed that many male and female students felt torn between what they thought was wrong under any circumstances and what their new religion was suddenly telling them was sometimes permissible.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

— Yes

Notes: Membership is achieved through the rite of baptism and, more specifically, through the rite of confirmation that often immediately follows baptism. The correct protocol for baptism is stipulated in manuals published in Utah. However, the Peruvian Mormon rite of baptism, at

least in Arequipa, varies slightly from the Anglo Mormon rite. This is a mere technicality, not a huge piece of evidence that a new religion is forming in Peru from the syncretism of Andean Catholicism and Mormonism. Nevertheless, Anglo Mormons in Peru use the Peruvian Mormon addition to the rite as one more piece of ammunition for their case that Peruvians are not capable of self-government. The argument of these Anglo Mormons is that even after 60 years of experience running the church in Peru, Peruvian Mormons still need Anglo supervision, which is why both the Arequipa temple construction site manager and the Arequipa Mission President during the contributor's fieldwork in 2018 were Anglo Mormons flown in from Utah. About 8 of the 20+ Mormon chapels in Arequipa are equipped with a small classroom with shutters that open to reveal a small rectangular baptismal font flanked by steps on either side leading to it from the male and female restrooms. Someone in one of the congregations that uses one of these chapels will have the job ("calling") of scheduling the baptismal font. When the full-time missionaries (often an 18-year-old Utahan paired with an 18-year-old Peruvian) who are temporarily assigned to the congregation have an "investigator" who wishes to be baptized, they confer with the font scheduler and fix a baptismal date. In Perifericos Ward in Arequipa, baptisms invariably took place on Saturdays. There were about two adult baptisms per month during the time the contributor was in Arequipa. Baptismal ceremonies in Perifericos Ward were often very impromptu events. The only vital aspect of the rite is that a baptizer ordained to the office of "priest" say the correct prayer and submerge the baptizee completely under the water in the presence of two adult witnesses. It is not necessary that the baptism be conducted inside a Mormon chapel at all. In fact, early baptisms in Arequipa in the 60's took place in outdoor thermal pools in nearby Yara. However, as baptism is an important personal life stage event, many other "cultural" additions to the rite itself usually take place. These are fairly standard throughout Mormonism and include a photo shoot with the participants dressed in their white clothing, a gathering of family, friends and congregation members in the small classroom overlooking the font, an opening hymn, a prayer, a speech about baptism by one of the local members, and a speech about the Holy Ghost by another. The baptism itself then takes place and all the people in the small classroom watch. The baptism must be redone if a single hair or piece of clothing from the baptizee does not submerge completely. Once the witnesses give the approving nod that the rite was done correctly, the shutters on the font are closed and the wet participants go change into their dry, Sunday best. While they are changing, the gathered assembly sings Mormon hymns to the tune of European folk songs. Upon the new member's return to the classroom, the bishop of the congregation welcomes the new member as do the presidents of every age and gender-specific sub-organization to which the new member now belongs, such as the Relief Society if the member is a female over the age of 18. As these meetings are often organized by the young full-time missionaries at the last minute, attendance is usually extremely low and it is often difficult for the Bishop or Relief Society president to attend. Nevertheless, since the occasion is a great missionizing tool in that it gives the non-Mormon family members and friends of the baptizee a sacred, solemn experience inside a Mormon edifice, the missionaries always manage to pull off a successful event that culminates in some sort of refreshments usually involving cheese puffs and crackers hastily bought from a nearby kiosk. All of the aforementioned details are practically the same between Anglo Mormonism and Peruvian Mormonism. The principal difference, which is something that was pointed out to the contributor by the Anglo Mormon mission president of Arequipa when he appeared unannounced to supervise a Perifericos Ward baptism (see attached photo), is that Peruvian Mormons tend to close the shutters on the font immediately after the baptism. On this particular occasion, when the Mission President saw them do this he interrupted the proceedings and had his missionaries reopen the shutters saying that it would be nice for people to get photos of the baptizee while she (significantly, the baptizee was female) was fresh out of the water wearing white, wet (and thus sheer) clothing. In a later conversation about this and other similar incidents, another prominent Anglo Mormon in Arequipa explained to the contributor that this font-hiding behavior on the part of Peruvian Mormons was symptomatic of their inability to spiritually discern the difference between Mormon "culture" and Mormon "doctrine," and that this inability was why Anglo Mormons needed to be in Peru. According to him, Peruvians are incapable of understanding the aspects of holiness that make a baptism valid. From the Peruvian Mormon perspective, however, closing the doors on the font is required to meet the demands of corporal modesty that are common sense under Andean norms of decency (see De La Cadena, Marisol. 2000. Indigenous Mestizos: The

Politics of Race and Culture in Cuzco, Peru, 1919–1991. Durham, NC: Duke University Press Books) regardless of religion. White, wet clothing becomes sheer. So, it is only common sense in the Andes that the front shutters be closed to preserve the baptizee's dignity and modesty. Again, this difference may seem silly, but it is an example of how Peruvians are infantilized for being unable to do the impossible: separate the "vital" from the "cultural" in a religion wherein only Anglo culture determines what is "vital." Peruvians are deemed incapable of self-government because Anglos see them as being unduly influenced by "culture," whereas Anglos see themselves, and their church's doctrine, as being immune to "culture." Anglos do not see themselves as coming from a cultural standpoint at all. Anglos, in their own estimation, come from the standpoint of universal truth, something every competent adult should be able to recognize.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: contact with Mormon missionaries

Notes: Though official membership on the records of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints is only granted through baptism and subsequent confirmation (a simple ritual wherein a holder of the Melchizedek Priesthood places his hands upon the head of the recent baptizee, says the baptizee's full name and states, "having authority of the Melchizedek priesthood, I confirm you a member of the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints and say unto you, receive the Holy Ghost," then continues with whatever words of encouragement and fortune-telling he feels inspired to say), many people in the Andes consider themselves to be "Mormon" simply because they had a single encounter with Mormon missionaries or because they happen to have a Book of Mormon in their residence. In this way, they often also consider themselves to be Catholic, Adventist, Jehovah's Witness, and any number of other "religions" along with Mormon. This demonstrates that "religious membership" means something rather different in the Andes than it does for the official Mormon missionaries.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: The term "religious professionals" does not exactly coincide with how Mormons consider church leadership to work, mostly because "professional" implies training and payment. As previously mentioned, church leaders are "called" to hold positions to which they did not apply and for which they are often completely unprepared. The majority of these positions are not exactly paid positions, though members who have received the calling to the "General Authority" level or above on the church's general administration hierarchy do receive extremely lucrative "living stipends" of upwards of 120,000 USD annually. Even these high level officials do not exactly proselyte, so there is certainly no "professional" proselyting force in the church, however, since missionary work is part of the church corporation's official mission statement, all members regardless of their leadership position are expected to "share the gospel" in some way with their family and friends. The church is constantly attempting to market different slogans to motivate its membership to do this. One recent slogan is "every member a missionary." The closest thing to a professional proselyting force would of course be the massive "volunteer" army of full-time Mormon missionaries who proselyte daily throughout the world despite their lack of theological training and lack of remuneration. These missionaries, distinguished from the general membership by being deemed "full-time missionaries" do, in fact, apply to be placed in the position of full-time missionary, which is but one of many factors that make their "calling" different than any other in the church.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: This answer represents a salient component of the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints' foundational patriarchy and contemporary misogyny. "Mandated" is a strong word, but for all intents and purposes, young males who are "worthy" and "able" are mandated to serve a full-time proselyting mission for two years sometime between the ages of 18 and 26. Full-time missionaries are not considered to be "paid" because they receive a living stipend instead of a wage. That living stipend comes from a fund that they themselves, their parents, or their congregations pay into along with all the other missionaries, their parents, and their congregations throughout the world. For this reason, the full-time Mormon mission is always considered "self-funded" though some missionaries put far more into the fund than they get out and some get out far more than they put in. Females are not mandated to serve a full-time mission and, in fact, do not even have the option to serve until age 19, one year after their male counterparts. If they do serve, they may only serve 1.5 years. In many local instances of Mormonism, such as that observed by the contributor in 2018 in Perifericos Ward in Arequipa, Peru, the mandate for males to serve a mission one year younger than females and return a half year later implies that a female's true mission is to marry one of these males once he becomes a "returned missionary" (retornado) at age 20. In this sort of cultural context, the hope is that, in the extra year she waits to serve a mission, a female will marry a retornado instead of serving a mission herself. The result is that, in Peru even more than in Utah, retornadas (female returned missionaries) are stigmatized. Retornadas in Arequipa, Peru are always surrounded by the unasked, yet palpable question, "why did you go on a mission instead of getting married?" While mission service is stigmatizing to females, the failure to serve a mission is stigmatizing to males. In Peruvian Mormonism, males who are not retornados are not considered full persons in their religious society, even when the reason for their lack of retornado status stems from their finding out about Mormonism in the first place after age 26 when it was too late for them to serve a full-time mission. The result is a paradoxical situation wherein retornados do not want to marry retornadas and retornadas only want to marry retornados. This situation represents one of the many unintended consequences of the social engineering to which the church resorts in order to enforce the nuclearization of family and delegitimize the traditional Peruvian notion of family. Importantly, the only other time when Mormons can serve full-time proselyting missions also points to the church's delegitimization of the Peruvian family. Mormons can serve full-time proselyting missions as elderly, retired couples with no dependent kin living at home (an "empty nest"). The church places great importance and emphasis on these elderly "couples missions" and so Peruvians, who almost never have the type of nuclear familial situation that results in an "empty nest," feel like they come up short of full "Saint" status within Mormonism's global community. Also, "couples missions" do not get to tap into the church's global missionary fund, meaning they must truly be self-funded, which also disqualifies most Peruvians.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

— No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

— No

Notes: As previously mentioned, conducting missionary work in one's day to day life outside of one's time as a full-time missionary is highly encouraged, but not mandated. For example, questions involving one's missionary efforts are not found on the list of questions to which one must answer affirmatively if one wishes to be considered "worthy" to enter a Mormon temple. The things that are required for temple worthiness are the things that many Mormons would consider "mandated." Mormons who have this temple worthiness hold a physical "temple recommend," a card with an expiration date, a bar code, and the signature of their local ecclesiastical leader, which the male gatekeeper of each temple uses to quickly verify temple worthiness.

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– Yes

Notes: Since the majority of proselyting in Peru is carried out by small cohesive groups of young, Anglo Mormon males who are out of their parents' home for the first time in their lives, a sort of militaristic, "Lord Of The Flies" group mentality often develops that can make proselyting highly coercive and corrosive in much the same way that a similar mentality can make individual military platoons highly callous towards the suffering of non-combatants (see <https://apps.dtic.mil/dtic/tr/fulltext/u2/a490174.pdf>.) Since the proselyting efforts of young, full-time missionaries often involve extended periods with little to no oversight from their new parental figures--the often elderly, often Anglo, mission president "and his wife," (the position of "Mission President" is a male-only, three year "calling," which often requires the candidate to uproot himself from Utah and move with his wife, and sometimes coresident children, to the same foreign country where he served a full-time mission as a youth)--these missionaries sometimes channel the latent racism and misogyny of their church into overtly racist and misogynistic practices of psychological coercion. This can be especially troubling when two male Anglo missionaries target a female Peruvian for conversion. In one such instance known to the contributor, Anglo Mormon missionaries in Arequipa stalked a young arequipeña woman for weeks. She finally succumbed to baptism just so that they would stop stalking her. Her nominal membership seemed to satisfy them as they never bothered her after that even though she never attended church. However, through a miraculous experience involving two different Anglo Mormon missionaries twenty years later who were not at all coercive, she became an "active" member of a Mormon congregation. The first set of missionaries were probably satisfied at merely baptizing her without actually "converting" her because of the pressure in some missions, often fomented by specific mission presidents, to increase "mission stats" such as baptisms, hours of proselyting, and hours spent teaching in the homes of "investigators." For more tactics that Mormon missionaries have used in the past to meet the demands of the pressure to increase statistics, see this article about "baseball baptisms" wherein, unbeknownst to them, youth joined the U.S. religion of Mormonism when what they thought they were doing was joining a league for the U.S. sport of baseball (<https://www.sunstonemagazine.com/pdf/093-30-44.pdf>)

↳ Does the coercion take the form of physical force:

– No

↳ Does the coercion take the form of economic sanctions:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: Under the sense of "official" that the Peruvian government reserves for the Catholic church, Peru does not "officially" support the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints and neither does the state government of Utah. In practice however, the church exerts powerful influence over the governments of both places. In Utah, the church is so rooted in the government that law makers can essentially do nothing without its tacit permission (as this LA Times article attests: <https://www.latimes.com/archives/la-xpm-1993-03-21-mn-13641-story.html>). In Peru, the church seeks a similar relationship to the one its has with Utah and it constantly works towards this through periodic public displays of charitable donations, which generate a debt of gratitude, and through widely publicized meetings with Peruvian heads of state (see attached article). It is known to the contributor through a conversation with the Arequipa temple construction site manager that Peru's Ministry of Culture changed a nation-wide law regarding zoning restrictions in archaeological sites just so that the Arequipa temple could be built atop ancient pre-Incan terracing.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In theory, Peruvian Mormonism's stance on apostasy is the same as that of the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints' official stance, which can be found on its web page here: <https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/manual/gospel-topics/apostasy?lang=eng> . The church's definition of apostasy is far broader than that which this database gives for apostasy: the complete, public abandonment of the religion. According to the church, apostasy can involve straying from the laws of Mormonism even while faithfully believing in those laws. Under this definition, all Mormons are in constant danger of apostasy and the line at which a Mormon has crossed over into apostasy changes positions almost as often as the church's General Handbook. In 2015, a handbook change stipulated that a believing, practicing Mormon who entered into a same-sex marriage was suddenly an apostate. There are punishments meted out for cases of apostasy by official church courts convened at the "stake level," a local level of ecclesiastical hierarchy made up of leaders who oversee seven or eight congregations. This means that the punishments for different apostasies can be catered to local circumstances. However, at the worldwide church level, the "mandatory minimum" punishment for this sort of same-sex marriage apostasy was that the children of the offending parties could not be baptized until age 18 and until they officially renounced their parents' lifeways. Many congregations throughout Peru, which usually tend to ignore changes in church policy, celebrated this new stance against homosexuality by printing out the Spanish translation of the new handbook change and displaying it on hallway bulletin boards inside Mormon chapels. However, due to the U.S. public outcry against the church and the hit it took in the U.S. media over what the media took to be an arcane display of homophobia, the church softened its stance on same-sex marriage, calling it a "serious transgression" instead of "apostasy" (see attached article from *The Atlantic*). In the Perifericos Ward that the contributor joined in 2018 in Arequipa, Peru in order to study Peruvian Mormonism ethnographically, he became privy to the apostasy sentences that a few male members of the congregation were serving. The congregation had about 400 people of all ages and genders on its membership roles, but only about 150 of these participated in congregational activities with any regularity. Of those 150 "active" members of the congregation, about 25 were males above the age of 18. These 25 made up the Elder's Quorum. As the contributor was the "Elder's Quorum President," he came to know the personal situations of 4 of his quorum members who were undergoing punishments for varying levels of apostasy. At the time, the official church had two basic terms for apostasy-court sentencing: disfellowshipment and excommunication. Disfellowshipment, as interpreted by the bishop of Perifericos Ward, could include any number of punishments ranging from not being able to take the sacrament (the Eucharist) to not being able to volunteer to give the opening prayer to begin a Sunday School class. Excommunication, on the other hand, is a much more serious verdict in official Mormonism and precludes participation of any kind in church services, including paying tithing or even asking a question during Sunday School. The excommunicant's priesthood is rescinded as is his/her official membership in the church. At the end of an ambiguous length of time, the excommunicant must be rebaptized into the church in order to leave the state of apostasy. Seeing a congregation wherein 4 out of 25 males are paying the official price for apostasy (usually because of matrimonial infidelity) is common in Peru but almost unheard of in Utah. The reason for this is not so much that serious transgressions are not being committed by Mormon males in Utah, but because Peruvian church leaders in Peru do not feel it is appropriate to read between the lines or "bend" the rules stipulated in church handbooks and manuals. Anglos, on the other hand, since they come from the culture that wrote these manuals, feel much more comfortable giving the rules a lenient interpretation when it suits them. And, in the gentleman's club that is the Anglo Mormon Elders Quorum (of which the bishop is technically also a member), it does not suit leaders to mete out heavy punishments against their buddies whom, at any moment, might be called to replace them as leaders. Recently, there have been a few high-profile excommunications in the church for the sin of "apostasy." For example, Kate Kelly was excommunicated for her advocacy of female priesthood ordination (<https://www.nytimes.com/2014/06/24/us/Kate-Kelly-Mormon-Church-Excommunicates-Ordain-Women-Founder.html> .) Many Mormons become "apostates" simply because they no longer believe in the church. In many such cases, though they cannot be officially punished because the church no longer holds any authority over them that they personally recognize as legitimate, they remain as members of companies, families, or governments wherein their church does wield significant power. These apostates often lose their jobs (many Peruvian Mormons in Peru are employed by the corporation of the church, and such employment is often contingent not only upon their continued orthodoxy, but upon their continued temple worthiness), civic positions, and even families. In addition to this, former Mormons are collectively punished through continual church discourses espoused at locally, regionally, and globally broadcast conferences communicated to them through their Mormon friends and family. These discourses trivialize the reasons Mormons leave the church and even, in the

case of a July 26, 2020 Facebook Live broadcast meant for Mormon youth in Chile, Argentina, Uruguay, and Paraguay, insult the intelligence of Mormons and former Mormons whose value systems do not precisely match those outlined in the General Handbook (for a particularly blatant example of this, see Brad Wilcox's contribution to the conference beginning at minute 43 https://www.facebook.com/NoticiasIglesiaDeJesucristo/videos/647636839178816/?notif_id=1595797254670376¬if_t=live_video_explicit&ref=notif)

- ↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Apostates can lose membership in their families. If an apostate is an employee of the church, as many Peruvian Mormons are, he or she could lose wealth.
 - ↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:
 - No
 - ↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punished in the afterlife:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Cursed by "high god":
 - Yes
 - ↳ Cursed by other supernatural being(s):
 - No
 - ↳ Other divine punishment:
 - Yes [specify]: inability to exist in a "whole" family after death
 - Notes: This serves to not only punish the apostate, but to punish the apostate's entire family and lineage of antecedents and descendants. Such a familial disruption causes staunchly Mormon families to place even more stigma upon apostates during life.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 600000

Notes: The church itself has a statistic page for each country in South America, and for that matter, most countries in the world. As of August 3, 2020 there are 619,045 members of record of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints in Peru (see <https://newsroom.churchofjesuschrist.org/facts-and-statistics/country/peru>), which according to that same page, represents 1.94% of the population of Peru. According to a 2017 interview the contributor conducted with the Peruvian Consul in Utah, himself a Peruvian Mormon, of the approximately 8,000 Peruvians in Utah, 5,000 are Mormon. Estimates vary, but approximately 60% of Utahans are Mormon. There are, however, cities in Utah that are upwards of 90% Mormon. Despite the fact that Peruvians make up less than one percent of the population of Utah, Utah still has the seventh highest per capita population of Peruvians in the U.S. The other six states are all on the Eastern Seaboard. Just because Peru has around 600,000 Mormons, does not mean that all of these Mormons identify as such. Part of the proof Mormonism uses for its claim to be "the only true and living church upon the face of the whole earth, with which I, the Lord, am well pleased," (<https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/scriptures/dc-testament/dc/1?lang=eng>) is its numbers. The church has prophesied that its numbers will grow and grow until it they fill the whole earth. Its growth, therefore, is thought to be a sign of its truthfulness. The extent to which its membership numbers reflect the way people actually identify is a reality that the church does not like to publish. The church tends to inflate its numbers so that its members can feel that they are part of a healthy, growing organization. If the amount of members on the Perifericos Ward's records who actually identify as members of Perifericos Ward is any indication, only about 1/3 of Peruvians whom the church identifies as members actually identify themselves as members. This means there are about 200,000 Peruvians who identify as Mormon in Peru. That only 1/3 of the church's reported membership in a country would identify as such actually reflects quite favorably on the Peruvian church. 1/3 is a high fraction compared to other countries in the world, and even other countries in South America. Peruvian Mormons are the most "active" Mormons in South America. One measure of this is the number of temples in Peru. Temples are the most holy and most expensive edifices in Mormonism and their construction is usually only justified in areas where there is a large concentration of full tithe-paying members (Mormons who pay a full ten percent of their monthly income to the church). Peru has 4 temples. Chile, where Mormons supposedly make up over 3% of the country's population, only has 2 temples. This means that Chile has a higher concentration of Mormons than Peru, but a lower concentration of "active" Mormons. In most countries throughout the world, only about 1/4 of the church's reported membership wants anything to do with the church. Effectively, this means that, though the church boasts of its 16 million members throughout the world, only 4 million actually consider themselves to be members. Census data from various countries demonstrates that this sort of statistical inflation is not the case among other U.S.-based Christianities. For example, the membership numbers that the Jehovah's Witnesses report are consistently lower, not higher, than the numbers of people in the census who identify as Jehovah's Witnesses. In the case of Mormonism, the numbers the church reports are consistently four times higher than what censuses show (Stewart 2008). In short, people who were baptized Mormon on a whim as youth and don't even remember ever setting foot in a Mormon church are included in the church's numbers right along with the 150 active members of Perifericos Ward in Arequipa, Peru who participate in church activities on an almost daily basis. As part of the contributor's ethnographic investigations, he accompanied many pairs of Mormon missionaries in both Peru and Utah during their proselyting efforts. On more than one occasion, missionaries became excited when an "investigator" decided to be baptized only to become disappointed later upon finding out that the investigator had already been baptized years prior and simply did not remember the occasion. Work Cited Stewart, David G. 2008. "Growth, Retention, and Internationalization." In *Revisiting Thomas F. O'Dea's The Mormons: Contemporary Perspectives*, edited by Cardell K. Jacobson, John P. Hoffmann, and Tim B. Heaton, 328-62. Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 1.94

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints has an extremely complex organizational system that includes hierarchies within hierarchies and other hierarchies that don't quite fall within hierarchies. Part of this complexity stems from the fact that the church is both a religion and a multi-billion dollar corporation. Another part of the complexity stems from the fact that the male-controlled "priesthood" or the power and authority to act in the name of God on the earth, has its own confusing hierarchy that is somewhat different from the church administration hierarchy and that works with hierarchies of other organizations, such as the female-led Relief Society, that are seen as mere appendages to it. Males who come to church fairly regularly for one year pretty much automatically become priesthood holders whereas females with degrees in theology who strive their hardest every day to be the best Mormons they can be cannot hold the priesthood at all. In broad strokes, every congregation with enough Melchizedek priesthood holders to be considered a "ward" rather than a "branch" is led by a male bishop and his two male councilors. Seven or eight wards, each led by their respective bishops, fall under the jurisdiction of a stake president, his councilors, and his High Council made up of 12 men who also make up a church disciplinary court in cases of suspected apostasy. In Arequipa, Peru, all of these positions are usually occupied by Peruvians. To understand the higher levels of the hierarchy, it is perhaps best to focus on a particular person. Let us take the Peruvian Mormon named Simon as an example. Simon was an "Area Authority Seventy" meaning he was in the administrative rung that liaises between stake presidents in Peru (currently mostly Peruvians) and the three "General Authority Seventies" (currently one Mexican-American, one Anglo-American, and one Italian-Guatemalan) who preside over the South America Northeast Area (Bolivia, Colombia, Ecuador, Peru, and Venezuela). These General Authority Seventies report directly to the Quorum of the Twelve Apostles in Salt Lake City (currently ten Anglo Americans, one German American, and one German Brazilian) who, in turn, report to The First Presidency (currently all Anglo Americans) made up of the prophet (who is also the president of the church corporation) and his two councilors (also considered apostles along with the prophet, meaning that at any one time, there are technically 15 apostles). All these roles are ecclesiastical "callings," not paid church corporation posts, however, those at or above the General Authority Seventy level receive extremely hefty "living stipends" while those at or below the Area Authority Seventy level do not. Aside from these "unpaid" ecclesiastical positions, there are thousands of paid positions within the church corporation. For example, there is a research division within the church that gainfully employs around 40 social scientists with PhD's.

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– No

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 8

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– Yes

Notes: Mormonism has a strong sense that males who currently hold the priesthood, which comes with power, were preordained to it through the laying on of hands in a pre-Earth life that Mormons call the preexistence. As the ancient American prophet Alma proclaimed in the Book of Mormon (Alma chapter 13 verse 3): "And this is the manner after which they were ordained—being called and prepared from the foundation of the world according to the foreknowledge of God, on account of their exceeding faith and good works; in the first place being left to choose good or evil; therefore they having chosen good, and exercising exceedingly great faith, are called with a holy calling, yea, with that holy calling which was prepared with, and according to, a preparatory redemption for such."

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

Notes: Though this common Mormon belief is not at all supported by Mormon scripture and is, in fact, often contradicted by it, many Mormons of all nationalities believe that the highest of their church's leaders, namely the prophet and president of the church, his councilors, and the 12 apostles, were "called" to occupy those positions as a result of their "righteousness." Righteousness in Mormonism tends to be a complex amalgamation of obedience to Mormon commandments, a strong work ethic, a faithfulness to U.S.-defined nuclear family values and relationships, and modest, but significant, displays of financial success.

↳ Powers are inherited:

– Yes

Notes: This is a very complex aspect of Mormon kinship, but yes, there is a sense that leadership positions and the powers that come with them can be inherited. For example, it is thought that those who are literal biological descendants of the Israelite tribe of Levi are destined to become bishops. Also, regardless of the mysteries of Mormon lineages that are simultaneously both biological and spiritual, the fact is that the upper hierarchies of the church, and the powers inherent to them, are often kept within a few of Utah Mormonism's founding families.

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):
– Yes

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:
– Yes

Notes: This is the most definitive of the many complex "yes" answers in this section. Technically, upon the death of the current prophet and president of the church (who, at the time of writing, is 94 years old), any ordinary "worthy" Mormon male could suddenly be "called" to be the prophet. Once in the position of prophet, he will take upon himself the "mantle" of his office and become a seer and a revelator, suddenly able to see into the future and predict calamities. In reality, this has never happened. A standing member of the quorum of the 12 apostles as always been called to be the next prophet, and, arguably, no prophet since Joseph Smith, Mormonism's first, has really ever prophesied. However, seeing a man ascend from the ordinary to the extraordinary does occasionally happen in the case of the calling of a bishop. He who is in the position of bishop, regardless of his complete lack of supernatural powers prior to becoming bishop, will suddenly have what Mormons call the "power of discernment." This power comes to men who are bishops and leaves them when they are no longer bishops. The power involves the ability to essentially read an interviewee's mind and discern whether or not the person is lying in their answers to the temple recommend interview questions. Incidentally, Peruvian Mormon would-be immigrants to Utah often consider the U.S. embassy official in charge of granting them a tourist visa to also have this same power of discernment.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:
– Yes

Notes: They are chosen by God.

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:
– No

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:
– No

Notes: It may appear to unbelievers that this is the case, but from a faithful perspective, the leader is chosen by God.

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:
– No

Notes: God is thought to choose the leaders.

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:
– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:
– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing

the leader:

— No

Notes: Again, God chooses the leader, however local and global bodies of church members occasional "sustain" their leaders in a ritual that serves as a symbolic unanimous vote. Members raise their right hands in favor of the leader's election. Members are then asked if there are "any opposed" to the leader's election. In answer, they keep their hands down. The leader asking for the vote then reports to all present that the election has been unanimous. In the extremely rare cases where there are "any opposed," the opposing party is supposed to be called aside after the meeting and asked the grounds of their opposition. To the knowledge of the contributor, never once have these grounds actually precluded the election of a local or global leader in the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints.

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

— Yes

Notes: This is believed to be the primary part of the selection process.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

— Yes

Notes: Technically, they are considered fallible, especially at the local level. However, there is a strong sense that the men who occupy the upper three echelons of the church (the quorum of the 12 apostles, the prophet's two councilors, and especially the prophet himself) are infallible and that they speak the direct word of God. Church scriptures promise that church leaders will never lead members astray. Some members take this literally and some do not. Here is an example from one of the contributor's interviews with the Peruvian Mormon named Ofelia Dominguez in Arequipa in 2018. OFELIA: They called Shannon [Ofelia's daughter] in to an interview. The bishop was bothered because she is going out with Azyo. Not just the bishop either, his councilors, everyone is against her going out with him, and so she came back from her interview badly affected. And she expressed to me her sadness and said, "Mamá, I don't understand why so much resentment against Azyo on the part of my leaders. They told me roundly, 'we want you to stop seeing him completely.' But what I feel--- Mamá, I have prayed and I feel like he is a good young man and I want to go out with him." And I took this opportunity and said, "what do you think now after hearing from the bishop and listening to his councilors?" And she is a little close-minded at times, "no, if my leader tells me something, it is for a reason, Mamá, so I am going to pay heed." "Oh, really? Okay, so you are going to tell him that you aren't going to see him anymore?" "Yes, Mamá, I have to because my leader told me so." "Oh, really? And how do you feel about that, I mean, what do you feel inside yourself?" "But it's that, Mami, I really like him, I feel something very special." "Okay then, even though you feel something very special for him, you are going to throw that all away just because your bishop and his councilors told you to? You are going to stop going out with him?" "Yes, I know it is for the best because they are my leaders and they are counseling me for my benefit." "Alright, sounds perfect then," I told her, "but, you know what? The leaders are human beings, and they make mistakes and sometimes we as humans judge based on certain things, and we judge people as well. And do you know that they don't know Azyo perfectly? Do you think for one second that if I knew that he was a disobedient young man and that he was really bad for you, that I would permit you to go out with him? I am your mother," I told her. "I know that young man, and you know it." "But my bishop said!" And she started to cry. I told her, "look. Pray. The bishop can tell you many things, but tell the Lord. What will the Lord tell you? You are forgetting that you are a missionary, that you have been a missionary, so make your decision, pray to the Lord. The leaders make mistakes, Hijita." And so she started to study, and she prayed and the next day when she woke up, I asked her, "And? What did you think?" She said, "Mami. I am going to keep going out with him." "Alright, are you sure?" "Yes, Mamá." The above interview excerpt was also published here: Palmer, Jason. 2020. "Peruvian Mormon Matchmaking: The Limits of Mormon Endogamy at Zion's Border." In *The Routledge Handbook of Mormonism and*

Gender, edited by Amy Hoyt and Taylor G. Petrey, 1 edition, 419–31. New York, NY: Routledge.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:
– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:
– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:
– No

Notes: The contributor has chosen to mark "no" only because "required" is a strong word as is "all matters." But, effectively, disciples are required to--as they say and as their children sing-- "follow the prophet, he knows the way."

https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/music/library/childrens-songbook/follow-the-prophet?lang=eng&_r=1

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The texts that members of the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints generally consider "scripture" are their four "canonical" books: The Book of Mormon, The King James Bible (both Old and New Testaments), The Doctrine and Covenants (a religious history of early frontier Anglo Mormonism), and The Pearl of Great Price, a short text that includes a number of documents including Joseph Smith's "translation" of ancient papyri

<https://www.josephsmithpapers.org/paper-summary/egyptian-papyri-circa-300-bc-ad-50/1> from Egypt that a mummy exhibit brought to Kirtland, Ohio in 1835, see:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Book_of_Abraham . The contemporary versions of these books in Spanish that Peruvian Mormons in Peru and Utah use during their Sunday church services and personal scripture study are available online at the church's official website

<https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/scriptures?lang=spa> as well as through an app that most Peruvian Mormons have on their smartphones

<https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/pages/mobileapps/gospellibrary?lang=eng> . However, the original first editions and, in some cases, the manuscript copies are available here:

<https://www.josephsmithpapers.org/paper-summary/book-of-mormon-1830/1> . Interestingly, though the church does not have an official Quechua-speaking mission in Peru (Quechua is Peru's most common language other than Castilian Spanish), it has translated the Book of Mormon into a variant of Bolivian Quechua (quite different from the many variants and registers of Quechua spoken in Peru)

↳ Are they oral:

— Yes

Notes: Technically, everything that is spoken by the servants of God is God's voice and, as such, scripture. As God himself stated in The Doctrine and Covenants section 1, verse 38: "whether by mine own voice or by the voice of my servants, it is the same." Some Mormons interpret this to mean that whatever the prophets and apostles of the church speak orally becomes automatic scripture. Not only that, but they believe this automatic, oral scripture overrides all previous scripture (written or otherwise) that it might happen to contradict. The church broadcasts what is known as its General Conference from The Conference Center in Salt Lake City, Utah biannually (every October and April). The speeches that the upper echelons of the church give during these conferences are transcribed (and sometimes significantly changed or "toned down") and published in the church's November (for the October conference) and May (for the April conference) issues of its monthly magazine published in Spanish as the *Liahona* (The Ensign, in English). <https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/magazines/liahona?lang=spa> These issues of the *Liahona*, along with the articles written by the prophet or the apostles for the other monthly issues, are considered "scripture." Though they are considered scripture, they are not "enacted" as such, at least not among Peruvian Mormons in Perifericos Ward in 2018. These particular Mormons often motivated each other to read the *Liahona* by hyping it up as "living scripture" from the mouth of "modern prophets," however the words from the four canonical books always held much more sway than any recent materials published by the church. Technically, the Salt Lake City, Utah-distributed manuals of the church, in as much as they are written by "modern prophets" are also considered "scripture." However, even Peruvian Mormons who would never downplay the importance of the four canonical books sometimes openly disparage the manuals. The contributor has heard many Peruvian Mormons say things like, "the manual can say whatever it wants to say, but this is what we are going to do." Most Mormons, Peruvian or otherwise, would not be so dismissive of the four canonical books even though everything published by the church is equally "scripture" according to God's logic that "whether by mine own voice or by the voice of my servants, it is the same." Though non-canonical church publications may not be quite as holy as the canonical publications, there still forms a palpable energy among Peruvian Mormons every October and April when General Conference time approaches. Many chapels in Arequipa receive closed circuit broadcasts of these conferences, which are projected onto a large screen that suddenly bathes the otherwise Peruvian space in the dazzling light of Salt Lake City, Utah. General Conference speeches from the church president and the apostles are intermingled with hymns sung by the (99% Anglo) Mormon Tabernacle Choir, with images of the Salt Lake City temple, and with live feeds deliberately showing the more ethnically diverse of the wholesome, Utah Mormon nuclear families wandering around the Temple Square gardens during intermission. Having Salt Lake City always be the fount from which scripture springs orally to the membership creates a profound, global Mormon cultural archetype wherein only Anglo-dominated places can truly be holy places, only European music can be sacred music, and only Anglo words can be God's words. Incidentally, many Peruvian Mormons time their permanent immigration to Utah to coincide with the semi-annual General Conference so that they can use their tickets to said conference as solid evidence of the purpose for which they need a temporary tourist visa, which they will then overstay.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

— Yes

Notes: The Book Of Mormon depicts a light-skinned, Israelite family led by a prophet named Lehi who is of the subtribe of Manasseh. He, his wife Sariah, their four sons (Laman, Lemuel, Nephi and Sam) and their unnamed daughters fled the Babylonian captivity of Jerusalem to arrive at what many Peruvian Mormons argue was an almost completely uninhabited American continent in 600 BCE. After Lehi's family inhabited the Americas, Laman and Lemuel became cursed because they did not practice proper kinways. Their skin was darkened (apologists who want to downplay the church's foundational racism attempt to argue that the

curse and the darkening of the skin were completely unrelated events, as this fascinating comic demonstrates:
<https://www.facebook.com/MakingsbyMeikah/photos/a.1448055688715448/1448054165382267>
). Nephi prophesied that, though his siblings' brown-skinned descendants—the Lamanites—would end up killing off all his light-skinned descendants—the Nephites—the Lamanites would one day be restored to the true kinways as contained in the Book Of Mormon, and their skin would be restored to whiteness. Nephi also prophesied that the mechanism of this restoration would include European conquistadors. Their propitious removal of the more wicked among the Lamanites (the Amerindians) would prepare the way for a Euro-American nation-state, "lifted up by the power of God above all other nations," (<https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/scriptures/bofm/1-ne/13.30?lang=eng&clang=eng#p30>) that would one day allow for the religious freedom necessary to bring the Book Of Mormon out of its hidden New York repository and into the heathen hands of the Amerindian descendants of its dark-skinned antagonists. After writing all this down, Nephi handed off the task of writing the religious history of his people to a new prophet who in turn bequeathed the responsibility to another, and that other to another down the generations until 1000 years later, in about 400 CE, the prophet Mormon had inherited a whole cave full of records. He summarized these onto gold plates and gave them to his son Moroni who engraved a few closing remarks at the end. Moroni, the last Nephite prophet of the Americas (depicted as light-skinned in the illustrations that accompany the free edition of the Book of Mormon to which most Peruvian Mormons were first exposed), witnessed the dark-skinned Lamanites completely destroy his people. Since he had no descendants to whom he could bequeath the records, Moroni hid them under a rock (along with other talismans that had been passed down through the ages, such as an interpretation device known as the Urim and Thumim) in what would one day become Upstate New York. In 1820, as a resurrected, supernatural being of flesh and bone, Moroni appeared to a 14-year-old Anglo settler-colonist named Joseph Smith and told him where to find the gold plates. Joseph Smith translated a portion of these into English through the power of the Urim and Thumim and through inspiration from Iroquois legends and Seneca grave goods he called "seer stones" that he had become adept at pilfering, (see file:///E:/lit%20review/Mormon%20specific/Latter-day_Saint%20Rhetoric,%20Religion,%20and%20Repatriation.pdf). He published this inspired translation as The Book Of Mormon in 1830. In the 1830's, in the midst of the U.S. government's Indian Removal Act, this book provided Anglo settler-colonists—who, according to the book, were members of the scattered Israelite subtribe of Ephraim, Manasseh's older brother—an answer to Musa Dube's question in her feminist reading of Exodus, "Does this text encourage travel to distant and inhabited lands, and if so, how does it justify itself?" (2000, 57). In other words, the theme from Exodus surrounding the justified genocide of the Canaanites as expressed in the Book of Mormon, and later in the actual Mormon exodus to Utah, provided Anglo Mormons (Ephraim) one justification for their expropriation of the lives and lands of the Ute, Diné, Shoshone, and Paiute (Manasseh) that later became the U.S. state of Utah. From an anthropological perspective, the Book of Mormon represents an ingeniously insidious addition to the "Indianist" literature common during U.S. imperial conquest designed to give Anglo settler-colonists a sense of indigeneity, of being the oppressed "people of the land" instead of being the oppressors. From a Peruvian Mormon perspective, the Book of Mormon represents the literal history of the people who once inhabited the ruins they see around them in places like Machu Picchu today. Many Peruvian Mormons consider themselves to be Lamanites and, as such, biological descendants of Israel. From the church's contemporary PR-focused, colorblind-racist perspective, The Book of Mormon should no longer be read as the ancestral history of a cursed/blessed people, the Lamanites, who still exist today. The church once held fast to this idea of Lamanite identity and utilized it to convince thousands of Peruvians to become Mormons. But Lamanite identity is now seen as anti-modern and overtly racist in the U.S., and so the church, as a U.S-centric organization, is backing away from it. In so doing, it is betraying hundreds of thousands of Peruvian Mormons who have deep, strong, generational ties to that identity. Work Cited Dube, DR Musa W. 2000. Postcolonial Feminist Interpretation of the Bible. St. Louis, Mo: Chalice Press.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: Moroni was a supernatural being when he revealed the location of the gold plates to Joseph Smith.

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: There are stories in the Book of Mormon wherein people are "inspired" by Satan, another supernatural being.

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: In a sense, God the Father himself is a human being who has evolved into divinity.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: The prophets in the Book of Mormon are considered non-divine humans, as is Joseph Smith.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

Notes: There have been many additions and deletions in the Book of Mormon to make it sound less racist. Also, after DNA evidence came out in 2002 that there was no Israelite "blood" among isolated Amerindian groups (Murphy 2003), the church changed its text yet again. In 1981, the introduction to the book had read, "After thousands of years, all were destroyed except the Lamanites, and they are the principal ancestors of the American Indians." (Fletcher Stack 2007). This was already a slightly watered down version of the idea that many Peruvian Mormons have of the book, which is that not only are the Lamanites the principal ancestors, they are the sole ancestors. However, in 2007, in direct reaction to mounting DNA evidence, that line was qualified even more to read, "they are among the ancestors of the American Indians" (<https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/scriptures/bofm/introduction?lang=eng&clang=eng>). The single word "among" seems insignificant. In fact, most Peruvian Mormons do not know about its addition to their holy text. Nevertheless, the word "among" dilutes their descendency from Israel and demonstrates the church's capitulation to a U.S.-centric notion of relatedness that has outsourced its kinship system to geneticists. The addition of the word "among" demonstrates that authority over story can be weaponized to disrupt identity. Works Cited Murphy, Thomas W. 2003. "Simply Implausible: DNA and a Mesoamerican Setting for the Book of Mormon." *Dialogue: A Journal Of Mormon Thought* 4 (36): 109-31. Fletcher Stack, Peggy. 2007. "Single Word Change in Book of Mormon Speaks Volumes." *The Salt Lake Tribune*, 2007, November 8 edition. <http://archive.sltrib.com/article.php?id=7403990&itype=NGPSID>.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious

community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The largely male, largely Anglo committees that write the scripture study manuals and guides in the Church Office Building in Salt Lake City, Utah decide not only how to interpret scriptures, but which parts of the scriptures deserve focus and which parts should best be skipped. Little is known about who makes up these closed committees of paid, church corporation employees and how much oversight the ecclesiastical leaders of the church have over the products they publish. What little is known can be found in anthropologist Daymon Smith's unique book, *The Book of Mammon: A Book About A Book About The Corporation That Owns The Mormons*. Recently an interpretation of the dark skin "curse" of the Lamanites was published in one of these committee-written, Book of Mormon study guides that apparently included "erroneous" information damaging to the church ecclesiastical leaders' antiracist facade. The church had to issue an embarrassing correction (see attached newspaper article), which only served to draw attention to the anachronistic racism that pervades the Book of Mormon rather than distract from it. The Peruvian Mormons known to the contributor did not notice that the original, uncorrected version of the manual contained a mistake. In other words, it did not strike them as being any more racist than what they were already used to seeing in church manuals and in the Book of Mormon itself.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– No

Notes: There are many groups of people who consider themselves faithful members of the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints who have unofficial ways of interpreting its foundational scriptures. For example, even though antiblackness is foundational to Mormonism, there are Black Mormons in the U.S. who have found ways to interpret scripture that create a space for them within Mormonism (<https://www.facebook.com/sistasinzion>)

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: In some sense, Mormons consider themselves to be the select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures to the rest of the world. They believe that the Bible only provides half of the evidence necessary to establish Jesus Christ as the one and only source of salvation. The Book of Mormon is the keystone of their religion because it provides the other half, the half that the rest of the Christian world does not have and that it so desperately needs. Within Mormonism there are many special training programs for scriptural transmission. One is the Missionary Training Center, which all full-time missionaries attend for intensive foreign language and proselyting training for 3 weeks to 2 months before they enter their mission areas. As Mormonism has no paid, full-time clergy, there is nothing equivalent to a Catholic seminary meant to train a person who wishes to become a pastor as a full-time profession or vocation. However, there is something called the Church Education System or CES. The aspect of CES that Peruvian Mormons seem to cherish most is not its training in the transmission of the scriptures, but its inculcation of Puritanical time thrift, something they do not get during the non-Mormon aspect of their regular school day. In Periféricos Ward, the most talked-about of the CES's many programs is simply called "Seminary." It is designed to be concurrent with the four years of U.S.-style high school, and each year's curriculum focuses on one of Mormonism's four canonical books. In Utah, most public high schools and junior highs have a church-owned, dedicated Seminary building on their campuses. Seminary for these students is incorporated as just another period of their regular school schedule and is designated as "released time" on their transcripts. Seminary teachers in Utah are CES employees and are

usually paid a much higher salary than their secular high school teaching counterparts next door. Seminary teachers (and their university counterparts known as Institute teachers) receive professional development training, many have PhDs in scriptural linguistics, and since scriptural teaching is their profession, they probably represent Mormonism's most elite, select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures (other than perhaps the religious studies faculty at Brigham Young University, the church's own private university with campuses in Utah, Idaho, Hawaii, and Jerusalem). To be a professional seminary teacher in Utah one must be male and one must be married. If a seminary teacher gets divorced, he loses his job. In Peru (and most places outside of Utah) on the other hand, Seminary teaching is an unpaid "calling" like any other, and lessons are held early in the morning before regular school starts, usually in the home of the teacher. Seminary seniors are often asked to stand before their congregations and "bear testimony" of their Seminary experiences to motivate incoming freshmen. The contributor has witnessed many of these testimonies in Periféricos Ward, and they almost always gloss over what was learned in Seminary in order to elaborate on the character-building aspects of getting up early enough to attend it. The typical testimony begins with a comical description of the lethargy that made attendance impossible in the beginning. This is made even more comical to the contributor's Anglophone ears by the fact that Spanish has a special verb meaning "to unfortunately have to wake up early" (*madrugar*) which almost carries enough of a negative connotation in Peru to be a swear word. The testimony will then shift to the hateful tactics to which parents resorted, usually involving ice water, in order that students might develop the austere habitus of early rising. Finally, testimonies unanimously end with expressions of gratitude, not for what was taught in Seminary, but for its unlocking of a brand new time of day, a time that promises to forever provide an edge over sleeping competitors in the battle for entry into a time-disciplined, capitalist future of scarcity. Ofelia is a seminary teacher in Periféricos Ward. When one of her potential students convinced Nailah, that student's mother, that she really could not get up early, the subordination of scriptural curriculum to early rising was made explicit. OFELIA: It is not correct that Seminary be taught in the afternoon. Nevertheless, Nailah and her daughter didn't want to get up early. Ever since last year Nailah has been pestering me, saying, "Hermana, I want you to teach it in the afternoon." So I consulted with the supervisor [another "called" position], and the supervisor consulted with the brother who is in charge of seminary in all of Arequipa [a CES paid position] and he said that the Area Presidency had prohibited afternoon Seminary because the youth, One—must learn to sacrifice, to get up early, and to get themselves to the places where Seminary is taught; and Two—when youth take Seminary in the morning they start the day with the Spirit because they pray and read the scriptures. So, last year, I told Nailah that, but she didn't give up. She kept insisting and insisting, and since she has some kind of calling in the Young Women, she felt she could just start teaching her daughter seminary in the afternoons without consulting with the supervisor or anyone. One day, another mother approached the supervisor to ask for the registration forms for her daughter and she says, "my daughter is going to take night Seminary," "but, Hermana, there is no night teacher." "Isn't Hermana Nailah teaching it?" And so the supervisor got angry and accused Nailah of attributing to herself the calling of Seminary teacher. Nailah essentially called herself, and that is why the supervisor is constantly checking on that class because as soon as other youth who lived near Nailah found out about it, they were like, "oh yeah, it's in the afternoon?! We don't have to *madrugar* anymore! We're there!" Now she has a decent-sized group, like six students. So we're going to see what happens with that group. How will they end up? Nobody knows. Even though Nailah's students are receiving the same Utah-designed, manual-driven education as Ofelia's own Seminary students, Ofelia worries about how the time difference will affect their future. Mormon Seminary taught in the afternoon may not be enough to counteract the relatively time-undisciplined education that students receive during the rest of their day in arequipeño schools. It certainly will not be enough to prepare students to compete with the intense future centrism of the Utah-style education embodied in the 18 to 20-year-old Anglo missionaries for whom Ofelia cooks every day and with whom her Seminary students will someday be paired when they go on their own missions. Seminary is such an important, foundational aspect of the formation of young Mormon selves that the committee that designs CES curriculum probably holds the greatest power over scriptural interpretation in Mormonism. This is ironic because, unlike the highest leaders of the church whose words are taken to be automatic scripture, almost nobody knows who the members of this Utah-based committee are. Nevertheless, they are the ones who decide which verses of the Book of Mormon the youth in Peru will memorize, which verses they

will summarize, and, importantly, which verses they will conveniently skip.

- ↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:
 - Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:
– Yes

- ↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:
 - Percentage: 1

Notes: 1% is the lowest number allowed in the field. If the question is asking what percentage of the entire square footage of the city of Arequipa, Peru is covered with facilities owned and operated by The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints, the answer is far less than 1%. However, there is one area in Arequipa that is a major exception to this. In the outskirts of the city, there sits an ancient settlement that has been continuously inhabited for the past 3,000 years and that, in the 16th century, the Spanish organized into a small set of dwellings around a central town square. That town is called Carmen Alto. Though not a single one of its approximately 1,000 residents was Mormon before the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints began construction of the Arequipa Temple there in 2017, 37% of Carmen Alto is now owned by the church (see attached map). Though the church owns a much larger percentage of Utah's buildings than it does of Peru's, the "percentage of area" taken up by religious monuments in the average Utah city would still be less than 1% simply because Utah settlements often include vast areas of open space.

- ↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:
 - Square meters: 31457

Notes: This was calculated by using the polygon feature of Google Earth on the above image. 31,457 square meters represents the area of the entire plot of land that the Arequipa temple takes up, not the square meters of floor space inside the temple itself. According to <https://churchofjesuschristtemples.org/statistics/dimensions/> the square footage of the Arequipa temple's actual floor space is 26,969. In square meters that is 2,505.

- ↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
 - Height, meters: 25

Notes: This is an estimate, see photo.

- ↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
 - Height, square meters: 3239

Notes: 3,239 square meters is the area of the polygon of land covered by the Mormon meeting house that the contributor attended every Sunday in 2018 in Arequipa, Peru. There are about 20 such meeting houses in Peru which are shared by approximately 45 separate congregations. This square footage includes a concrete soccer court which usually takes up about half of each meeting house's land space. Mormon church meeting houses in Utah usually do not have outdoor soccer courts, instead they have large parking lots and indoor basketball courts. The size of the land of the meeting house that the contributor attended in 2017 in Utah, which was

average-sized for a Mormon meeting house in Utah, is 13,756 square meters, about 4 times larger than the largest comparable meeting house in Arequipa. This is not counting the 9,421 square meter baseball field right next to the meeting house which, though it is not precisely owned by the church, has no fence between it and the church and is often used for church events.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 7

Notes: Most Mormon meeting houses in both Peru and Utah are single story buildings, however, especially in Utah, they often have high vaulted ceilings which add to their height. Most Mormon meeting houses in Peru and Utah also have decorative steeples that increase this average height estimate.

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage of area: 1

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: The Arequipa temple was the global church's 167th dedicated temple and Peru's 3rd. The Lima, Peru temple, dedicated in 1986, was South America's 3rd temple and the world's 38th. Mormon temples must not be confused with every-day Mormon meeting-houses (chapels). Mormon temples are the only places that offer the rites of eternal exaltation (the highest form of salvation), rites that culminate in marriage and that depend on heteronormative, Utah-centric definitions of kinship. For the prophet and president of the church corporation to have selected Arequipa as a temple site and center of a "temple district," local Mormons in the city must have first established an administrative "Zion" to the extent that most of their small congregations (branches) meeting in rented buildings had graduated into larger congregations (wards) meeting in relatively luxurious chapels, architecturally designed in and funded by church headquarters in Salt Lake City, Utah. These wards must have further multiplied enough to be geographically bounded into many, relatively self-governing "stakes of Zion" rather than remaining under one large, Utah-controlled "mission." The conglomeration of these "stakes" (Arequipa has seven) each with their seven or eight wards, must have enough "worthy families" to warrant the multimillion-dollar construction of a temple. Adult Mormons who are "temple worthy" are privileged to make an oath inside their holy temples as part of a ritual called the endowment. They pledge to sacrifice everything, "for the building up of the Kingdom of God on the earth and for the establishment of Zion" (Mormons In Transition 2011, 30). They are then left to define Zion for themselves. On the one hand, Zion claims to be open to all and is supposed to ceremonially bind all humans into a universal kinship. On the other, its ultimate symbol, its architectural culmination, and the only spot of earth where such binding—"sealing"—can be done is the temple, the same temple that is only open to the most "worthy"

of Saints. The pinnacle of Zion's inclusiveness lies inside one of the most exclusive buildings on the planet. This foundational paradox does not exist without ramifications for Peruvian Mormon lives. Work Cited Mormons in Transition. 2011. "[1990] The Mormon Temple Endowment Ceremony." Institute for Religious Research. 2011. <http://mit.irr.org/mormon-temple-endowment-ceremony>.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: Every temple has at least two altars.

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: The sites of important occurrences in Anglo Mormon history throughout their series of exoduses from New York to Utah are marked with commemorative plaques, buildings, monuments, and even temples, all owned by the church and often deemed holy or sacred. For example, the Sacred Grove where Joseph Smith is thought to have seen his first vision is owned by the church. On the other hand, the sites of important occurrences in the Book of Mormon that happened in what is now Peru are not marked at all nor does the church officially consider them holy despite the fact that most Peruvian Mormons recognize these sites as sacred places and cite ethnoarchaeological evidence to establish their Book of Mormon authenticity and historicity. Basilio Corimayta, a Peruvian known to the contributor from a small town near Arequipa who has lived in Utah since 1983, knew the Book of Mormon was a true history of Peru the moment he saw it because "there was a TON of coincidence, too much coincidence to not be true." When asked what some of those coincidences were, he said that in Machu Picchu there is a place called Intihuatana. It looks like a sundial and it is the place where the Inca king tied the sun in the sky for 36 hours so that the people could finish building Cuzco. This night without darkness matches the cosmic sign of Christ's birth that the Americas received according to the Book of Mormon. Such ethnoarchaeological proofs of the Book of Mormon's historicity, however, are part of a narrative that is increasingly at odds with the official church which, ironically, desires to distance itself from the idea that the Book of Mormon is a history of the Amerindians with a verifiable geography and sacred places that still exist. The church seeks this distance because the racist paternalism implicit in Lamanite identity is currently clashing with the colorblind, post-racial modernity the church is striving to embrace. Lamanite identity—the very identity the church helped create—has become a public relations problem; something to be mitigated and, if possible, ignored until it goes away. True Lamanites, however, as owners of the Book of Mormon, are not going away. They are adding details to the story, connecting the end of the written narrative to what they see in the ruins of civilizations around them today. As Jacoba Arriátegui, a Peruvian Mormon who has lived in Utah for over 40 years, told the contributor in an interview in December 2017 in the basement of her daughter's large home in Salsands, Utah: I brought my kids over here [to the U.S. from Peru] when they were very little. They didn't know Peru. But little by little I am taking them back and teaching them what Peru is and what the ruins are and all the things that are over there. Three years ago I took Arcadio H., my son. We went to Trujillo and he just stood there agape, looking. "Mamá," he said. "This is [the Book of Mormon city of] Zarahemla." "Zarahemla?" [I asked]. "What did Zarahemla look like, Mamá? It was a walled city, and what was the width of the walls, Mamá? Because it describes them right there in the Book [of Mormon]," he said. They were almost one meter thick, and the city was right next to the sea. "This is it." He tells me. "Here you have the ruins of Zarahemla. Look at the walls. Look at the height of the parapets that are so high, and look at how they were described as terminating vertically one by one. It is all here." ... So I go about teaching my kids little by little and every time I go to Peru I take one with me, or some grandkids, and I go about teaching them the story of the Book of Mormon, "here it is," I tell them, "Look." Her husband, Arcadio Costa, was sitting close to her and the contributor watching TV during this interview, but he could not contain himself and chimed in, ARCADIO: Frankly, I had a book. I don't remember where I left it, but it tells of Incas named Viracocha and Pachacutec. Their God tells them, "here my God was sitting." The God, what did they call him? He had a name, and with his finger he drew many worlds—and that is a book that is not Mormon—and it says that those

many worlds were his. So, what is it that the Book of Mormon teaches us? JASON: That God made many worlds before this one? ARCADIO: Of course. So, how did this Inca know that God had many worlds? It must be that when the Lord came here to the Americas, he arrived over there [in Peru] and not here [in North America]. And he spoke with the Incas and with the Indigenous people that were over there ... So after that, it says that four brothers arrived ... so these were the four Brothers Ayar that it talks about, and one of them stayed in Peru and one went to Mexico in order to establish what they brought, which was much more advanced than what the Incas had. Do you see? The history of Peru is a vast history and it is similar to the Book of Mormon. JASON: Meaning the four brothers would be Nephi, Sam, Laman, and Lemuel? ARCADIO: Yep, but they call them the four Brothers Ayar in their Quechua language, see? JASON: And why do you think that artists of Book of Mormon scenes always depict only Mexico? I mean, you can see Aztec temples in that famous painting with Jesus descending from heaven, as if it all only happened in Mesoamerica, but not in Peru. JACOBA: Because they only know what it's like close around here: Mexico. The artists only know Mexico but they haven't exactly studied Peru. They can't even imagine the grandeur that exists in Peru. They can't fathom it. Because if they went, they would remember the descriptions of Zarahemla, what it was like ... And they would enter, and if they relived the scenes of Zarahemla they would find that it is a walled city close to the sea as described. ARCADIO: And in Machu Picchu, we saw with our own eyes the--- JACOBA: ---the baptismal fonts. Jacoba and Arcadio's discussion does not sound like speculation. They are sure that some of the Book of Mormon's events happened in Peru. However, Arcadio and Jacoba are not white. Their surety does not count as official church knowledge. As such, the following 2018 statement from the church—one of the few times an official church publication has used the word "Lamanite" since 1999 to imply contemporary people—came to them as a slap in the face: Just as the history of the northern ten tribes of Israel after their exile in Assyria is a matter of speculation rather than knowledge, the history of the Lamanites after the close of the Book of Mormon record is a matter of speculation. The Church asserts that all members are part of the covenant house of Israel either by descent or adoption but does not take a position on the specific geography of the Book of Mormon or claim a complete knowledge about the origins of any specific modern group in the Americas or the Pacific. (<https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/history/topics/lamanite-identity?lang=eng>) The problem with this declaration's parsing of the terms "speculation" and "knowledge" is that, for the church, white people's speculation is knowledge and Peruvian knowledge is speculation. Were it not so, Peru would be riddled with as many official Mormon devotional markers as the U.S.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

— Yes

Notes: These are Mormon meeting houses, also known as chapels.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

— Yes [specify]: conference centers, institute buildings, etc.

Is iconography present:

— Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

— On persons

— At home

— Some public spaces

Notes: As to iconography in homes: Family home evening, also called "Family Night" was an initiative started by the church in the 1960's—complete with a manual—wherein nuclear

families are supposed to drop social, professional, and even ecclesiastical affairs one night a week, preferably Monday, and spend time together singing, studying scriptures, and, most of all, having “wholesome recreational activities” (<https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/scriptures/the-family-a-proclamation-to-the-world/the-family-a-proclamation-to-the-world?lang=eng>), incidentally, that link will take you to a document that is perhaps the most common form of iconography on the walls of Peruvian Mormon homes. It is a single-page document called THE FAMILY A PROCLAMATION TO THE WORLD and it can be found framed or pinned up in the homes of most Peruvian Mormons, see photo). In Utah this has become a consumerist extravaganza. Not only do most movie theaters, bowling alleys, and “fun zones” advertise Monday “Family Night” specials, but LDS bookstores, such as the church-owned Deseret Book, sell all kinds of Book of Mormon-themed Family Night games and supplies. One popular Deseret Book item the contributor has seen on the walls of many Peruvian Mormons in Utah is a peg board whereupon the hand-painted names of family members are cycled weekly through Family Night’s different roles. Any visitor to the home during the week will see that it is Tatiana’s turn to say the opening prayer, Mamá’s turn to decide on the activity, Junior’s turn to give the lesson, and Papá’s turn to provide the refreshments. Family Night, therefore, not only gives Utah businesses a chance to demonstrate their Mormon-friendliness, it gives Mormon families a material way (home décor) to show off their dedication to achieving the only social grouping that is legible in Mormonism as “family.” Peruvians in Peru—who are constantly being joined by new converts to Mormonism—feel they come up short in catching the spirit of this nuclear family culture, so they often combine many families together for Family Night in order to teach the new and potential members among them how it is to be done.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

— Yes

Notes: Church iconography runs a wide gamut. Everything is fare game from replicas of Book of Mormon objects, such as the animate brass compass Lehi used to navigate from the Middle East to the Americas, to the mark of the compass sewn into Mormon sacred, white undergarments. However, as far as church meeting houses go, the church recently (May 2020) mandated that only a few dozen paintings would be approved for display on foyer walls. Every single one of the approved paintings depicts a white, Nordic-looking Jesus.

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

— No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

— Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

— No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

— Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

— Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: One distinguishing characteristic of Peruvian Mormon iconography is that Jesus is depicted as strikingly, anachronistically white. This of course stems from the church's official representations of Jesus. As Kwame Ture said, the church takes its racism "to such ludicrous heights that it paints Jesus Christ white even though he never put his foot in Europe" (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yQrDBZfDjZA>). It is interesting to note that Mormon depictions of Jesus by successful Anglo Mormon artists in Utah sometimes become so popular in Peru that their art is used by other churches, even ones that are quite antagonistic to Mormonism. The Anglo artist does not know his art is being used in Peru and the Peruvian does not know that the art is Mormon. In a particularly ironic example, the contributor noted that in Arequipa, many Catholic homes have stickers on their windows with different phrases and imagery warning any oncoming missionaries that they are Catholic and will not be baptized into any new sect. One such door posted "we are Catholic here" under the image of a Nordic Jesus painted by famous Mormon artist Greg Olson. <https://www.google.com/search?hl=EN&gl=US&tbm=isch&q=Greg%20Olson%20Jesus>

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Obligatory for some

Notes: The full-time Mormon mission (obligatory for "worthy" "able" males between the ages of 18 and 26) is a pilgrimage in every anthropological sense of the term. From the opening of the "mission call" envelope wherein Mormon teenagers discover together with their family the exotic or familiar world city God has reserved specifically for their evangelizing impact, the Mormon mission is both a pilgrimage and a rite of passage. For Catholics, sites are often considered sacred because a localized miracle is an announcement that "worship is to be rendered in a place" (Weibel 2005, 116). For followers of the New Age, "the planet Earth gives off energy that is stronger in some places than in others" (116). The founders of anthropological pilgrimage studies, Edith and Victor Turner, consider pilgrimage to these sacred sites a ritualistic and "liminal phenomena" (Turner 1979) in that it fosters *communitas*, or the space between the structures of society. Pilgrims seek the liminoid, or some kind of contact in the sacred center beyond social structure. Pilgrimage is, among other things on the Turners' list, "movement from a mundane center to a sacred periphery which suddenly, transiently, becomes central for the individual, an axis mundi of his faith" (Turner & Turner 2011, 34). The central purpose of sending Mormon youth to serve missions in places not of their choosing, places peripheral to their experience, is to give the missionaries, not the missionized, an axis mundi of faith. These missionaries, as pilgrims, achieve "direct contact with the sacred" (Winkelman & Dubisch 2005, xxiii) "unmediated by holy church powers and representatives" (xxii). In fact, one of God's mouthpieces on earth today, a member of The Quorum of The Twelve Apostles, tried to explain his lack of mediation in the process whereby full-time Mormon

missionaries (his audience for the following quotation) are assigned their own personal sacred place to missionize. In those sessions when I ... participate in deciding [which missionary] the Lord would call [to which mission], I simply would say this to you: That you be careful. If there is anyone in this room who is saying, "I wonder if I was called by mistake," or "I wonder if that's really the place for me," I just warn you: You be careful! I'll just tell you, no member of The Twelve called you. It was not a human choice. It was not a computer that did it. I'll just tell you that of all the experiences I've had of having the mind of the Lord made fairly clear—or VERY clear—nothing compares to the experience of those moments of missionaries being assigned. (Eyring 2011, min. 0:49) God himself selects the place where each missionary is to go, meaning that the mission area is an intimately personal holy land for each missionary. This makes the mission a pilgrimage. However, the Mormon mission is also a textbook rite of passage as if lifted directly from the pages of Arnold Van Gennep's (1961) book *The Rites of Passage* where "the liminal period" between "rites of separation" and "rites of incorporation" was coined. The young missionary is first put through a ritual, called the "setting apart," after which the missionary remains apart until being ritually "released" post mission. During this "apart" time they may not embrace members of the opposite sex, even kin, and their telecommunication with kin is severely restricted. The entire 1.5 to 2-year mission (depending on gender) is the liminoid in many of the ways Victor Turner (1979) outlines: The neophytes are empty vessels into which the doctrine of their society (in this case, church) is poured, if they do not "return with honor" (see attached photo) after having completed their full mission period (tour of duty) they become nonpersons in their society (especially if they are male, see Doty et. al. 2015), they are at the complete mercy of their mission president, and (again, similar to the military) they have nothing "to demarcate them structurally from their fellows" (234). Mormon missionaries must stay with their assigned "companion" at all times except to go to the restroom. Companion assignments change every few months. Today, Peruvians are almost always called to serve missions within Peru where they are likely to have ten different companions during their mission. Five of those will likely be from Peru, Bolivia or Chile, five will likely be from the U.S., and two or three of those five will likely be from Utah (see attached photo). Often, in interviews with the contributor, Peruvian Mormons who live in Utah include in their migration story the fact that they had "friends" in Utah with whom they stayed when they first arrived from Peru. Pedro is a case in point. The Anglo friends Pedro mentioned having in Utah were his former mission companions who, having gone through the same rite of passage, became his blood-brothers (soldiers from the same platoon). Companionships receive identical living stipends and eat and dress the same though one companion be from cosmopolitan Sundance, Utah and the other be, as Pedro was, from a *barriada* (ghetto) in Lima without running water. This temporarily equalizing aspect of the mission fosters *communitas* in the world-wide "Mormon supranation" (Knowlton 2008) through the liminality of missionary work and the "homogeneity and comradeship" (Turner 1969, 82) it engenders. However, the *communitas* in a mission companionship consisting of a Utahan and a *limeño* is not created from an equitable fusion of U.S. and Peruvian cultures. The culture of Mormonism's global "imagined community" (Anderson 2006, title) or universal supranation—what Mormons unironically call "gospel culture" (Oaks 2012, title)—is seen by outsiders as essentially the culture of 1950's rural Utah (O'Dea 1957), of U.S. settler-coloniality (Taylor 2000) and of capitalist ambition (Ong 2003). In this sense, there is nothing "Peruvian" about it. Nevertheless, since Mormons imagine gospel culture to be a placeless, divine construct, they believe it accrues as "cultural capital" (Bourdieu 1994) in the socio-spiritual bank accounts of all Mormons regardless of nationality. This placeless universality does not mean gospel culture is not implicitly centered around the place of Utah in the minds of many Mormons, it simply means that all Mormons, marked and unmarked, should, in theory, be able to fully live gospel culture even though doing so may, in practice, require immigrating to Utah. When Pedro returned from his mission, the shock of inequality from sudden re-entry into Peruvian structure motivated him to immigrate to Utah wherein the bulk of his blood-brotherhood and cultural capital had now coalesced. Works Cited (in order of appearance) Weibel, Deana L. 2005. "Of Consciousness Changes and Fortified Faith: Creativist and Catholic Pilgrimage at French Catholic Shrines." In *Pilgrimage and Healing*, edited by Jill Dubisch and Michael Winkelman, 111-34. Tucson, AZ: University of Arizona Press. Turner, Victor. 1979. "[1967] Betwixt and Between: The Liminal Period in Rites de Passage." In *Reader in Comparative Religion: An Anthropological Approach*, edited by William Armand Lessa and Evon Zartman Vogt, 234-43. New York: Harper & Row. Turner, Victor, and Edith Turner. 2011. [1978] *Image and Pilgrimage in Christian Culture*. New York: Columbia University

Press. Winkelman, Michael, and Jill Dubisch. 2005. "Introduction: The Anthropology of Pilgrimage." In *Pilgrimage and Healing*, edited by Jill Dubisch and Michael Winkelman, ix-xxxvi. Tucson, AZ: University of Arizona Press. Eyring, Henry. 2011. Poderoso Mensaje a Los Misioneros. Presidente Eyring. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3c8fQM9vsiU>. Van Gennep, Arnold. 1961. [1908] *The Rites of Passage*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press. Doty, Kristine J., S. Zachary Bullock, Harmony Packer, Russell T. Warner, and James Westwood. 2015. "Return with Trauma: Understanding the Experiences of Early Returned Missionaries." *Issues in Religion and Psychotherapy* 37 (1, article 9): 33-45. Knowlton, David. 2008. "Go Ye to All the World: The LDS Church and the Organization of International Society." In *Revisiting Thomas F. O'Dea's The Mormons: Contemporary Perspectives*, edited by Cardell K. Jacobson, John P. Hoffmann, and Tim B. Heaton, 390-412. Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press. Turner, Victor. 1969. *The Ritual Process: Structure and Anti-Structure*. Aldine. Anderson, Benedict. 2006. [1983] *Imagined Communities: Reflections on the Origin and Spread of Nationalism*. London ; New York: Verso. Oaks, Dallin H. 2012. "The Gospel Culture." *The Ensign of the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter Day Saints*, 2012. O'Dea, Thomas F. 1957. *The Mormons*. 1st Edition edition. The University of Chicago Press. Taylor, Lori Elaine. 2000. "Telling Stories about Mormons and Indians." PhD diss., State University of New York at Buffalo. Ong, Aihwa. 2003. *Buddha Is Hiding: Refugees, Citizenship, the New America*. Berkeley: University of California Press. Bourdieu, Pierre. 1994. "Social Capital: Preliminary Notes." In P. Bourdieu: *Sociological Texts*, edited by Nikos Panagiotopoulos, 91-95. Athens: Delfini.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

— Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

— Yes

Notes: The body and the spirit form one entity called the soul. A individual spirit's purpose in coming to earth is to receive a body so that the individual can become a complete soul. In Mormonism, the powers that the body has are often considered more important than the powers that the spirit has. For example, a spirit cannot procreate. Procreation, inasmuch as it is part of the nuclear family, is one of Mormonism's most vital concepts.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

— No

Notes: This is an extremely important distinction for Mormonism. Spirit is conceived of as ontologically distinct from body, BUT it is not conceived of as non-material. Spirit is made of a much more refined matter than body, but it is made of matter nonetheless.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

— Yes [specify]: In Anglo Mormonism, an individual soul is the combination of one spirit and one body.

Notes: However, in Andean Mormonism, there is the possibility that a soul could be made of two or more spirits in a single body. Put differently, the Anglo Mormon person is made up of dividual parts and individual parts; material parts and spiritual parts, but these parts all combine into one whole soul. Peruvians in Arequipa are made up of many parts as well, but souls are just some of these parts, not the whole person. A living Mormon body is a soul. A living arequipeño body

contains many souls. Some of these souls stick around after the body has decomposed, some go to Christian heavens, but others merge back into collective ancestral inner worlds that produce the material of new humans. Though she is Mormon and has lived in upper-class Salsands, Utah for decades, Jacoba (a Peruvian) still retains parts of this cyclical ancestral idiom that complicates the individuated family. When she talks of her ancestors, she tears the Western arboreal analogy of genealogy apart at the middle. She once said to the contributor, "I always tell human beings: 'Look. Plant: Your kids are your branches and your grandkids are your roots, and they remain there, planted.'" As a Mormon, she has seen countless "family tree" depictions where grandchildren fall below children. These trees sprout individual ancestors as branches and individual descendants as roots. Yet, Jacoba places descendants (kids and grandkids) as both the branches and the roots; the future and the past. Hers is a family rhizome, not a tree, because children can give parts of themselves to parents, making parents descendants as much as antecedents. Furthermore, since the cycle of reciprocity in Peru has little to do with genetics or vertical blood descent, anybody who gives and takes of the substance of relatedness and coresidence could become a dividual within Jacoba's genealogy. Individuals incorporate parts to delimit wholes while dividuals give up parts to expand wholes. Dealing with parts of dividual people is a matter-of-fact aspect of living in the Andes, even for Mormons whose doctrine of primordial individuality does not seem capacious enough to allow for these agentive parts of self. Ofelia (a member of a Mormon congregation in Arequipa, Peru) has had experiences with dividual souls. OFELIA: In our enclosed courtyard we saw a man who was over by the fig trees. He was tall with his white shirt and straw hat. When we saw him, I said, "Shannon, look." And we both saw the man hide among the trees ... "Who is there?" Nobody answered, and nobody ever came out. The next afternoon, Ofelia's grandmother, who lived next door, came to tell her that her uncle, who also lived next door, had died that morning. JASON: You mean that the spirit in the orchard was your uncle, but your uncle was still alive at that moment? OFELIA: In that moment he was still alive, but we saw his spirit walking. That is why there are some Catholic beliefs [laughs] that say that the spirit makes its last rounds to say goodbye to people. Ofelia dismisses as pejoratively "Catholic" the belief that part of a live person can wander unbeknownst to the person's other parts. Though Ofelia may have found the belief connected to it laughable, the fact of clothed spirits walking was such a standard part of her social milieu that it was undeniable. For a non-Mormon example, the PTA of the contributor's daughter's school in Arequipa celebrated a pachamanca (earth meal) requiring the improvisation of a brick earth-oven in which to cook chicken and potatoes. The PTA president, a Quechua-speaking grandmother who always dressed in her town's traditional clothing, sent her unassuming husband to go look for bricks in the back of the schoolyard. He came back saying that he found some bricks, but that a human baby was crying beneath them, and he did not want to disturb it. His wife scolded him, "it's just a baby's alma penando (pining soul). Go get the bricks!" Before eventually complying, he mumbled that perhaps the bricks themselves had taken on soul and that he would not be held responsible if the chicken got baked back into animation. Though only a passing comment, likely a joke, the danger that bricks or stones can become subjects, thus making humans their objects, is real in his altiplano village.

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Food:

– Yes

Notes: Heavenly Father cares if Mormons break their health code (the Word Of Wisdom) even though it was originally given as a mere suggestion and explicitly "not by way of commandment." Also, there is nothing in the original code (from the Doctrine and Covenants, here: <https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/scriptures/dc-testament/dc/89.1,2,4?lang=eng&clang=eng#p1,2,4>) that would give the reader the slightest clue as to how the contemporary code is understood. If one were to follow the original code, one would have to be vegetarian and eat only locally available fruits, vegetables, and grains. The contemporary health code involves none of that and only includes negative language. One must completely avoid coffee, the tea leaf, alcohol, tobacco, and illicit drugs. The code has been interpreted in many Andean Mormon congregations as requiring the prohibition of coca, a millennial herb vital to Andean culture. Interestingly, hierba mate has not been prohibited nearly as often in Mormon congregations in Argentina, Uruguay and Paraguay where it is consumed almost constantly even during Mormon worship services. The demonizing of coca (largely in Bolivia) and the acceptance of hierba mate, both of which are mild stimulants, probably has something to do with the way coca is associated with indigeneity and hierba mate with whiteness. In other words, the inequitable application of the Word of Wisdom in South America reveals Mormonism's fundamental anti-indigeneity and white supremacy similar to the way disproportionate sentencing for crack cocaine possession (associated with Black people) over powder cocaine possession (associated with white people) reveals the anti-blackness fundamental to the U.S. judicial system. The racism behind the Word of Wisdom also plays out in the Pacific Islands where Mormonism has become extremely widespread. The kava ceremony, vital to conceptions of masculinity on many islands and in many Tongan and Samoan neighborhoods of Salt Lake City, Utah, has been deemed against the Word of Wisdom.

Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: And here we see the mix of two taboos that Heavenly Father cares about. Only worthy Mormons can enter the holy temples of Mormonism. One of the questions to which Mormons must answer affirmatively if they want to enter the temple is "do you obey the Word Of Wisdom?" People who do not obey the Word Of Wisdom defile Mormonism's most sacred space, and people who chew coca (most people in the high Andes) are often considered to be in violation of the Word Of Wisdom. This contributes to a situation in Peruvian Mormon temple worship wherein a brown body is automatically more suspect than a white body of profaning the sacredness of the space, a space that is saturated in white pigmented symbology.

Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: Notably in Anglo Mormonism, especially in Utah, the U.S. flag is a sacred object that Heavenly Father cares about more than any other nation's flag. This idea spreads to Peruvian Mormons in Utah because of the church's long standing relationship to the Boy Scouts of America (an organization with its own horrendous anti-indigeneity and settler adoption fantasy). Peruvian Mormons in Utah are part of Spanish-speaking congregations that the Anglo Mormon leadership in Utah considers mere training grounds for Latin Americans who, when they become fully "Mormonized" are supposed to graduate into fully-fledged English-speaking congregations. Latin American Mormons rarely do this, however. They stay in Spanish-Speaking congregations even if they prefer English because these congregations provide a refuge from the whiteness, what Peruvian

Mormons call "la gringada," that oppresses them in most other venues of their lives. Yet, at the same time, they see English-speaking congregations as practicing a more advanced, superior form of Mormonism. Part of the superior nature of these English-speaking congregations is that they often have long, generational traditions of strong Scouting programs that are integrally interwoven into the church's rites of passage for males, which involve ordination to the holy priesthood. Religiosity, U.S. patriotism, and "playing Indian" become so intertwined in these congregations that the U.S. flag sewn onto each Boy Scout's uniform becomes a symbol as sacred as the "sign of the compass" sewn into the breast of the sacred undergarments their Scout Masters wear. Rather than transferring into English-speaking congregations*, Latin American Mormons wish to increase the level of spirituality in their own Spanish-speaking congregations so that they can catch up and even surpass the level of spirituality in English-Speaking congregations. Spanish-speaking congregations that wish to rise to English-speaking congregations' level of righteousness often come to see a successful scouting program as a key indicator of that rise. Peruvian Mormons in Utah are extremely proud of their children who have achieved the Eagle Scout designation, especially if they have done so within a Spanish-speaking congregation's very own scouting program. Scouting often involves multi-troop camp-outs where scouts from these Spanish-speaking congregations (who tend to prefer English) and their leaders (who sometimes cannot speak English) compete with scouts from English-speaking congregations in all kinds of outdoor events, such as getting back into a capsized canoe from the middle of a deep pond, that most Spanish-speaking scouts, coming from inner cities in Utah, have not exactly had occasion to practice. The end result is that scouts from Spanish-speaking congregations perform dismally in most of these areas. One of the ways their leaders have them compensate for these humiliations is by not humiliating themselves further through sloppy uniforms. The Spanish-speaking leaders become extremely strict and knowledgeable in uniform regulations, including and especially the treatment of the U.S. flag patch that must go in a certain place and in a certain orientation (certainly not upside-down) on a particular one of each scouts' shoulders. One Peruvian Mormon scout master who saw the rise of Spanish-speaking scouting in Northern Utah, became emotional in an interview with the contributor as he described what the scouting uniform meant to him and how he always taught his scouts to not throw their uniform on the ground with the rest of the dirty laundry as if it were just any old shirt. This scout master was the aforementioned Basilio Corimayta. Since the BSA uniform includes a U.S. flag patch, and since, if a U.S. flag touches the ground it must be ceremonially burned, he taught his scouts to treat their entire uniform like a U.S. flag and never let it touch the ground. Incidentally, during the contributor's fieldwork in 2018, Peru's national team made it into the FIFA World Cup for the first time in 35 years. This was a huge deal among the Peruvian Mormon community in Utah, and Basilio, an avid soccer fan and proud Peruvian, often wore a Peruvian national team jersey in support. The jersey had a Peruvian flag patch sewn into it. One day, as the contributor was taking photos of Basilio's home decor as part of this project (see photo) he noticed that among the clothing on the floor around the washing machine lay Basilio's Peruvian national team jersey. Apparently, he did not hold the Peruvian flag as sacred as he held the U.S. flag despite the fact that, at the time, he was an undocumented alien as far as the U.S. government was concerned. This is all to say that scouting's role in the Utah instantiation of Peruvian Mormonism has made the U.S. flag an explicitly sacred object. As a result of the BSA's welcoming of homosexual scout masters, the church announced its schism from scouting. It later announced that it would begin its own youth program in 2020 that would not resemble scouting, and, as such, be available to youth all over the world. Perhaps it realized that trying to be a global organization while holding onto an explicitly U.S. exceptionalist program was hurting its multicultural image, especially in Latin America. However, its elimination of scouting has left many Latin American Mormons in Utah floundering to find what the mark of full inclusion into Anglo Mormonism is now supposed to be. After working for decades to finally bring their scouting programs up to the level of the English-speaking programs in Utah, the church pulled the entire program out from under them. *The contributor knows of many Peruvian Mormons in Utah who have transferred to English-speaking congregations only to return to their Spanish-speaking congregation one year later. The reasons these Peruvian Mormons return to their Spanish-speaking ward include never

being given a "calling" or responsibility within the English-speaking ward, rarely being greeted or spoken to in the English-speaking ward, being the victim of constant microaggressions in the English-speaking ward, being the victim of overt racism in the English-speaking ward, and being told by the bishop of the English-speaking ward, "I feel prompted to tell you that you should attend the Spanish-speaking ward." For more information about Spanish-speaking Mormon congregations in the U.S., see the works of Ignacio Garcia, such as his book *Chicano While Mormon: Activism, War, and Keeping the Faith*. Also see the following book chapters: Garcia, Ignacio M. 2015. "A Barrio Perspective on Building Zion in the Twenty-First Century." In *A Book of Mormons: Latter-Day Saints on a Modern-Day Zion*, edited by Emily W. Jensen and Tracy McKay-Lamb, 69-75. I Speak for Myself. Ashland, Oregon: White Cloud Press. Garcia, Ignacio M. 2018. "Empowering Latino Saints to Transcend Historical Racialism: A Bishop's Tale." In *Decolonizing Mormonism: Approaching a Postcolonial Zion*, edited by Gina Colvin and Joanna Brooks, 139-60. Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: female chastity and clothing, enforcing the nuclearization of family, delegitimizing all family models associated with people of Color,

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: all non-marital sexual practices and homosexual practices are sin. Up until 2015 at least, the official church considered interethnic marriage ill advised.

Notes: There was a short time in the late 80's when the official church published in its Handbook of Instructions that oral sex within marriage was sinful.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Another of the questions to which Mormons must answer affirmatively if they are to

receive or renew their "temple recommend" card required for temple entry is, "are you honest in all your dealings with your fellow man."

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: Part of the temple rite known as the endowment involves many oaths. God takes the breaking of these very seriously. The officiator in the ceremony himself states, "God will not be mocked."

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: There are plenty of scriptures in the Mormon canon that focus on Puritanical time thrift, such as this one: "the day of this life is the day for men to perform their labors. And now, as I said unto you before, as ye have had so many witnesses, therefore, I beseech of you that ye do not procrastinate the day of your repentance until the end; for after this day of life, which is given us to prepare for eternity, behold, if we do not improve our time while in this life, then cometh the night of darkness wherein there can be no labor performed."

[https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/scriptures/bofm/alma/34.32,33?](https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/scriptures/bofm/alma/34.32,33?lang=eng&clang=eng#p32,33)

lang=eng&clang=eng#p32,33 As Anglo Mormons often associate laziness with indigeneity and blackness, they have written an entire curriculum called the Self-Reliance Initiative that they piloted in Latin America and Africa. The entire thrust of this curriculum is to make its students feel guilty about three principal things: 1) every moment they waste not trying to earn money, 2) every time they are unpunctual, and, 3) every time they depend for financial help on their "extended family" or (God forbid) their church. Members of Perifericos Ward in Arequipa, Peru in 2018, including the contributor, were required by their local church leaders to sign up for one of 4 Self-Reliance course offerings. Many members who applied for church financial assistance in this ward were required to first present a diploma from one of these 12-week courses before their assistance was granted. The hope behind adding this prerequisite for financial help was that, after finishing what amounted to a 12-week guilt trip, members would blame their financial situation on their own laziness and no longer have the gall to ask for help.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: Contention is of the devil.

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: This is one fourth of the four fold mission statement of the church.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but not that much. Heavenly Father seems to care much more about protecting his church from moochers than he does about distributing the immense stores of His church's wealth equitably.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: genealogy, statistics, preserving textual history.

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

- ↳ Other purpose:
 - Yes [specify]: resurrect the dead

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

- ↳ A supreme high god is present:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
 - Yes

Notes: Not only is He anthropomorphic his is "anglopomorphic" in that he is imagined as a light-skinned, muscular, tall, heteronormative cysgender male who is nearly identical in appearance to his son Jesus Christ. Joseph Smith saw God the Father and his son Jesus Christ standing together above him in the air. Reportedly, as published on the official church website (see attached article), Joseph Smith said that Jesus was light complected and had blue eyes.

- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No

- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - Yes
 - Notes: He is a kin relation to all humans, including elites.

- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - Yes [specify]: their words are his words

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Yes [specify]: he has a body of flesh and bone and once inhabited a mortal body
 - Notes: There is debate as to whether the following oft-repeated statement by an early

20th century prophet of the church is "doctrine": "As man now is, God once was; as God now is, man may be." (see attached article)

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Mormons believe their God is the God of everyone, which is why their president and his two councilors, who speak God's words, produce proclamations "to the world" and not simply to their church's membership. See this video of the contemporary prophet and president of the church giving his newest proclamation to the world:

<https://newsroom.churchofjesuschrist.org/article/restoration-proclamation>

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: how to create other ones like it, which He has done many times before

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: Prosperity theology has become a very strong cultural element of Utah-Mormonism that creates some tension with Peruvian Mormonism. In Peru there is a traditional sense that wealth symbolizes greed and anti-social behavior. In Utah, however, there is a strong sense among Anglo Mormons that wealth is a reward from God that he reserves for the righteous. Many Peruvian Mormon immigrants quickly adopt this cultural value when they arrive in Utah as it is part of the American Dream. Also, they see that the men called to be bishops in the Mormon congregations around them often happen to be the wealthiest members of their congregations. This happens so commonly that they begin to assume that riches are a prerequisite for high leadership positions in Utah-Mormonism. Since leaders are seen as being more righteous or closer to God than their parishioners, and since they are also usually far wealthier than their parishioners, it becomes easy to consider riches as a reward from God for righteousness.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: As a testament to Mormonism's fundamental antiblackness, many Anglo Mormons in Utah interpreted Hurricane Katrina as a punishment from God because it largely affected Black people. When natural disasters affect majority white populations they are seen as "trials" from God meant to impel his chosen people towards higher levels of devotion. As to the COVID-19 pandemic, many Peruvian Mormons (such as those who decided to translate the attached article and publish it in the Peruvian Mormon-founded Mormon news outlet MasFe) think that, rather than a punishment, it represents a sort of "incubation period" they liken unto a butterfly's chrysalis. God has always used persecution to "socially distance" his chosen people so that they can emerge, after the pandemic, stronger and more beautiful than ever. In this way, persecution and triumph over persecution are the marks of a chosen people.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Since Peruvian Mormons believe in the Reina Valera version of the Old Testament, and since the high god of that book can be jealous and angry, their supreme high god

exhibits negative emotion. However, it is important to note that Mormons believe the god, Jehovah of the Old Testament is actually not the supreme high god. Jehovah is Jesus, the son of the supreme high god, also known as Heavenly Father or Elohim. Jehovah was what Jesus called himself before he got a body. Though Mormons understand Elohim and Jesus to be extremely similar in temperament, there is a sense in the Book of Mormon, especially in the book of Jacob chapter 5, that Elohim is somewhat less patient and less merciful than Jesus. That chapter presents an allegory likening the House of Israel unto a corrupted vineyard. The master of the vineyard (who seems to represent Elohim) is extremely "pained" that his vineyard has become corrupt, but he just wants to burn it and start over. The servant of the vineyard (who seems to represent Jesus or Jehovah) continually convinces the master to wait a little longer and keep trying to salvage the good parts of the vineyard rather than scrapping the entire thing.
<https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/scriptures/bofm/jacob/5?lang=eng>

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Hunger in the sense that Elohim needs to fill his belly with food? No. Hunger in the sense that Elohim feels lack and needs something to fill that void? Yes. As we are all literally His spirit children from a nuclear family in "the preexistence," He misses us just like any U.S. 1950's sitcom family father would miss His son. Also, He wants to hear from us, so we should "call Him up," as it were, through prayer. Many Peruvian Mormons report that this notion of a literal father-god is what attracted them to Mormonism from Catholicism. They report that they always felt like the Catholic god was distant, cold, and uncaring and that the Mormon god is a loving, if estranged, father who wants to be part of their lives.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: Elohim is the high god, but it is permissible to worship his son Jesus. It is not permissible to worship any other supernatural being.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: a liquid running through his veins that is not blood

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: In the experience of the contributor, dreams are one of the main ways God communicates with Peruvian Mormons and Bolivian Mormons. Anglo Mormons, on the other hand, often report that Heavenly Father communicates to them through the tertiary god known as the Holy Ghost, which gives them extreme emotions they call "feeling The Spirit." These emotions let them know with 100% accuracy what is "true." The Holy Ghost can communicate so powerfully to people's emotions because, unlike Elohim and Jesus, He doesn't have a body (but He does have a gender.) Since He is only a spirit, His spirit can communicate

directly with the spirit each person has inside without having to be mediated by the fallible body and its censoring sensory organs. Unsurprisingly, since Mormonism was founded by Anglos, official Mormon doctrine states that the way God happens to communicate with Anglos (through feelings of the Holy Ghost) is the only way He communicates that can be fully trusted. According to Mormon scripture, if you ask God a question, such as "is the Mormon church true," God will give you an answer through the Holy Ghost causing your "heart to burn." This "burning of the bosom" is supposed to be the highest way of knowing something is true, even higher than seeing something with your own eyes.

<https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/scriptures/bofm/moro/10?lang=eng>

Eyes can deceive, but these extreme emotions from the Holy Ghost cannot.

When one compares this to how people in the Andes come to know that Mormonism is the only "true" church, one finds yet another instantiation of white supremacy: Anglo ways of knowing become higher and more trustworthy than other ways of knowing. As mentioned, God communicates with Andean Mormons through far more concrete means than simply feelings of the Holy Ghost. Andean Mormons often report to the contributor that God communicates with them through dreams, visions, extreme coincidences, or physical supernatural visitations. This is especially the case when they tell the story of why they joined Mormonism in the first place. For example, one Bolivian man, upon first meeting Anglo Mormon missionaries, told them that he had a dream the night before that God was reprimanding him from the front steps of a large, white building saying, "you are not married." The man replied to God saying, "but I am married; this is my wife here." God said, "yes, technically you are married, but in my eyes you are not married." When the man asked the Anglo missionaries what that dream could possibly mean, they had an immediate answer because, according to Mormonism, the only form of marriage valid in God's eyes is that which is carried out inside the holy temple. When they showed him an image of a holy temple (in recounting this experience, he couldn't remember which specific city's temple it was, but it was very white on the outside, so it was not the Salt Lake City temple which is grey) he said, "that is the same building I saw in my dream." Such dreams and coincidence are commonplace in Mormonisms other than Anglo Mormonism. On one occasion, the contributor was at a Mormon church-owned campground in Utah with a Peruvian Mormon family led by Arcadio Costa and Jacoba Ariategui, a married couple who had immigrated from Lima to New Jersey in the 80's. Around the campfire, Arcadio began to tell the story of how he came to join the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints. The following are the raw field notes the contributor took of Arcadio's story on July 3, 2015. Bracketed items were added subsequently. Unlike the other excerpts of raw qualitative data in this entry, the following is not a transcription of a digital audio file. It is the contributor's attempt to reproduce Arcadio's words from memory a few hours after he spoke them (originally in Spanish). ARCADIO: Anyway, I eventually fixed my immigration papers and sent for my family. And then my family started getting into the church in New Jersey and I said, "that is fine," but I went to church and it was testimony meeting and this white woman was up there and I think it was English and she was crying and crying and I had no idea why [she was probably feeling The Spirit, which tends to make Anglos cry. Compared to Anglos, Latin American Mormons rarely cry when expressing the truth claims of the church and often make fun of Anglos, behind their backs, for doing so. That Arcadio eventually cries during this storytelling may stem from his adoption of Anglo cultural norms, having lived in the U.S. for over 40 years at this point] and that kind of turned me off, "what in the world is this about?" And then the next time I went, it happened to be testimony meeting yet again [the first Sunday of every month is "fast and testimony meeting" during the first hour of the 3 hour block of meetings. It is an open mic sharing of religious experiences, opinions, and gratefulness] and again this woman was up there just crying, but then I understood that a loved one had died and it kind of moved me. But 3 hours?! Come on! I hadn't even spent half an hour in a Catholic church, and I worked all the time and you wanted me to spend 3 hours at church on my only

day off? I was installing carpets at that time. And so that is when I started having these dreams. In the first one, I was the one preaching the gospel to these people, and later, after having reflected on my life, they ended up being the same people in Molino Pampa [the place in Peru where he and Jacoba served a couples mission in 2009] because they looked the same and it was the same kind of jungle place. Anyway, in the dream, someone wanted to know if the book I was preaching from was true and I said, "if it is true, when I open it," and my daughter was there, "when I open it, I will open it in half and it will levitate over to my daughter." And so I did, and it levitated in little circle movements like this over to her. So, I woke up and asked Jacoba what that means, and she said it must mean the Book of Mormon is true [Jacoba had recently been given a Book of Mormon through a series of miraculous experiences involving an Anglo Mormon missionary who glowed in the dark. At the time of these dreams, Arcadio and Jacoba were being heavily proselytized and a few of their children were baptized]. Then in another dream, I was in a big field, never ending with nothing at all but grass. In the field there were these two guys holding up their arms like this (as if holding up something invisible), and they said they were Peter and John. And this was before I knew anything about the Bible, and I had no idea who Peter and John were and they supposedly were holding up Jesus' tunic and waiting for him to come up out of the water, and I couldn't see anything, not the tunic and nobody in the water, and I told them so. They looked at each other and said, "it is because you have no faith." (Arcadio's voice cracked and he started to tear up at this point, which surprised me, as there was no sense that this was sentimental to him, maybe it was that The Spirit was testifying to him the truth of what he was saying). And then (he recovered very quickly from crying) Jesus came up out of the water and shook my hand, I could actually feel his hand, and he said, "Hello, I am Jesus Christ." Then there was another dream where God pointed to a building and told me that I could find the truth there and it was a distinctive red brick building, not your typical LDS church building. And another dream wherein he warned me that he would take away that which is most dear if I didn't join the church. So I woke up from that and said, "this is serious, I guess I need to do this," but I still delayed getting baptized. And there was this missionary who was from Utah who came and he was sent to NJ because he talked to his mission president in NY and said, "my mission has no meaning, I haven't baptized anyone," and so the mission president said, "I'll send you to NJ, and if you don't find your meaning there, you can go home." So, he was sent to my family, and do you think he found meaning? With all the dreams I'd been having and my kids already members? You better believe he found meaning! Well he asked me what I do for a living and I said, "I lay carpet," and he said, "No way! My dad has a carpet business in Utah! Why don't you go and work for him?" So he called him right then and asked if he wanted a partner, and so we set things up and when he finished his mission he went back to Utah and was released and then drove back to NJ and we drove together back to Utah and it was in Clearfield where we started working [Arcadio and Jacoba's whole family moved to Utah because of this and Clearfield remains the central node of their migratory network to this day. More family members still arrive to this small area of Utah from Peru every year because of Arcadio's original contact in the carpet business]. But there I found out that his dad was a less active member of the church and, even after all this, I still was not a member of the church. His wife had betrayed him and he smoked and drank. And a lot of people in Clearfield would drink and invite me to drink, saying, "you can lay carpet in the basement and help yourself to the scotch or anything down there," and so there were tons of opportunities to drink [which is against the Mormon health code known as the Word Of Wisdom]. One day I went to the Patriarchal Blessing of my daughter who was already a member and the Mormon patriarch asked me if I was a member, and I said, "no." "Oh," said the patriarch in a surprised voice, "but you come to support your daughter?" "Yes," I said. And he came over to me and put his hand on my shoulder and in tears said, "you will be the first bishop of a Hispanic ward and that ward will never leave the face of the earth and will divide

and become many wards." And I thought, "how is that going to happen? I'm not even a member." And anyway, later that day I was offered a drink at work and I rejected it for some reason, for the first time, and the guy said, "why not? Are you Mormon or something?" And I don't know why, but I said, "yes (tearing up again), and I don't drink." And so, from that day forth until today I haven't had a drink. And I was baptized and after a year I got my priesthood, and then do you know what my first calling was? Branch president of a Spanish-speaking Branch in Ogden, because before then all the Spanish speakers had to go to Salt Lake City. There was the Monte Sion branch and this other one I can't remember. Oh, wait, I forgot to tell you that the building where the Ogden branch congregated was the exact same red brick building from my dream. And it was true, it has since become many different wards, Clearfield, Roy, etc. [many Spanish-speaking congregations in Utah start out as provisional "branches" and have to graduate up to the level of "ward." New English-speaking congregations, on the other hand, usually start out already as "wards." The leader of a branch is the branch president and the leader of a ward is the bishop.]

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: Joseph Smith was probably the last Mormon to practice these openly. However, there are still Mormons, largely Anglo Mormons of sects other than The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints, who practice this, particularly in and around the small city of Santaquin, Utah. It involves the use of diving rods and seer stones to find hidden runes or religious artifacts. The late Mormon author, Ogden Kraut was an expert on divination practices. Here is his Amazon.com author page: https://www.amazon.com/s?i=stripbooks&rh=p_27%3AOgden+Kraut&s=relevancerank&text=Ogden+Kraut&ref=dp_byline_sr_b His son, Kevin Krout, has a YouTube Channel that delves into many aspects of divination and other more mystical/archaeological Mormon practices: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCgzc0qUk6NB4_Ap4q84hNPw

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: The question of who has the authority to receive and interpret communication from God has always been a bone of contention within Mormonism simply because of the tension between its message that communication with God is (once again) open to all and its preference for a hierarchical line of authority to God. "Once again" is mentioned parenthetically because part of Mormonism's message is that there was a time between approximately 500 CE (when the last white Amerindian prophet, Moroni died) and 1820 CE (when Joseph Smith had his first vision) called The Great Apostasy. This was a time when God dramatically reduced his communication with humans and when He completely severed the hierarchical line of authority, the priesthood, that connected the heavens to the earth. Joseph Smith restored the line, and Mormonism has always struggled with the balancing act of having to both propagate and protect it. In contemporary Mormonism, this tension tends to map onto racial and gendered tensions such that Anglo Mormon males are seen as communicating in more literal ways with God than Peruvian Mormon females. This is ironic given that, according to Anglo Mormons, the only valid way God communicates with humans is through abstract feelings of The Spirit, not through tangible visitations and audible voices. Nevertheless, there is a real sense

in both Anglo and Peruvian Mormonism that if God is going to audibly speak to anyone or physically appear to anyone, it is going to be to the prophet or the apostles, all of whom happen to be white (or white "passing") males. Rosa, a member of Perifericos Ward in Arequipa, Peru, told the contributor a story in June 2018 that disrupts this racist and sexist understanding of the line of authority. Rosa is a single mother who owns a soccer jersey sewing business she founded in Arequipa's historic downtown. She is the boss of at least three male employees, one of whom would occasionally interrupt her storytelling to ask accounting questions as the contributor sat with her and her sixteen-year-old daughter, Jeni among industrial sewing machines and bits of fabric. Mormon missionaries had baptized Rosa before Jeni was born, but she felt forced into that baptism (she was the one who was stalked, as mentioned in a previous entry) and never went back to the Mormon church. ROSA: Church wasn't what I needed. And no matter what church I went to—like my brother's church, what was it called? The Church of the Living Water?—it didn't sit right with me. And I did not remember the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints where I had been baptized. It was erased from my mind. But one morning when I was reading the Bible, I don't know why, but I guess I felt much more sensitive, and the light of the sun crossed my patio and entered my room, and it was so strong. There was something strange, Hermano, [Brother Jason] because when I started to read, my eyes looked at the letters with a brilliance around the edges. Each letter shone. I said, "it's probably just the light from the window that is making this happen," but the more I continued reading the scriptures, the stronger I felt like I was actually inside them. Suddenly, Hermano, I started to feel that it wasn't me who was reading, instead it was someone else who was reading to me. When I heard the voice, I got so scared that my whole body went cold. "What? All this thinking about the Bible is driving me insane. This cannot be happening." I looked at the scriptures again, and again I felt the same, very strong voice. But this time it wasn't with all that fear, rather, this time I tried to listen to the voice, and it wasn't my thoughts. I felt the voice of the Lord, and I, in that moment, finally broke into tears, Hermano. It was as if I were feeling He was there, that He was talking to me. Then He asked me if I loved Him. [crying] Those were the same words He spoke to Peter, "in reality, do you love me?" And in that moment I finally asked myself if it was true if I really loved Him. I answered Him with all of my love, "yes!" [long pause, recovering from emotion]. That is how it happened, Hermanito. I told Him, "Lord, I love You, but where should I go?" That is what I asked Him, "where do You want me to go if You want me to go somewhere?" That is how I talked to Him. "If I go with my mom to the Catholic church, I don't feel right. Where do You want me to go? But Lord," I said, "Lord, today I'll make You a proposal, the first person that You send to the door of my house and the first one who knocks on my door, I will ask him what church he goes to. And if he goes to the Catholic church, then so will I, and I will be forever faithful. I will show You how much I love You. And if it is my brother, ni modo [oh well], I'll go to his church. Even though I don't like it, I'll go." And that is the proposal I made, Hermano. And so I waited for someone to knock. So much uncertainty! "Who will be the first one to knock?" My brother was going to come at 4:00 on the dot supposedly, so "ay, please let 4:00 never come!" But nobody knocked. And it was 4:00. Suddenly—a knock! And my brother is extremely punctual. "Wow, it must be my brother. Ay, what have I done!?" But when I open the door, it was the missionaries! Hermano, when I saw them I didn't think, "oh no, anyone but them!" Instead, I felt an INMENSE joy that welled up from I don't understand where. Only then did I remember that Mormon missionaries even existed. I told them, "I am waiting for you." For many Mormons, the resurrected Lord, Jesus Christ himself follows the church's official, hierarchical pattern, which means He is not supposed to speak audibly to anyone but to the fifteen elite men He has called as His "modern prophets" and apostles. The fact that He would break the pattern to include Rosa, a member of one of the most excluded identities in contemporary constructions of Mormon Zion—a mestiza single mother—can be quite threatening to church authority. According to Jennifer Basquiat (2004), the Anglo

missionaries in Haiti perceive the way God communicates with Haitian Mormons as a similar sort of threat. Haitians often report having religious conversion experiences even more spectacular than those of Joseph Smith himself. Rather than being delighted that their "investigators" are becoming converted so deeply and unmistakably to Mormonism, Anglo Mormon missionaries downplay these experiences because the experiences threaten white supremacy. Deep down, Anglo Mormons feel that if anyone deserves to have such spectacular religious visitations, it is white people, not Haitians. Work Cited Basquiat, Jennifer Huss. 2004. "Embodied Mormonism: Performance, Vodou and the LDS Faith in Haiti." *Dialogue - A Journal of Mormon Thought* 37 (4): 1-34.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Through as many forms as there are Peruvian Mormons.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Not usually, but they can definitely be seen and recognized as the individuals they were when they were alive. Spirits existing in the place from official Mormon doctrine called "the spirit world" are thought to hold the shape of their earthly body "at its prime." The contributor's own mother, an Anglo Mormon from birth, has seen many spirits of her dead ancestors. As mentioned in a previous entry, Andean Mormons (unlike Anglo Mormons) often consider human bodies as having more than one spirit inside them, including one that can move around unbeknownst to the other ones in the body. This often happens when the human is near death or has been badly scared. For example, an Anglo Mormon missionary known to the contributor was in an accident wherein his vehicle rolled down a hill in Bolivia (a common occurrence on the narrow, serpentine road that connects La Paz in the high Andes to the jungle cities below such as San Borja). He stepped out of the vehicle virtually unscathed, but badly shaken. He lived with Bolivian Mormons at the time, and when he arrived home well past the missionary curfew, the homeowner, a Bolivian Mormon, was not worried. The Anglo missionary asked why he was not worried and the Bolivian Mormon said, "because your spirit* came to say goodbye to us as if you were going to die, but then it said, 'actually, I'll go back to my body now,' so we knew you were okay." The Anglo Mormon did not know that his spirit had done any such thing and did not report having a "near death experience" or ever being unconscious during the accident. *The word for "spirit" used in this case was "ajayu." The ajayu is an important part of understanding Andean health and sickness. There is a common ailment in the Andes, and Latin America in general, called "susto." Susto is caused when a person's ajayu leaves the body because of a scare and then gets stuck somehow, often by possessing a stone or other previously inanimate object. As one of Alejandra Vega's (2008) collaborators told her (page 3 of the below-cited article): "...Por muchas cosas el alma puede asustarse. Los niños, por ejemplo, pueden asustarse de un ruido fuerte, cosas que escuchan, cosas que ven, del oscuro...fácil se asustan los niños y ya se sale el alma del cuerpo y se enferma. Lloro mucho, le da diarrea, no duerme...y ya hay que llamar al alma, que vuelva, así se curan. Allá en Bolivia yo sé de gente que tuvo el alma atrapada, hay veces los saxra (3) agarran, quieren comer al ajayu. La persona puede morir si el alma no vuelve, jodido es..." (Gervasia, oriunda de La Paz) 3. Los saxra son espíritus malignos dependientes del Supaya, hoy identificado con el diablo Vega,

Alejandra. 2008. "La pérdida del alma y la etiología de un taxón tradicional: el Susto entre los migrantes Aymara de Buenos Aires." In . Universidad Nacional de La Plata. Facultad de Humanidades y Ciencias de la Educación. Departamento de Sociología. <https://www.academica.org/000-096/449>. For the rest of these "spirit" entries, "spirit" will be used to designate the official, Anglo Mormon version of spirit which is the non-tangible half of an individualized self that begins to exist on a different dimension of this earth called the spirit world after the death of the other half of itself, the body. If an Andean Mormon conceptualization of *ajayu* or other sort of "spirit" is used again in these entries, that difference will be stipulated.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: Not usually, though there have been instances where a spirit has tapped a Mormon on the shoulder.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: They do not have an omniscient view of this world. Their knowledge is largely restricted to what they remember during their own earth life, though they are permitted occasionally to see and even move "beyond the veil" that separates the earth's physical dimension from its "spirit world."

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: Since Peruvian Mormons in Utah have told the contributor that their ancestors have visited them in Utah, far from the place where they died, one would imagine that the spatial rules of the spirit world, though it lies in this world, are different such that spirits are not restricted to specific areas in the spirit world and, if they are, these areas do not map onto the Earth's regions.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– No

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: Potentially yes, but not all the time. They are not omniscient. It seems they

have to get special dispensation to be able to see humans, but there are probably no restrictions on where the human can be seen once said dispensation is procured.

↳ Human spirits can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: Spirits often know, for example, when Mormons are trying to find out about them through family history. Spirits find ways to help Mormons out with the genealogical process often by intuiting what they are thinking and even communicating with them through a sort of telepathy.

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– No

Notes: Not necessarily. It depends on your relationship to them. Also, human spirits, when they are inside living human bodies, know little more than their body's brain knows, or, rather, they do not have a way of communicating all they do know to that brain because God has deliberately placed a veil between the spirit memory and the body memory such that the living human self cannot remember (at least not much) about the preexistence.

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

Notes: Not necessarily or automatically by virtue of their being spirits. The spirits of dead humans are very much the same in personality, power, talents and inclinations as the living humans they used to be. If a human was a "seer" of the future while alive, he or she (gender continues to be binary even after death) will probably be able to do so after death in the spirit world. Mormons commonly note, for example, that if a human is addicted to smoking during life, that human's spirit will still be addicted after death but will have no recourse other than to go through lengthy (though not eternal) withdrawal symptoms because only spirits with physical bodies can smoke. The same logic goes for other bodily actions that Mormons traditionally consider "addictions," such as masturbation.

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– Yes [specify]: they are able to remember the pre-earth time

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– No

Notes: It is not so much that they can reward as that they can help Mormons do important tasks, such as fill out their FamilySearch.org family tree.

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– No

- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits possess hunger:
 - Yes
 - Notes: But they cannot eat.
- ↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: the possess all of the memories and tendencies that they acquired while they had a body
- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - Notes: In waking life? Yes. Everyday? Probably not.
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - No
 - Notes: The only spirits known to posses are not the spirits of formerly living humans, they are the spirits of never-to-be humans (demons.)
 - ↳ Through divination processes:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through specialists:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: writing, such as leaving notes on the back of ancestral photographs that were not there before

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: The non-human supernatural beings that exist in official Mormonism and that have been seen by living Mormons include, but are not limited to, spirits of humans who have died, spirits of humans who have not been born yet, angels (this is an ontologically ambivalent category that is in some cases equivalent to a spirit and in other cases equivalent to a resurrected being), resurrected beings (beings who have died and have already been resurrected into an immortal body with a certain degree of "glory"), beings of unusual longevity (those mortal humans promised to remain on the earth until Jesus' Second Coming) and demons (the spirit children of Heavenly Father and Heavenly Mother that fought on Lucifer's side and, therefore, will never get bodies). The supernatural beings that can be seen in Peruvian Mormonism include the other kinds of dividual spirits, such as *ajayu*, that inhabit a person's body. The *kharisiri*, or "vampire of the Andes" is another supernatural being that some Peruvian Mormons have reported seeing or knowing about. These are white specters who attack humans all over the Andean world, suck out the body fat so important to their connection between the upper and inner worlds, and sell it to the capitalists to lubricate their machines. Or, as one recently baptized Mormon convert in Arequipa told the contributor, a more technologically advanced *kharisiri* might be sitting next to you on a bus, stab you in the side with a syringe, suck out your body fat—rich in collagen and lipids—and sell it to cosmetic companies. In the Andes, the *kharisiri* are not from either the inner or the upper worlds and so cannot be reasoned with. As such, there is usually no cure for this separation from one's body fat, which almost invariably results in death. Here is a YouTube video about the *kharisiri* in a non-Mormon context. It was originally in Spanish and the contributor has dubbed it in English: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Xwc19yD11nO>

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: Only the resurrected beings of Heavenly Father, Jesus and the spirit called The Holy Ghost are thought of as omniscient. Heavenly Mother is so rarely spoken of that Mormons don't know if she is omniscient or not, but they logically assume she would be. All other supernatural beings are restricted in some way, though Satan himself (Lucifer) has very few restrictions.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Some of them do.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Some of them do.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: The omniscient ones can, the others cannot always.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: The omniscient ones can, the others cannot always.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: The omniscient ones can, the others cannot always.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: The omniscient ones do, the others do not always.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: The omniscient ones can, the others cannot always.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: there are too many different supernatural beings, including gods, to provide a concise answer

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: Since, in Mormonism, non-human supernatural beings include resurrected beings like Heavenly Father and Jesus Christ, and since, as previously mentioned, these gods can reward, supernatural beings can reward.

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Since, in Mormonism, non-human supernatural beings include resurrected beings like Heavenly Father and Jesus Christ, and since, as previously mentioned, these gods can reward, supernatural beings can reward.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Some do, some don't.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: they exhibit, along with humans, an infinite individuality or "intelligence" that is "co-eternal" with God, meaning it was never created.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: All humans are mixed human-divine beings as is the god, Jesus Christ. As these two sorts of beings are, in other ways, at the opposite poles of a human-god binary, the rest of these questions are going to be answered as they apply to either humans or God, meaning most answers are going to be "yes."

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: The most common mixed human-divine beings are us, and we can see ourselves. We are dual beings of divine spirit and biological flesh. Jesus was an even more complexly human-divine hybrid because not only did his spirit come from the sexual union of a god and a goddess as ours did but his biological body was created from the union of a celestial sperm and a mortal egg.

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:
 - Yes

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes

Notes: Jesus is one of the omniscient beings in Mormonism, and he is a human-divine hybrid.

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have other knowledge of the human world:

– Yes [specify]: Jesus is a human-divine being and He helped create the world, so He knows a lot about it. Plus, He is all seeing and all knowing.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: everything that humans exhibit because all humans are human-divine beings.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Notes: Jesus does not need to resort to divination practices to communicate with humans. He communicates with them, according to Anglo Mormonism, through an intermediary called the Holy Ghost. He communicates with them, according to Peruvian Mormonism, through dreams, miracles, coincidences, and physical or auditory manifestations of Himself. Humans, as human-divine beings, do not need to resort to divination practices to communicate with each other. Most Peruvian Mormons use Whatsapp for that purpose.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: all kinds of human communication technology is used

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: In official Mormonism, once a spirit has inhabited a body it is forever biologized into the lineage of that body under a Eurocentric kin idiom. Therefore, after a person dies, their spirit, as an individual with a name and dates, will forever fall into a specific, numbered slot on the modern Western arboreal model of vertical blood-descent. That spirit will become an "ancestor" on the "lineage" of a specific living "descendant" who, forever after, will be able to capture this relationship visually on the church's genealogical website, <https://www.familysearch.org/en/>. In Peruvian Mormonism, this Western kinship model is considered vital, however there is a sense that the substance that connects families together is not so much shared "blood" as it is shared food and drink. In Anglo Mormonism, proper kinship is only established at the moment two partners meet in temple marriage or at the moment two gametes meet in conception. In Peruvian Mormonism, these two sorts of meetings are important, but added to them is a third and just as legitimate form of kin establishment: living, eating, and dancing together in place and over time. This means the model of vertical blood descent, fixated as it is on whose sexual relationship produced which offspring, clashes quite dramatically with Peruvian Mormon notions of kinship and can cause many to feel their ancestry is diminished compared to the ancestry of Anglo Mormons with "pioneer stock." This feeling is then substantiated when a Peruvian Mormon actually sees an Anglo Mormon's immensely complete "family tree," especially if that Anglo Mormon's own ancestors were Anglo Mormons who had their own family trees. For example, see the photograph below of the contributor's daughters' family tree. The contributor is an Anglo Mormon and his spouse is a Peruvian Mormon. Therefore, their daughters should theoretically have an Anglo half and a Peruvian half of their tree. In practice however, their Anglo nine tenths is much more brachiated and foliated than their Peruvian one tenth.

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It may seem like a hierarchy, but it is too complex to be a strict hierarchy when one considers human spirits, gods, and demons to all be "supernatural beings." It is more like the nexus of a continuum and two binaries. The continuum represents time because as time passes, certain beings become more powerful. Human spirits can become gods, and gods can achieve "eternal progression." Heavenly Father is more powerful today than he was yesterday. One of the binaries is "body versus no body." Supernatural beings with bodies are much more powerful than ones without bodies, but there are two notable exceptions to this. One is Satan. He doesn't have a body, yet seems to be more powerful in some ways (such as in cunning) than Heavenly Father himself, a god with the highest form of supernatural body, one that eternally progresses. The other exception is the Holy Ghost who also doesn't have a body but is considered part of the "God Head" or the pantheon of three gods at the "top" of whatever model this web of quasi-hierarchies would turn out to be. The other binary is good versus evil, which is also complicated by the Holy Ghost and Satan. The Holy Ghost is good and Satan is evil, so they seem to be on opposite sides of that binary, and, since neither has a body, they are on a relatively level playing field. Still, on a power hierarchy, who would come out on top, Satan or the Holy Ghost? It is hard to say who is more powerful, but it would seem that Satan holds more power than any of the individual gods in the godhead simply because he is the sole inhabitant of the opposite of the godhead. His power over the godhead stems from the fact that if he chose to stop being evil, he would throw off the whole balance of the universe. According to the Book of Mormon, there would be no good without evil. Therefore, Satan has the power, in eliminating his own evil, to eliminate good. The Holy Ghost does not have that power because if the Holy Ghost turned evil, Heavenly Father and Jesus would still be there to offset the deficit in goodness and restore balance. It is also hard to say whether Satan and the Holy Ghost, being without bodies, are more powerful than humans with bodies. Heavenly Mother also stands to turn any sort of hierarchy on its head and expose it as a suspiciously human-like patriarchy, which is perhaps why she is rarely mentioned in Mormonism. Is Heavenly Mother the female equivalent to Heavenly Father to the extent that She has the same amount of power as He does? Or, does She in fact surpass Him in power? Furthermore, does Jesus have a female equivalent? What about the Holy Ghost and Satan? And then there is the inevitable question, what about the god of the world Heavenly Father inhabited before He achieved godhood? What about the Satan of that world? The Heavenly Mother of that world? The Jesus of that world? Or, as would seem to be the case if one reads the entire canon of Mormon scripture, did the Jesus from this world die for the sins of everyone on all worlds including the sins that Heavenly Father himself committed back when he was a human? If so, where on any "hierarchy" would this place Jesus?

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: Some of them are, some of them aren't. For example, Satan only has dominion over this world. Elohim has dominion over many worlds.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: chronological, body/no body, evil/good, male/female

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

— Yes

Notes: Kolob is the name of the closest star to the planet currently designated as the Celestial Kingdom, the planet upon which God the Father and his son Jesus Christ dwell.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

— No

Notes: The Mormon afterlife includes a complex, detailed plan that requires a brief explanation of the beforelife. What follows is the contributor’s attempt to explain this plan combining his own upbringing as a male, Anglo Mormon in Utah and his research among Peruvian Mormons. God the Father was once a human on a planet much like this one. He somehow achieved godhood which meant he became a “glorified” being with a spirit made of spirit-matter and a body made of flesh, bone, and some special liquid better than blood that provided immortality. He somehow met a similarly glorified goddess whom Mormons call Heavenly Mother. After some sort of process akin to sexual reproduction, Heavenly Mother gave “birth” to children. For some reason that still remains a mystery to Mormons, these children were not born as glorified souls made of spirit and body, rather they were merely spirits made of spirit-matter in the shape of the bodies they would one day inhabit. Heavenly Father and Heavenly Mother’s spirit children existed as individual “intelligences” even before they were born into body-shaped spirits, but little is known about that pre-preexistent state. The first-born spirit son of these heavenly parents was Jesus and the second born was Lucifer. The Father, with the help of Jesus and the spirit of the man who would later become Adam, created a physical Earth so that His spirit children could go there and inhabit physical bodies. The spirits of Jesus and Adam were able to manipulate physical matter because they had the power of the priesthood, the same priesthood that is given to all “worthy” Mormon males today, but that was only given to males of “non-African descent” prior to 1978. The bodies that God’s spirit children would inhabit on Earth would not be glorified like the one He had, rather they would be fallen and mortal. In order to provide a way for these bodies to one day become glorified like his own, the Father needed someone to go down to Earth and save it from its fallen state. He asked which of his two first-born sons wanted to become the Savior of the world. They both did, but the Father chose Jesus. This made Lucifer angry and so a war was fought. 1/3 of the spirit children joined Lucifer and 2/3 joined Jesus. Lucifer and his faction lost the war and their punishment for starting it was that they would never get to be physically born onto the earth with bodies. They will remain as mere spirits forever. This makes them angry and jealous and motivates them to torment God’s spirit children who are inhabiting bodies on the earth today. According to contemporary church doctrine, all humans born on the earth today were valiant fighters on Jesus’ side during that primordial war. However, according to past church doctrines filtered through local cultural understandings in Peru, spirits who are born into already-Mormon homes were more valiant in the war than others. Furthermore, according to a doctrine that many Peruvian Mormons do not know that their church has officially retracted, spirits born into Black bodies were neutral during the war, meaning that their punishment for not fighting against Lucifer was to be born Black. Even further, furthermore, according to the Anglo Mormon apostle Mark E. Peterson, arguably the largest influence on Mormon thought during a full half of the 20th century, spirits born as Anglo Mormons in the U.S. were the most valiant in the war, and those born into other nations, races and religions fought at various lower levels of valiance, from the level of “Chinamen” who fought poorly, down to the lowest level of “the Negro” who didn’t fight at all. In a 1954 address in support of racial segregation at The Convention of Teachers of Religion On The College Level he hypothesized that the Chinese were Chinese before the continent now known as Asia had separated from Pangea. He posited that God created China as a place in which to segregate His Chinese spirit children. What else could explain why China tended to experience such a high level of Chinese births? He asked church educators to imagine a Chinese, born in China with a dark skin, and with all of the handicaps of that race, which seems to have little opportunity ... [Now] think of the mercy

of God to Chinese people who are willing to accept the Gospel. In spite of whatever [bad things] they might have done in the pre-existence to justify being born over there as Chinamen, if they now, in this life, accept the gospel and live it the rest of their lives, they can have the Priesthood, go to the temple and receive endowments and sealings, and that means they can have exaltation. Isn't the mercy of God marvelous? (Peterson 1954, 15) When a human dies, its spirit separates from its body and stays on this earth but exists in this earth's spirit-matter dimension known either as spirit prison or spirit paradise depending on the status of the human's official church membership at death. In this sense, the defined space of the afterlife is neither above, nor below; it is right here on this earth, only in a different dimension called the "Spirit World." The state of the spirit as being in prison or paradise depends on whether or not the spirit received certain Mormon rites while it was paired with a body during life. If it was not baptized and confirmed a member of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints during life, it is in a state of "prison" and if it was baptized it might be in a state of "paradise" or "prison" depending on other factors. Spirits in prison cannot, of themselves, move to paradise because the physical earth compound of H₂O required for baptism cannot exist in the spirit dimension, nor can terrestrial liquids of any kind. However, if a temple worthy, living Mormon enters a temple's baptismal font on this physical earth with the name and birthdate of a spirit in prison and is baptized on its behalf, that spirit can become a member of the church and move to paradise. This practice is called "baptism for the dead." Many Peruvian Mormons, as they look around the temple baptistry during a baptism for the dead, often for one of their own ancestors, report seeing apparitions of the very spirits benefiting from the rite. Once all the spirit children awaiting their turn to be born into bodies on this earth have had the chance, Jesus Christ will end the cycle by coming to earth a second time, this time as an immortal, resurrected being of body and spirit. 1000 years after He comes to the Earth again, all the spirits in the spirit world, whether they be in paradise or prison, will be reunited with their bodies at varying degrees of "glory." At that point in time, the physical earth will be burned in a great cleansing fire and changed into the Celestial Kingdom, the highest of Mormon heavens. What will happen to the current Celestial Kingdom next to the star, Kolob, remains to be seen. Spirits resurrected to the most glorified body type, the same one that Heavenly Father has, get to remain on earth, now the Celestial Kingdom (compared to the brightness of the sun). Those resurrected with less glorified body types must go inhabit other less glorified planets such as the Terrestrial Kingdom (compared to the brightness of the moon) or the Telestial Kingdom (compared to the brightness of the stars). There are a few really bad people who will get thrown into "outer darkness" after resurrection rather than inheriting a planet that matches their body type, but pretty much everyone will get to inhabit a planet that is quite a bit better than our contemporary earth. Among those who get to inhabit the Celestial Kingdom there are further gradations of glory. The highest of the high glories can only be achieved by conjugal unions consisting of a husband and his wife or wives wed in a physical earthly temple. Again, as with baptism, these temple marriages can be carried out on behalf of the dead. Each of these conjugal couples will become Heavenly Father and Heavenly Mother to their own nuclear family of spirit children on their own planet and the cycle will begin again. It is important to note that Mormons do not overtly teach most of this "plan of salvation," as they call it, and would perhaps not even recognize it laid out in these terms. This simply represents the contributor's attempt to piece together aspects of the plan into a digestible format. Works cited Peterson, Mark E. 1954. "Race Problems As They Affect the Church." In Paper Presented at the Convention of Teachers of Religion on the College Level, Brigham Young University, Provo, Aug 27.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

- ↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:
 - Yes [specify]: other planet

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

Notes: This distinction is the culture versus doctrine distinction which is unclear to most Peruvian Mormons, but crystal clear to most Anglo Mormons. As mentioned in a previous entry, Anglo Mormons use the fact that this distinction is unclear to Peruvian Mormons as evidence that Peruvian Mormons are not fit for self-government.

- ↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

Notes: Especially those involving gender, which is not considered a metaphysical concept, but a biological one.

- ↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

- ↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Notes: There is a sense that sin accumulates and stains as if it were an impersonal cosmic substance.

- ↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

- ↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

- ↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

- ↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals (any time period)

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The punishment of greatest emphasis in the afterlife is phrased to outsiders as if it were a reward. Mormon missionaries tell potential converts that they can be rewarded with the opportunity to be with their loved ones after death if they will do what is necessary to become worthy to enter the temple and be ritually "sealed" to them. People who grew up Mormon in the highly Mormon society of Utah often go out into the broader world thinking that Mormons are the only ones who know about the possibility of being together with family members after death. In reality, most Christians believe that being with loved ones after death is simply the default state, not a reward or anything that has to be earned. This means the Mormon idea of "forever family" is actually a punishment when phrased negatively: "If you do not get 'sealed' with your loved ones, your punishment is that you will not be with them in the afterlife." As the current president of the church declared in 2019 in what many U.S. Mormon feminists have dubbed the "Sad Heaven" speech, Love songs perpetuate a false hope that love is all you need if you want to be together forever. And some erroneously believe that the Resurrection of Jesus Christ provides a promise that all people will be with their loved ones after death. In truth, the Savior Himself has made it abundantly clear that while His Resurrection assures that every person who ever lived will indeed be resurrected and live forever, much more is required if we want to have the high privilege of exaltation. Salvation is an individual matter, but exaltation is a family matter. (Nelson 2019, 89) Then, speaking to all those who know that they must make covenants in the temple in order to seal the Anglo-defined family, but who, for whatever reason, have not yet made those covenants, Nelson continued, they have chosen not to make covenants with God. They have not received the ordinances [one-time rites] that will exalt them with their families and bind them together forever ... They need to understand that while there is a place for them hereafter—with wonderful men and women who also chose not to make covenants with God—that is not the place where families will be reunited and be given the privilege to live and progress forever. That is not the kingdom where they will experience the fulness of joy—of never-ending progression and happiness. Those consummate blessings can come only by living in an exalted celestial realm with God, our Eternal Father; His Son, Jesus Christ; and our wonderful, worthy, and qualified family members ... as you choose not to make covenants with God, you are settling for a most meager roof over your head throughout all eternity ... If you truly love your family and if you desire to be exalted with them throughout eternity, pay the price now. (Nelson 2019, 90) Nelson, Russell M. 2019. "Come Follow Me." *The Ensign of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints*, May 2019.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:
– Yes

Notes: This is not considered punishment necessarily, it is considered more to be the natural consequence of actions. All humans will be resurrected to a certain degree of glory in a human form. All these degrees of glory will seem like "rewards" compared to the way humans are living now. However, there will be degrees of glory that will be inferior to others with no chance of leveling up. This could eventually, after one had an eternity to think about it, be considered a punishment.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]
– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– No

Notes: When bad things happen to Mormons in this life, they are often considered the natural consequences of actions rather than deliberate, divine punishments. Sometimes they are also considered part of a God-given trial meant to make the recipient stronger. Mormons often say that God chastises most the people he loves most. At the same time, when bad things happen to non-Mormons in this life, Mormons often see these things as divine punishments, especially when they happen to groups of people who have heard about Mormonism but have largely rejected it, such as African Americans.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
– Yes

Notes: Mormonism, as a U.S. religion, always considers the U.S. to be on the side of righteousness in any war. In this view, losing a war against the U.S. can be seen as a punishment for wickedness.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

Notes: Especially if those journeys happen on Sunday when one should not be traveling. However, Mormons focus far more on the blessings that come from keeping the commandments than they do on the punishments that come from breaking them.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Assuming mild sensory displeasure is the natural consequence of breaking a commandment, such as becoming addicted to an illicit drug, then punishment could include this.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: Mormon scriptures are replete with such punishments.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: A punishment in this life could consist of not having one's Patriarchal Blessing promises fulfilled. Those who grew up Mormon often undergo a ritual wherein a priesthood-holding man puts his hands upon their head and pronounces upon them a blessing acting as the mouthpiece for Jesus Christ. This blessing is then typed up (lately it is digitized). One copy is given to the recipient and the other is curated at church headquarters in Salt Lake City, Utah. In these blessings, Jesus promises certain things that are contingent upon the recipients' faithfulness. Often Mormons are promised that they will live to see the Second Coming, that they will be able to serve a mission in a foreign language, or that they will have many children. If and when these promises are not fulfilled, it can be interpreted as a punishment for not following through with some aspect of "faithfulness." This can be especially psychologically damaging in the case of childlessness.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: Inasmuch as Mormons believe they will be resurrected and go to the Celestial Kingdom and that this world will become the Celestial Kingdom, they believe in reincarnation on this world.

↳ In animal/plant form:

– No

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– No

Notes: All humans will be reincarnated into the same basic body in which they lived their life. The difference will be that the body will be on one of many stages of glory or perfection depending on how righteously the human lived.

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: Sometimes they are done by what is considered the natural consequence of the action.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:
– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
– Yes

↳ Done randomly:
– No

Notes: Good things randomly happen, but these would not be considered a reward from Heavenly Father. Mormons believe that there are certain specific blessings, known only to God, that are attached to certain acts of righteousness such that if a person keeps a certain commandment "God is bound" to grant the blessing He had previously attached to that commandment. God has no choice but to reward the person, even if they do the action with ulterior motives, such as testing God to see if he really exists. This sort of logic is not extended to punishments in the same way. Bad things are only suspected of being divine punishments. Good things are almost sure to be divine rewards. Tithing is the prime example of this. Almost every Peruvian Mormon has a tithing story akin to this hypothetical story: "I was on my last cent, but I decided to pay tithing instead of buy food for my family. When I got home, I happened to put my hand in my pocket and there was 100 soles that had not been there before." Windfalls are often seen as the blessing that God has attached to the act of paying tithing.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Becoming a god.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Prosperity theology is not deliberate, but very strong in Mormonism. Wealth is seen as a supernatural reward for righteousness and proper living.

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– No

Notes: Good luck exists, but the benefits that come from it would not be considered supernatural rewards.

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Notes: Early Anglo Mormon origin myths of settling Utah are replete with such reward stories.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: Many mission presidents all over the world promise their male, full-time missionaries that the strictness with which they obey the mission rules will equate to the beauty of their future spouse.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Notes: This is actually the canonized reward for obeying the Word of Wisdom.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Notes: The Bible is replete with such promises, and Mormons not only believe in the Bible, they ritually connect their lineages to the Biblical ones with the highest propensity for fertility. This is done through a ritual called the Patriarchal Blessing wherein Mormons are told their fortune, which usually includes some mention of reproductive success, and ascribed to a specific tribe of Israel.

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Reward in this life consists of "love at home" in a nuclear family consisting only of a conjugal couple and their minor children living in a suburban, single-family home.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: There is a general, cultural feeling within Mormonism that since spirits are to recover their bodies during the resurrection, that it will be easier or perhaps faster to combine all the particles of the body if it is kept as whole as possible. As in other areas of Mormon life, it is important to be first and to be fast. There are those who will come forth in the morning of the "first resurrection" and those who will come forth in the evening of the second. Those who are first are more righteous. Perhaps cremated bodies will take so long to resurrect that they will come forth around brunch of the first resurrection along with less righteous people.

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

Notes: The exact mode of internment is not stipulated by the central Anglo-controlled church and locally traditional practices are allowed. There are in fact no mandates at all as to how the corpse is to be handled, however, members are encouraged to dress the corpse in ritual temple robes, including the sacred undergarments, if the person was an "endowed" temple-going Mormon during life. The endowment is a temple rite. Prior to it, Mormons are initiated in the use of the sacred, white undergarments. Before one is "sealed" in an eternal relationship to a spouse in a temple, one must be "endowed."

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Notes: Again, there are no actual stipulations about this, but this is the way it tends to happen in both Utah-Mormonism and Peruvian Mormonism.

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: This is often simply a logistical necessity in Peru. Since a permanent burial in an above-ground mausoleum is expensive but ideal, many Peruvian Mormons bury their dead in the same way their Catholic counterparts do, by placing the body in a mausoleum for a time and then, after failing to make the payments on the mausoleum, being forced to extract the remains and deposit them in the ground at a cheap cemetery. Often, if payment is never made or the family members can no longer be contacted, the mausoleum owner simply dumps the remains in a pile in the back of the cemetery.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned, the corpse is often clothed in temple robes. Other treatments, such as embalming, are also commonly performed among Mormons in Peru and Utah but are not thought of as religious per se.

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Yes [specify]: embalming

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: There is no prohibition against this nor is there any particular cultural penchant for it. Many Peruvian Mormons are buried with their wedding ring and temple robes.

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– No

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Notes: a wedding ring, for example.

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: any item depending on personal preference

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: Any grave goods are fair game depending on personal preference. Church doctrine does not deal much with the treatment of the dead.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: If Jesus comes again during this lifetime, then yes.

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– Yes

Notes: There is a much speculation about this in Mormonism. Some believe that Mormons must usher in the millennium by sending missionaries to every single country. Others think it will be accomplished by getting a certain percentage of the proxy "temple work" finished for the world's global dead.

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Yes

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– Yes

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: Mormons are often saying things like, "I think we will be surprised at how many Mormons don't survive the calamities of the end times."

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: There was a mini-eschaton on the American continent when Jesus died according to the Book of Mormon. Many people were killed, but the "more righteous among them" were not. Some Mormons take heart in this because it does not say "the most righteous among them." It is important to understand that Mormons believe the final eschaton will happen after Jesus Christ has reigned personally on the earth for 1000 years (the millennium), meaning that those who will be destroyed are only going to be those who openly rebel against His supernatural reign.

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Other survival condition:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: If the field knew, we'd tell you about it so you could prepare!

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

Notes: This above all.

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - Yes
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - Yes
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - Yes [specify]: self-reliance

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The body and the spirit form one entity called the soul. A individual spirit's purpose in coming to earth is to receive a body so that the individual can become a complete soul. In Mormonism, the powers that the body has are often considered more important than the powers that the spirit has. For example, a spirit cannot procreate. Procreation, inasmuch as it is part of the nuclear family, is one of Mormonism's most vital concepts.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– No

Notes: This is an extremely important distinction for Mormonism. Spirit is conceived of as ontologically distinct from body, BUT it is not conceived of as non-material. Spirit is made of a much more refined matter than body, but it is made of matter nonetheless.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: In Anglo Mormonism, an individual soul is the combination of one spirit and one body.

Notes: However, in Andean Mormonism, there is the possibility that a soul could be made of two or more spirits in a single body. Put differently, the Anglo Mormon person is made up of dividual parts and individual parts; material parts and spiritual parts, but these parts all combine into one whole soul. Peruvians in Arequipa are made up of many parts as well, but souls are just some of these parts, not the whole person. A living Mormon body is a soul. A living arequipeño body contains many souls. Some of these souls stick around after the body has decomposed, some go to Christian heavens, but others merge back into collective ancestral inner worlds that produce the material of new humans. Though she is Mormon and has lived in upper-class Salsands, Utah for decades, Jacoba (a Peruvian) still retains parts of this cyclical ancestral idiom that complicates the individuated family. When she talks of her ancestors, she tears the Western arboreal analogy of genealogy apart at the middle. She once said to the contributor, “I always tell human beings: ‘Look. Plant: Your kids are your branches and your grandkids are your roots, and they remain there, planted.’” As a Mormon, she has seen countless “family tree” depictions where grandchildren fall below children. These trees sprout individual ancestors as branches and individual descendants as roots. Yet, Jacoba places descendants (kids and grandkids) as both the branches and the roots; the future and the past. Hers is a family rhizome, not a tree, because children can give parts of themselves to parents, making parents descendants as much as antecedents. Furthermore, since the cycle of reciprocity in Peru has little to do with genetics or vertical blood descent, anybody who gives and takes of the substance of relatedness and coresidence could become a dividual within Jacoba's genealogy. Individuals incorporate parts to delimit wholes while dividuals give up parts to expand wholes. Dealing with parts of dividual people is a matter-of-fact aspect of living in the Andes, even for Mormons whose doctrine of primordial individuality does not seem capacious enough to allow for these agentive parts of self. Ofelia (a member of a Mormon congregation in Arequipa, Peru) has had experiences with dividual souls. OFELIA: In our enclosed courtyard we saw a man who was over by the fig trees. He was tall with his white shirt and straw hat. When we saw him, I

said, "Shannon, look." And we both saw the man hide among the trees ... "Who is there?" Nobody answered, and nobody ever came out. The next afternoon, Ofelia's grandmother, who lived next door, came to tell her that her uncle, who also lived next door, had died that morning. JASON: You mean that the spirit in the orchard was your uncle, but your uncle was still alive at that moment? OFELIA: In that moment he was still alive, but we saw his spirit walking. That is why there are some Catholic beliefs [laughs] that say that the spirit makes its last rounds to say goodbye to people. Ofelia dismisses as pejoratively "Catholic" the belief that part of a live person can wander unbeknownst to the person's other parts. Though Ofelia may have found the belief connected to it laughable, the fact of clothed spirits walking was such a standard part of her social milieu that it was undeniable. For a non-Mormon example, the PTA of the contributor's daughter's school in Arequipa celebrated a pachamanca (earth meal) requiring the improvisation of a brick earth-oven in which to cook chicken and potatoes. The PTA president, a Quechua-speaking grandmother who always dressed in her town's traditional clothing, sent her unassuming husband to go look for bricks in the back of the schoolyard. He came back saying that he found some bricks, but that a human baby was crying beneath them, and he did not want to disturb it. His wife scolded him, "it's just a baby's alma penando (pining soul). Go get the bricks!" Before eventually complying, he mumbled that perhaps the bricks themselves had taken on soul and that he would not be held responsible if the chicken got baked back into animation. Though only a passing comment, likely a joke, the danger that bricks or stones can become subjects, thus making humans their objects, is real in his altiplano village.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: Kolob is the name of the closest star to the planet currently designated as the Celestial Kingdom, the planet upon which God the Father and his son Jesus Christ dwell.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– No

Notes: The Mormon afterlife includes a complex, detailed plan that requires a brief explanation of the beforelife. What follows is the contributor's attempt to explain this plan combining his own upbringing as a male, Anglo Mormon in Utah and his research among Peruvian Mormons. God the Father was once a human on a planet much like this one. He somehow achieved godhood which meant he became a "glorified" being with a spirit made of spirit-matter and a body made of flesh, bone, and some special liquid better than blood that provided immortality. He somehow met a similarly glorified goddess whom Mormons call Heavenly Mother. After some sort of process akin to sexual reproduction, Heavenly Mother gave "birth" to children. For some reason that still remains a mystery to Mormons, these children were not born as glorified souls made of spirit and body, rather they were merely spirits made of spirit-matter in the shape of the bodies they would one day inhabit. Heavenly Father and Heavenly Mother's spirit children existed as individual "intelligences" even before they were born into body-shaped spirits, but little is known about that pre-preexistent state. The first-born spirit son of these heavenly parents was Jesus and the second born was Lucifer. The Father, with the help of Jesus and the spirit of the man who would later become Adam, created a physical Earth so that His spirit children could go there and inhabit

physical bodies. The spirits of Jesus and Adam were able to manipulate physical matter because they had the power of the priesthood, the same priesthood that is given to all "worthy" Mormon males today, but that was only given to males of "non-African descent" prior to 1978. The bodies that God's spirit children would inhabit on Earth would not be glorified like the one He had, rather they would be fallen and mortal. In order to provide a way for these bodies to one day become glorified like his own, the Father needed someone to go down to Earth and save it from its fallen state. He asked which of his two first-born sons wanted to become the Savior of the world. They both did, but the Father chose Jesus. This made Lucifer angry and so a war was fought. 1/3 of the spirit children joined Lucifer and 2/3 joined Jesus. Lucifer and his faction lost the war and their punishment for starting it was that they would never get to be physically born onto the earth with bodies. They will remain as mere spirits forever. This makes them angry and jealous and motivates them to torment God's spirit children who are inhabiting bodies on the earth today. According to contemporary church doctrine, all humans born on the earth today were valiant fighters on Jesus' side during that primordial war. However, according to past church doctrines filtered through local cultural understandings in Peru, spirits who are born into already-Mormon homes were more valiant in the war than others. Furthermore, according to a doctrine that many Peruvian Mormons do not know that their church has officially retracted, spirits born into Black bodies were neutral during the war, meaning that their punishment for not fighting against Lucifer was to be born Black. Even further, furthermore, according to the Anglo Mormon apostle Mark E. Peterson, arguably the largest influence on Mormon thought during a full half of the 20th century, spirits born as Anglo Mormons in the U.S. were the most valiant in the war, and those born into other nations, races and religions fought at various lower levels of valiance, from the level of "Chinamen" who fought poorly, down to the lowest level of "the Negro" who didn't fight at all. In a 1954 address in support of racial segregation at The Convention of Teachers of Religion On The College Level he hypothesized that the Chinese were Chinese before the continent now known as Asia had separated from Pangea. He posited that God created China as a place in which to segregate His Chinese spirit children. What else could explain why China tended to experience such a high level of Chinese births? He asked church educators to imagine a Chinese, born in China with a dark skin, and with all of the handicaps of that race, which seems to have little opportunity ... [Now] think of the mercy of God to Chinese people who are willing to accept the Gospel. In spite of whatever [bad things] they might have done in the pre-existence to justify being born over there as Chinamen, if they now, in this life, accept the gospel and live it the rest of their lives, they can have the Priesthood, go to the temple and receive endowments and sealings, and that means they can have exaltation. Isn't the mercy of God marvelous? (Peterson 1954, 15) When a human dies, its spirit separates from its body and stays on this earth but exists in this earth's spirit-matter dimension known either as spirit prison or spirit paradise depending on the status of the human's official church membership at death. In this sense, the defined space of the afterlife is neither above, nor below; it is right here on this earth, only in a different dimension called the "Spirit World." The state of the spirit as being in prison or paradise depends on whether or not the spirit received certain Mormon rites while it was paired with a body during life. If it was not baptized and confirmed a member of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints during life, it is in a state of "prison" and if it was baptized it might be in a state of "paradise" or "prison" depending on other factors. Spirits in prison cannot, of themselves, move to paradise because the physical earth compound of H₂O required for baptism cannot exist in the spirit dimension, nor can terrestrial liquids of any kind. However, if a temple worthy, living Mormon enters a temple's baptismal font on this physical earth with the name and birthdate of a spirit in prison and is baptized on its behalf, that spirit can become a member of the church and move to paradise. This practice is called "baptism for the dead." Many Peruvian Mormons, as they look around the temple baptistry during a baptism for the dead, often for one of their own ancestors, report seeing apparitions of the very spirits benefiting from the rite. Once all the spirit children awaiting their turn to be born into bodies on this earth have had the chance, Jesus Christ will end the cycle by coming to earth a second time, this time as an immortal, resurrected being of body and spirit. 1000 years after He comes to the

Earth again, all the spirits in the spirit world, whether they be in paradise or prison, will be reunited with their bodies at varying degrees of "glory." At that point in time, the physical earth will be burned in a great cleansing fire and changed into the Celestial Kingdom, the highest of Mormon heavens. What will happen to the current Celestial Kingdom next to the star, Kolob, remains to be seen. Spirits resurrected to the most glorified body type, the same one that Heavenly Father has, get to remain on earth, now the Celestial Kingdom (compared to the brightness of the sun). Those resurrected with less glorified body types must go inhabit other less glorified planets such as the Terrestrial Kingdom (compared to the brightness of the moon) or the Telestial Kingdom (compared to the brightness of the stars). There are a few really bad people who will get thrown into "outer darkness" after resurrection rather than inheriting a planet that matches their body type, but pretty much everyone will get to inhabit a planet that is quite a bit better than our contemporary earth. Among those who get to inhabit the Celestial Kingdom there are further gradations of glory. The highest of the high glories can only be achieved by conjugal unions consisting of a husband and his wife or wives wed in a physical earthly temple. Again, as with baptism, these temple marriages can be carried out on behalf of the dead. Each of these conjugal couples will become Heavenly Father and Heavenly Mother to their own nuclear family of spirit children on their own planet and the cycle will begin again. It is important to note that Mormons do not overtly teach most of this "plan of salvation," as they call it, and would perhaps not even recognize it laid out in these terms. This simply represents the contributor's attempt to piece together aspects of the plan into a digestible format. Works cited Peterson, Mark E. 1954. "Race Problems As They Affect the Church." In Paper Presented at the Convention of Teachers of Religion on the College Level, Brigham Young University, Provo, Aug 27.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: other planet

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: Inasmuch as Mormons believe they will be resurrected and go to the Celestial Kingdom and that this world will become the Celestial Kingdom, they believe in reincarnation on this world.

↳ In animal/plant form:

– No

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):
– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):
– No

Notes: All humans will be reincarnated into the same basic body in which they lived their life. The difference will be that the body will be on one of many stages of glory or perfection depending on how righteously the human lived.

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:
– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:
– No

Notes: There is a general, cultural feeling within Mormonism that since spirits are to recover their bodies during the resurrection, that it will be easier or perhaps faster to combine all the particles of the body if it is kept as whole as possible. As in other areas of Mormon life, it is important to be first and to be fast. There are those who will come forth in the morning of the "first resurrection" and those who will come forth in the evening of the second. Those who are first are more righteous. Perhaps cremated bodies will take so long to resurrect that they will come forth around brunch of the first resurrection along with less righteous people.

↳ Mummification:
– No

↳ Interment:
– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):
– No

Notes: The exact mode of internment is not stipulated by the central Anglo-controlled church and locally traditional practices are allowed. There are in fact no mandates at all as to how the corpse is to be handled, however, members are encouraged to dress the corpse in ritual temple robes, including the sacred undergarments, if the person was an "endowed" temple-going Mormon during life. The endowment is a temple rite. Prior to it, Mormons are initiated in the use of the sacred, white undergarments. Before one is "sealed" in an eternal relationship to a spouse in a temple, one must be "endowed."

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):
– Yes

Notes: Again, there are no actual stipulations about this, but this is the way it tends to happen in both Utah-Mormonism and Peruvian Mormonism.

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):
– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:
– No

↳ Cannibalism:
– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):
– No

↳ Feeding to animals:
– No

↳ Secondary burial:
– Yes

Notes: This is often simply a logistical necessity in Peru. Since a permanent burial in an above-ground mausoleum is expensive but ideal, many Peruvian Mormons bury their dead in the same way their Catholic counterparts do, by placing the body in a mausoleum for a time and then, after failing to make the payments on the mausoleum, being forced to extract the remains and deposit them in the ground at a cheap cemetery. Often, if payment is never made or the family members can no longer be contacted, the mausoleum owner simply dumps the remains in a pile in the back of the cemetery.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:
– Yes

Notes: As mentioned, the corpse is often clothed in temple robes. Other treatments, such as embalming, are also commonly performed among Mormons in Peru and Utah but are not thought of as religious per se.

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :
– Yes [specify]: embalming

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:
– No

Are grave goods present:
– Yes

↳ Personal effects:
– Yes

Notes: There is no prohibition against this nor is there any particular cultural penchant for it. Many Peruvian Mormons are buried with their wedding ring and temple robes.

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– No

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Notes: a wedding ring, for example.

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: any item depending on personal preference

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: Any grave goods are fair game depending on personal preference. Church doctrine does not deal much with the treatment of the dead.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Not only is He anthropomorphic his is "anglopomorphic" in that he is imagined as a light-skinned, muscular, tall, heteronormative cysgender male who is nearly identical in appearance to his son Jesus Christ. Joseph Smith saw God the Father and his son Jesus Christ standing together above him in the air. Reportedly, as published on the official church website (see attached article), Joseph Smith said that Jesus was light complected and had blue eyes.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– Yes

Notes: He is a kin relation to all humans, including elites.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

–Yes [specify]: their words are his words

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

–Yes [specify]: he has a body of flesh and bone and once inhabited a mortal body

Notes: There is debate as to whether the following oft-repeated statement by an early 20th century prophet of the church is "doctrine": "As man now is, God once was; as God now is, man may be." (see attached article)

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Mormons believe their God is the God of everyone, which is why their president and his two councilors, who speak God's words, produce proclamations "to the world" and not simply to their church's membership. See this video of the contemporary prophet and president of the church giving his newest proclamation to the world:

<https://newsroom.churchofjesuschrist.org/article/restoration-proclamation>

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: how to create other ones like it, which He has done many times before

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: Prosperity theology has become a very strong cultural element of Utah-Mormonism that creates some tension with Peruvian Mormonism. In Peru there is a traditional sense that wealth symbolizes greed and anti-social behavior. In Utah, however, there is a strong sense among Anglo Mormons that wealth is a reward from God that he reserves for the righteous. Many Peruvian Mormon immigrants quickly adopt this cultural value when they arrive in Utah as it is part of the American Dream. Also, they see that the men called to be bishops in the Mormon congregations around them often happen to be the wealthiest members of their congregations. This happens so commonly that they begin to assume that riches are a prerequisite for high leadership positions in Utah-Mormonism. Since leaders are seen as being more righteous or closer to God than their parishioners, and since they are also usually far wealthier than their parishioners, it becomes easy to consider riches as a reward from God for righteousness.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: As a testament to Mormonism's fundamental antiblackness, many Anglo Mormons in Utah interpreted Hurricane Katrina as a punishment from God because it largely affected Black people. When natural disasters affect majority white populations they are seen as "trials" from God meant to impel his chosen people towards higher levels of devotion. As to the COVID-19 pandemic, many Peruvian Mormons (such as those who decided to translate the attached article and publish it in the Peruvian Mormon-founded Mormon news outlet MasFe) think that, rather than a punishment, it represents a sort of "incubation period" they liken unto a butterfly's chrysalis. God has always used persecution to "socially distance" his chosen people so that they can emerge, after the pandemic, stronger and more beautiful than ever. In this way, persecution and triumph over persecution are the marks of a chosen people.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Since Peruvian Mormons believe in the Reina Valera version of the Old Testament, and since the high god of that book can be jealous and angry, their supreme high god exhibits negative emotion. However, it is important to note that Mormons believe the god, Jehovah of the Old Testament is actually not the supreme high god. Jehovah is Jesus, the son of the supreme high god, also known as Heavenly Father or Elohim. Jehovah was what Jesus called himself before he got a body. Though Mormons understand Elohim and Jesus to be extremely similar in temperament, there is a sense in the Book of Mormon, especially in the book of Jacob chapter 5, that Elohim is somewhat less patient and less merciful than Jesus. That chapter presents an allegory likening the House of Israel unto a corrupted vineyard. The master of the vineyard (who seems to represent Elohim) is extremely "pained" that his vineyard has become corrupt, but he just wants to burn it and start over. The servant of the vineyard (who seems to

represent Jesus or Jehovah) continually convinces the master to wait a little longer and keep trying to salvage the good parts of the vineyard rather than scrapping the entire thing. <https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/scriptures/bofm/jacob/5?lang=eng>

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Hunger in the sense that Elohim needs to fill his belly with food? No. Hunger in the sense that Elohim feels lack and needs something to fill that void? Yes. As we are all literally His spirit children from a nuclear family in "the preexistence," He misses us just like any U.S. 1950's sitcom family father would miss His son. Also, He wants to hear from us, so we should "call Him up," as it were, through prayer. Many Peruvian Mormons report that this notion of a literal father-god is what attracted them to Mormonism from Catholicism. They report that they always felt like the Catholic god was distant, cold, and uncaring and that the Mormon god is a loving, if estranged, father who wants to be part of their lives.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: Elohim is the high god, but it is permissible to worship his son Jesus. It is not permissible to worship any other supernatural being.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: a liquid running through his veins that is not blood

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: In the experience of the contributor, dreams are one of the main ways God communicates with Peruvian Mormons and Bolivian Mormons. Anglo Mormons, on the other hand, often report that Heavenly Father communicates to them through the tertiary god known as the Holy Ghost, which gives them extreme emotions they call "feeling The Spirit." These emotions let them know with 100% accuracy what is "true." The Holy Ghost can communicate so powerfully to people's emotions because, unlike Elohim and Jesus, He doesn't have a body (but He does have a gender.) Since He is only a spirit, His spirit can communicate directly with the spirit each person has inside without having to be mediated by the fallible body and its censoring sensory organs.

Unsurprisingly, since Mormonism was founded by Anglos, official Mormon doctrine states that the way God happens to communicate with Anglos (through feelings of the Holy Ghost) is the only way He communicates that can be fully trusted. According to Mormon scripture, if you ask God a question, such as "is the Mormon church true," God will give you an answer through the Holy Ghost causing your "heart to burn." This "burning of the bosom" is supposed to be the highest way of knowing something is true, even higher than seeing something with your own eyes.

<https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/scriptures/bofm/moro/10?lang=eng>
Eyes can deceive, but these extreme emotions from the Holy Ghost cannot. When one compares this to how people in the Andes come to know that Mormonism is the only "true" church, one finds yet another instantiation of white supremacy: Anglo ways of knowing become higher and more trustworthy than other ways of knowing. As mentioned, God communicates with Andean Mormons through far more concrete means than simply feelings of the Holy Ghost. Andean Mormons often report to the contributor that God communicates with them through dreams, visions, extreme coincidences, or physical supernatural visitations. This is especially the case when they tell the story of why they joined Mormonism in the first place. For example, one Bolivian man, upon first meeting Anglo Mormon missionaries, told them that he had a dream the night before that God was reprimanding him from the front steps of a large, white building saying, "you are not married." The man replied to God saying, "but I am married; this is my wife here." God said, "yes, technically you are married, but in my eyes you are not married." When the man asked the Anglo missionaries what that dream could possibly mean, they had an immediate answer because, according to Mormonism, the only form of marriage valid in God's eyes is that which is carried out inside the holy temple. When they showed him an image of a holy temple (in recounting this experience, he couldn't remember which specific city's temple it was, but it was very white on the outside, so it was not the Salt Lake City temple which is grey) he said, "that is the same building I saw in my dream." Such dreams and coincidence are commonplace in Mormonisms other than Anglo Mormonism. On one occasion, the contributor was at a Mormon church-owned campground in Utah with a Peruvian Mormon family led by Arcadio Costa and Jacoba Ariategui, a married couple who had immigrated from Lima to New Jersey in the 80's. Around the campfire, Arcadio began to tell the story of how he came to join the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints. The following are the raw field notes the contributor took of Arcadio's story on July 3, 2015. Bracketed items were added subsequently. Unlike the other excerpts of raw qualitative data in this entry, the following is not a transcription of a digital audio file. It is the contributor's attempt to reproduce Arcadio's words from memory a few hours after he spoke them (originally in Spanish). ARCADIO: Anyway, I eventually fixed my immigration papers and sent for my family. And then my family started getting into the church in New Jersey and I said, "that is fine," but I went to church and it was testimony meeting and this white woman was up there and I think it was English and she was crying and crying and I had no idea why [she was probably feeling The Spirit, which tends to make Anglos cry. Compared to Anglos, Latin American Mormons rarely cry when expressing the truth claims of the church and often make fun of Anglos, behind their backs, for doing so. That Arcadio eventually cries during this storytelling may stem from his adoption of Anglo cultural norms, having lived in the U.S. for over 40 years at this point] and that kind of turned me off, "what in the world is this about?" And then the next time I went, it happened to be testimony meeting yet again [the first Sunday of every month is "fast and testimony meeting" during the first hour of the 3 hour block of meetings. It is an open mic sharing of religious experiences, opinions, and gratefulness] and again this woman was up there just crying, but then I understood that a loved one had died and it kind of moved me. But 3 hours?! Come on! I hadn't even spent half an hour in a Catholic church, and I worked all the time and you wanted me to spend 3 hours at church on my only day off? I was installing carpets at that time. And so that is when I started having these dreams. In the first one, I was the one preaching the gospel to these people, and later, after having reflected on my life, they ended up being the same people in Molino Pampa [the place in Peru where he and Jacoba served a couples mission in 2009] because they looked the same and it was the same kind of jungle place. Anyway, in the dream, someone wanted to know if the book I was preaching from was true and I said, "if it is true, when I open it," and my daughter was there, "when I open it, I will

open it in half and it will levitate over to my daughter." And so I did, and it levitated in little circle movements like this over to her. So, I woke up and asked Jacoba what that means, and she said it must mean the Book of Mormon is true [Jacoba had recently been given a Book of Mormon through a series of miraculous experiences involving an Anglo Mormon missionary who glowed in the dark. At the time of these dreams, Arcadio and Jacoba were being heavily proselytized and a few of their children were baptized]. Then in another dream, I was in a big field, never ending with nothing at all but grass. In the field there were these two guys holding up their arms like this (as if holding up something invisible), and they said they were Peter and John. And this was before I knew anything about the Bible, and I had no idea who Peter and John were and they supposedly were holding up Jesus' tunic and waiting for him to come up out of the water, and I couldn't see anything, not the tunic and nobody in the water, and I told them so. They looked at each other and said, "it is because you have no faith." (Arcadio's voice cracked and he started to tear up at this point, which surprised me, as there was no sense that this was sentimental to him, maybe it was that The Spirit was testifying to him the truth of what he was saying). And then (he recovered very quickly from crying) Jesus came up out of the water and shook my hand, I could actually feel his hand, and he said, "Hello, I am Jesus Christ." Then there was another dream where God pointed to a building and told me that I could find the truth there and it was a distinctive red brick building, not your typical LDS church building. And another dream wherein he warned me that he would take away that which is most dear if I didn't join the church. So I woke up from that and said, "this is serious, I guess I need to do this," but I still delayed getting baptized. And there was this missionary who was from Utah who came and he was sent to NJ because he talked to his mission president in NY and said, "my mission has no meaning, I haven't baptized anyone," and so the mission president said, "I'll send you to NJ, and if you don't find your meaning there, you can go home." So, he was sent to my family, and do you think he found meaning? With all the dreams I'd been having and my kids already members? You better believe he found meaning! Well he asked me what I do for a living and I said, "I lay carpet," and he said, "No way! My dad has a carpet business in Utah! Why don't you go and work for him?" So he called him right then and asked if he wanted a partner, and so we set things up and when he finished his mission he went back to Utah and was released and then drove back to NJ and we drove together back to Utah and it was in Clearfield where we started working [Arcadio and Jacoba's whole family moved to Utah because of this and Clearfield remains the central node of their migratory network to this day. More family members still arrive to this small area of Utah from Peru every year because of Arcadio's original contact in the carpet business]. But there I found out that his dad was a less active member of the church and, even after all this, I still was not a member of the church. His wife had betrayed him and he smoked and drank. And a lot of people in Clearfield would drink and invite me to drink, saying, "you can lay carpet in the basement and help yourself to the scotch or anything down there," and so there were tons of opportunities to drink [which is against the Mormon health code known as the Word Of Wisdom]. One day I went to the Patriarchal Blessing of my daughter who was already a member and the Mormon patriarch asked me if I was a member, and I said, "no." "Oh," said the patriarch in a surprised voice, "but you come to support your daughter?" "Yes," I said. And he came over to me and put his hand on my shoulder and in tears said, "you will be the first bishop of a Hispanic ward and that ward will never leave the face of the earth and will divide and become many wards." And I thought, "how is that going to happen? I'm not even a member." And anyway, later that day I was offered a drink at work and I rejected it for some reason, for the first time, and the guy said, "why not? Are you Mormon or something?" And I don't know why, but I said, "yes (tearing up again), and I don't drink." And so, from that day forth until today I haven't had a drink. And I was baptized and after a year I got my priesthood, and then do you know what my first calling was? Branch president

of a Spanish-speaking Branch in Ogden, because before then all the Spanish speakers had to go to Salt Lake City. There was the Monte Sion branch and this other one I can't remember. Oh, wait, I forgot to tell you that the building where the Ogden branch congregated was the exact same red brick building from my dream. And it was true, it has since become many different wards, Clearfield, Roy, etc. [many Spanish-speaking congregations in Utah start out as provisional "branches" and have to graduate up to the level of "ward." New English-speaking congregations, on the other hand, usually start out already as "wards." The leader of a branch is the branch president and the leader of a ward is the bishop.]

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: Joseph Smith was probably the last Mormon to practice these openly. However, there are still Mormons, largely Anglo Mormons of sects other than The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints, who practice this, particularly in and around the small city of Santaquin, Utah. It involves the use of diving rods and seer stones to find hidden runes or religious artifacts. The late Mormon author, Ogden Kraut was an expert on divination practices. Here is his Amazon.com author page: https://www.amazon.com/s?i=stripbooks&rh=p_27%3AOgden+Kraut&s=relevancerank&text=Ogden+Kraut&ref=dp_byline_sr His son, Kevin Krout, has a YouTube Channel that delves into many aspects of divination and other more mystical/archaeological Mormon practices: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCgzC0qUk6NB4_Ap4q84hNPw

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: The question of who has the authority to receive and interpret communication from God has always been a bone of contention within Mormonism simply because of the tension between its message that communication with God is (once again) open to all and its preference for a hierarchical line of authority to God. "Once again" is mentioned parenthetically because part of Mormonism's message is that there was a time between approximately 500 CE (when the last white Amerindian prophet, Moroni died) and 1820 CE (when Joseph Smith had his first vision) called The Great Apostasy. This was a time when God dramatically reduced his communication with humans and when He completely severed the hierarchical line of authority, the priesthood, that connected the heavens to the earth. Joseph Smith restored the line, and Mormonism has always struggled with the balancing act of having to both propagate and protect it. In contemporary Mormonism, this tension tends to map onto racial and gendered tensions such that Anglo Mormon males are seen as communicating in more literal ways with God than Peruvian Mormon females. This is ironic given that, according to Anglo Mormons, the only valid way God communicates with humans is through abstract feelings of The Spirit, not through tangible visitations and audible voices. Nevertheless, there is a real sense in both Anglo and Peruvian Mormonism that if God is going to audibly speak to anyone or physically appear to anyone, it is going to be to the prophet or the apostles, all of whom happen to be white (or white "passing") males. Rosa, a member of Perifericos Ward in Arequipa, Peru, told the contributor a story in June 2018 that disrupts this racist and sexist understanding of the line of authority. Rosa is a single mother who owns a soccer jersey sewing business

she founded in Arequipa's historic downtown. She is the boss of at least three male employees, one of whom would occasionally interrupt her storytelling to ask accounting questions as the contributor sat with her and her sixteen-year-old daughter, Jeni among industrial sewing machines and bits of fabric. Mormon missionaries had baptized Rosa before Jeni was born, but she felt forced into that baptism (she was the one who was stalked, as mentioned in a previous entry) and never went back to the Mormon church. ROSA: Church wasn't what I needed. And no matter what church I went to—like my brother's church, what was it called? The Church of the Living Water?—it didn't sit right with me. And I did not remember the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints where I had been baptized. It was erased from my mind. But one morning when I was reading the Bible, I don't know why, but I guess I felt much more sensitive, and the light of the sun crossed my patio and entered my room, and it was so strong. There was something strange, Hermano, [Brother Jason] because when I started to read, my eyes looked at the letters with a brilliance around the edges. Each letter shone. I said, "it's probably just the light from the window that is making this happen," but the more I continued reading the scriptures, the stronger I felt like I was actually inside them. Suddenly, Hermano, I started to feel that it wasn't me who was reading, instead it was someone else who was reading to me. When I heard the voice, I got so scared that my whole body went cold. "What? All this thinking about the Bible is driving me insane. This cannot be happening." I looked at the scriptures again, and again I felt the same, very strong voice. But this time it wasn't with all that fear, rather, this time I tried to listen to the voice, and it wasn't my thoughts. I felt the voice of the Lord, and I, in that moment, finally broke into tears, Hermano. It was as if I were feeling He was there, that He was talking to me. Then He asked me if I loved Him. [crying] Those were the same words He spoke to Peter, "in reality, do you love me?" And in that moment I finally asked myself if it was true if I really loved Him. I answered Him with all of my love, "yes!" [long pause, recovering from emotion]. That is how it happened, Hermanito. I told Him, "Lord, I love You, but where should I go?" That is what I asked Him, "where do You want me to go if You want me to go somewhere?" That is how I talked to Him. "If I go with my mom to the Catholic church, I don't feel right. Where do You want me to go? But Lord," I said, "Lord, today I'll make You a proposal, the first person that You send to the door of my house and the first one who knocks on my door, I will ask him what church he goes to. And if he goes to the Catholic church, then so will I, and I will be forever faithful. I will show You how much I love You. And if it is my brother, ni modo [oh well], I'll go to his church. Even though I don't like it, I'll go." And that is the proposal I made, Hermano. And so I waited for someone to knock. So much uncertainty! "Who will be the first one to knock?" My brother was going to come at 4:00 on the dot supposedly, so "ay, please let 4:00 never come!" But nobody knocked. And it was 4:00. Suddenly—a knock! And my brother is extremely punctual. "Wow, it must be my brother. Ay, what have I done!?" But when I open the door, it was the missionaries! Hermano, when I saw them I didn't think, "oh no, anyone but them!" Instead, I felt an INMENSE joy that welled up from I don't understand where. Only then did I remember that Mormon missionaries even existed. I told them, "I am waiting for you." For many Mormons, the resurrected Lord, Jesus Christ himself follows the church's official, hierarchical pattern, which means He is not supposed to speak audibly to anyone but to the fifteen elite men He has called as His "modern prophets" and apostles. The fact that He would break the pattern to include Rosa, a member of one of the most excluded identities in contemporary constructions of Mormon Zion—a mestiza single mother—can be quite threatening to church authority. According to Jennifer Basquiat (2004), the Anglo missionaries in Haiti perceive the way God communicates with Haitian Mormons as a similar sort of threat. Haitians often report having religious conversion experiences even more spectacular than those of Joseph Smith himself. Rather than being delighted that their "investigators" are becoming converted so deeply and unmistakably to Mormonism, Anglo Mormon missionaries downplay these experiences

because the experiences threaten white supremacy. Deep down, Anglo Mormons feel that if anyone deserves to have such spectacular religious visitations, it is white people, not Haitians. Work Cited Basquiat, Jennifer Huss. 2004. "Embodied Mormonism: Performance, Vodou and the LDS Faith in Haiti." *Dialogue - A Journal of Mormon Thought* 37 (4): 1-34.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Through as many forms as there are Peruvian Mormons.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Not usually, but they can definitely be seen and recognized as the individuals they were when they were alive. Spirits existing in the place from official Mormon doctrine called "the spirit world" are thought to hold the shape of their earthly body "at its prime." The contributor's own mother, an Anglo Mormon from birth, has seen many spirits of her dead ancestors. As mentioned in a previous entry, Andean Mormons (unlike Anglo Mormons) often consider human bodies as having more than one spirit inside them, including one that can move around unbeknownst to the other ones in the body. This often happens when the human is near death or has been badly scared. For example, on Anglo Mormon missionary known to the contributor was in an accident wherein his vehicle rolled down a hill in Bolivia (a common occurrence on the narrow, serpentine road that connects La Paz in the high Andes to the jungle cities below such as San Borja). He stepped out of the vehicle virtually unscathed, but badly shaken. He lived with Bolivian Mormons at the time, and when he arrived home well past the missionary curfew, the homeowner, a Bolivian Mormon, was not worried. The Anglo missionary asked why he was not worried and the Bolivian Mormon said, "because your spirit* came to say goodbye to us as if you were going to die, but then it said, 'actually, I'll go back to my body now,' so we knew you were okay." The Anglo Mormon did not know that his spirit had done any such thing and did not report having a "near death experience" or ever being unconscious during the accident. *The word for "spirit" used in this case was "ajayu." The ajayu is an important part of understanding Andean health and sickness. There is a common ailment in the Andes, and Latin America in general, called "susto." Susto is caused when a person's ajayu leaves the body because of a scare and then gets stuck somehow, often by possessing a stone or other previously inanimate object. As one of Alejandra Vega's (2008) collaborators told her (page 3 of the below-cited article): "...Por muchas cosas el alma puede asustarse. Los niños, por ejemplo, pueden asustarse de un ruido fuerte, cosas que escuchan, cosas que ven, del oscuro...fácil se asustan los niños y ya se sale el alma del cuerpo y se enferma. Lloro mucho, le da diarrea, no duerme...y ya hay que llamar al alma, que vuelva, así se curan. Allá en Bolivia yo sé de gente que tuvo el alma atrapada, hay veces los saxra (3) agarran, quieren comer al ajayu. La persona puede morir si el alma no vuelve, jodido es..." (Gervasia, oriunda de La Paz) 3. Los saxra son espíritus malignos dependientes del Supaya, hoy identificado con el diablo Vega, Alejandra. 2008. "La pérdida del alma y la etiología de un taxón tradicional: el Susto entre los migrantes Aymara de Buenos Aires." In . Universidad Nacional de La Plata. Facultad de Humanidades y Ciencias de la Educación. Departamento de Sociología. <https://www.academica.org/000-096/449>. For the rest of these "spirit" entries, "spirit"

will be used to designate the official, Anglo Mormon version of spirit which is the non-tangible half of an individualized self that begins to exist on a different dimension of this earth called the spirit world after the death of the other half of itself, the body. If an Andean Mormon conceptualization of *ajayu* or other sort of "spirit" is used again in these entries, that difference will be stipulated.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: Not usually, though there have been instances where a spirit has tapped a Mormon on the shoulder.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: They do not have an omniscient view of this world. Their knowledge is largely restricted to what they remember during their own earth life, though they are permitted occasionally to see and even move "beyond the veil" that separates the earth's physical dimension from its "spirit world."

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: Since Peruvian Mormons in Utah have told the contributor that their ancestors have visited them in Utah, far from the place where they died, one would imagine that the spatial rules of the spirit world, though it lies in this world, are different such that spirits are not restricted to specific areas in the spirit world and, if they are, these areas do not map onto the Earth's regions.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– No

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: Potentially yes, but not all the time. They are not omniscient. It seems they have to get special dispensation to be able to see humans, but there are probably no restrictions on where the human can be seen once said dispensation is procured.

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: Spirits often know, for example, when Mormons are trying to find out about them through family history. Spirits find ways to help Mormons out with the genealogical process often by intuiting what they are thinking and even communicating with them through a sort of telepathy.

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– No

Notes: Not necessarily. It depends on your relationship to them. Also, human spirits, when they are inside living human bodies, know little more than their body's brain knows, or, rather, they do not have a way of communicating all they do know to that brain because God has deliberately placed a veil between the spirit memory and the body memory such that the living human self cannot remember (at least not much) about the preexistence.

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

Notes: Not necessarily or automatically by virtue of their being spirits. The spirits of dead humans are very much the same in personality, power, talents and inclinations as the living humans they used to be. If a human was a "seer" of the future while alive, he or she (gender continues to be binary even after death) will probably be able to do so after death in the spirit world. Mormons commonly note, for example, that if a human is addicted to smoking during life, that human's spirit will still be addicted after death but will have no recourse other than to go through lengthy (though not eternal) withdrawal symptoms because only spirits with physical bodies can smoke. The same logic goes for other bodily actions that Mormons traditionally consider "addictions," such as masturbation.

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– Yes [specify]: they are able to remember the pre-earth time

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– No

Notes: It is not so much that they can reward as that they can help Mormons do important tasks, such as fill out their FamilySearch.org family tree.

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– No

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits possess hunger:
 - Yes
 - Notes: But they cannot eat.
- ↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: the possess all of the memories and tendencies that they acquired while they had a body
- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - Notes: In waking life? Yes. Everyday? Probably not.
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - No
 - Notes: The only spirits known to posses are not the spirits of formerly living humans, they are the spirits of never-to-be humans (demons.)
 - ↳ Through divination processes:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through specialists:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
 - ↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: writing, such as leaving notes on the back of ancestral photographs that were not there before

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: The non-human supernatural beings that exist in official Mormonism and that have been seen by living Mormons include, but are not limited to, spirits of humans who have died, spirits of humans who have not been born yet, angels (this is an ontologically ambivalent category that is in some cases equivalent to a spirit and in other cases equivalent to a resurrected being), resurrected beings (beings who have died and have already been resurrected into an immortal body with a certain degree of "glory"), beings of unusual longevity (those mortal humans promised to remain on the earth until Jesus' Second Coming) and demons (the spirit children of Heavenly Father and Heavenly Mother that fought on Lucifer's side and, therefore, will never get bodies). The supernatural beings that can be seen in Peruvian Mormonism include the other kinds of dividual spirits, such as *ajayu*, that inhabit a person's body. The *kharisiri*, or "vampire of the Andes" is another supernatural being that some Peruvian Mormons have reported seeing or knowing about. These are white specters who attack humans all over the Andean world, suck out the body fat so important to their connection between the upper and inner worlds, and sell it to the capitalists to lubricate their machines. Or, as one recently baptized Mormon convert in Arequipa told the contributor, a more technologically advanced *kharisiri* might be sitting next to you on a bus, stab you in the side with a syringe, suck out your body fat—rich in collagen and lipids—and sell it to cosmetic companies. In the Andes, the *kharisiri* are not from either the inner or the upper worlds and so cannot be reasoned with. As such, there is usually no cure for this separation from one's body fat, which almost invariably results in death. Here is a YouTube video about the *kharisiri* in a non-Mormon context. It was originally in Spanish and the contributor has dubbed it in English:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Xwc19yDI1n0>

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: Only the resurrected beings of Heavenly Father, Jesus and the spirit called The Holy Ghost are thought of as omniscient. Heavenly Mother is so rarely spoken of that Mormons don't know if she is omniscient or not, but they logically assume she would be. All other supernatural beings are restricted in some way, though Satan himself (Lucifer) has very few restrictions.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Some of them do.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Some of them do.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: The omniscient ones can, the others cannot always.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: The omniscient ones can, the others cannot always.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: The omniscient ones can, the others cannot always.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: The omniscient ones do, the others do not always.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: The omniscient ones can, the others cannot always.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: there are too many different supernatural beings, including gods, to provide a concise answer

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: Since, in Mormonism, non-human supernatural beings include resurrected beings like Heavenly Father and Jesus Christ, and since, as previously mentioned, these gods can reward, supernatural beings can reward.

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Since, in Mormonism, non-human supernatural beings include resurrected beings like Heavenly Father and Jesus Christ, and since, as previously mentioned, these gods can reward, supernatural beings can reward.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Some do, some don't.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: they exhibit, along with humans, an infinite individuality or "intelligence" that is "co-eternal" with God, meaning it was never created.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: All humans are mixed human-divine beings as is the god, Jesus Christ. As these two sorts of beings are, in other ways, at the opposite poles of a human-god binary, the rest of these questions are going to be answered as they apply to either humans or God, meaning most answers are going to be "yes."

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: The most common mixed human-divine beings are us, and we can see ourselves. We are dual beings of divine spirit and biological flesh. Jesus was an even more complexly human-divine hybrid because not only did his spirit come from the sexual union of a god and a goddess as ours did but his biological body was created from the union of a celestial sperm and a mortal egg.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: Jesus is one of the omniscient beings in Mormonism, and he is a human-divine hybrid.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have other knowledge of the human world:

– Yes [specify]: Jesus is a human-divine being and He helped create the world, so

He knows a lot about it. Plus, He is all seeing and all knowing.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can reward:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can punish:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– Yes [specify]: everything that humans exhibit because all humans are human-divine beings.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

↳ In trance possession:
– No

↳ Through divination practices:
– No

Notes: Jesus does not need to resort to divination practices to communicate with humans. He communicates with them, according to Anglo Mormonism, through an intermediary called the Holy Ghost. He communicates with them, according to Peruvian Mormonism, through dreams, miracles, coincidences, and physical or auditory manifestations of Himself. Humans, as human-divine beings, do not need to resort to divination practices to communicate with each other. Most Peruvian Mormons use Whatsapp for that purpose.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: all kinds of human communication technology is used

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: In official Mormonism, once a spirit has inhabited a body it is forever biologized into the lineage of that body under a Eurocentric kin idiom. Therefore, after a person dies, their spirit, as an individual with a name and dates, will forever fall into a specific, numbered slot on the modern Western arboreal model of vertical blood-descent. That spirit will become an "ancestor" on the "lineage" of a specific living "descendant" who, forever after, will be able to capture this relationship visually on the church's genealogical website, <https://www.familysearch.org/en/>. In Peruvian Mormonism, this Western kinship model is considered vital, however there is a sense that the substance that connects families together is not so much shared "blood" as it is shared food and drink. In Anglo Mormonism, proper kinship is only established at the moment two partners meet in temple marriage or at the moment two gametes meet in conception. In Peruvian Mormonism, these two sorts of meetings are important, but added to them is a third and just as legitimate form of kin establishment: living, eating, and dancing together in place and over time. This means the model of vertical blood descent, fixated as it is on whose sexual relationship produced which offspring, clashes quite dramatically with Peruvian Mormon notions of kinship and can cause many to feel their ancestry is diminished compared to the ancestry of Anglo Mormons with "pioneer stock." This feeling is then substantiated when a Peruvian Mormon actually sees an Anglo Mormon's immensely complete "family tree," especially if that Anglo Mormon's own ancestors were Anglo Mormons who had their own family trees. For example, see the photograph below of the contributor's daughters' family tree. The contributor is an Anglo Mormon and his spouse is a Peruvian Mormon. Therefore, their daughters should theoretically have an Anglo half and a Peruvian half of their tree. In practice however, their Anglo nine tenths is much more brachiated and foliated than their Peruvian one tenth.

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It may seem like a hierarchy, but it is too complex to be a strict hierarchy when one considers human spirits, gods, and demons to all be "supernatural beings." It is more like the nexus of a continuum and two binaries. The continuum represents time because as time passes, certain beings become more powerful. Human spirits can become gods, and gods can achieve "eternal progression." Heavenly Father is more powerful today than he was yesterday. One of the binaries is "body versus no body." Supernatural beings with bodies are much more powerful than ones without bodies, but there are two notable exceptions to this. One is Satan. He doesn't have a body, yet seems to be more powerful in some ways (such as in cunning) than Heavenly Father himself, a god with the highest form of supernatural body, one that eternally progresses. The other exception is the Holy Ghost who also doesn't have a body but is considered part of the "God Head" or the pantheon of three gods at the "top" of whatever model this web of quasi-hierarchies would turn out to be. The other binary is good versus evil, which is also complicated by the Holy Ghost and Satan. The Holy Ghost is good and Satan is evil, so they seem to be on opposite sides of that binary, and, since neither has a body, they are on a relatively level playing field. Still, on a power hierarchy, who would come out on top, Satan or the Holy Ghost? It is hard to say who is more powerful, but it would seem that Satan holds more power than any of the individual gods in the godhead simply because he is the sole inhabitant of the opposite of the godhead. His power over the godhead stems from the fact that if he chose to stop being evil, he would throw off the whole balance of the universe. According to the Book of Mormon, there would be no good without evil. Therefore, Satan has the power, in eliminating his own evil, to eliminate good. The Holy Ghost does not have that power because if the Holy Ghost turned evil, Heavenly Father and Jesus would still be there to offset the deficit in goodness and restore balance. It is also hard to say whether Satan and the Holy Ghost, being without bodies, are more powerful than humans with bodies. Heavenly Mother also stands to turn any sort of hierarchy on its head and expose it as a suspiciously human-like patriarchy, which is perhaps why she is rarely mentioned in Mormonism. Is Heavenly Mother the female equivalent to Heavenly Father to the extent that She has the same amount of power as He does? Or, does She in fact surpass Him in power? Furthermore, does Jesus have a female equivalent? What about the Holy Ghost and Satan? And then there is the inevitable question, what about the god of the world Heavenly Father inhabited before He achieved godhood? What about the Satan of that world? The Heavenly Mother of that world? The Jesus of that world? Or, as would seem to be the case if one reads the entire canon of Mormon scripture, did the Jesus from this world die for the sins of everyone on all worlds including the sins that Heavenly Father himself committed back when he was a human? If so, where on any "hierarchy" would this place Jesus?

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

— Yes

Notes: Some of them are, some of them aren't. For example, Satan only has dominion over this world. Elohim has dominion over many worlds.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

— Yes [specify]: chronological, body/no body, evil/good, male/female

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

— Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: Heavenly Father cares if Mormons break their health code (the Word Of Wisdom) even though it was originally given as a mere suggestion and explicitly "not by way of commandment." Also, there is nothing in the original code (from the Doctrine and Covenants, here: <https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/scriptures/dc-testament/dc/89.1,2,4?lang=eng&clang=eng#p1,2,4>) that would give the reader the slightest clue as to how the contemporary code is understood. If one were to follow the original code, one would have to be vegetarian and eat only locally available fruits, vegetables, and grains. The contemporary health code involves none of that and only includes negative language. One must completely avoid coffee, the tea leaf, alcohol, tobacco, and illicit drugs. The code has been interpreted in many Andean Mormon congregations as requiring the prohibition of coca, a millennial herb vital to Andean culture. Interestingly, hierba mate has not been prohibited nearly as often in Mormon congregations in Argentina, Uruguay and Paraguay where it is consumed almost constantly even during Mormon worship services. The demonizing of coca (largely in Bolivia) and the acceptance of hierba mate, both of which are mild stimulants, probably has something to do with the way coca is associated with indigeneity and hierba mate with whiteness. In other words, the inequitable application of the Word of Wisdom in South America reveals Mormonism's fundamental anti-indigeneity and white supremacy similar to the way disproportionate sentencing for crack cocaine possession (associated with Black people) over powder cocaine possession (associated with white people) reveals the anti-blackness fundamental to the U.S. judicial system. The racism behind the Word of Wisdom also plays out in the Pacific Islands where Mormonism has become extremely widespread. The kava ceremony, vital to conceptions of masculinity on many islands and in many Tongan and Samoan neighborhoods of Salt Lake City, Utah, has been deemed against the Word of Wisdom.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: And here we see the mix of two taboos that Heavenly Father cares about. Only worthy Mormons can enter the holy temples of Mormonism. One of the questions to which Mormons must answer affirmatively if they want to enter the temple is "do you obey the Word Of Wisdom?" People who do not obey the Word Of Wisdom defile Mormonism's most sacred space, and people who chew coca (most people in the high Andes) are often considered to be in violation of the Word Of Wisdom. This contributes to a situation in Peruvian Mormon temple worship wherein a brown body is automatically more suspect than a white body of profaning the sacredness of the space, a space that is saturated in white pigmented symbology.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: Notably in Anglo Mormonism, especially in Utah, the U.S. flag is a sacred object

that Heavenly Father cares about more than any other nation's flag. This idea spreads to Peruvian Mormons in Utah because of the church's long standing relationship to the Boy Scouts of America (an organization with its own horrendous anti-indigeneity and settler adoption fantasy). Peruvian Mormons in Utah are part of Spanish-speaking congregations that the Anglo Mormon leadership in Utah considers mere training grounds for Latin Americans who, when they become fully "Mormonized" are supposed to graduate into fully-fledged English-speaking congregations. Latin American Mormons rarely do this, however. They stay in Spanish-Speaking congregations even if they prefer English because these congregations provide a refuge from the whiteness, what Peruvian Mormons call "la gringada," that oppresses them in most other venues of their lives. Yet, at the same time, they see English-speaking congregations as practicing a more advanced, superior form of Mormonism. Part of the superior nature of these English-speaking congregations is that they often have long, generational traditions of strong Scouting programs that are integrally interwoven into the church's rites of passage for males, which involve ordination to the holy priesthood. Religiosity, U.S. patriotism, and "playing Indian" become so intertwined in these congregations that the U.S. flag sewn onto each Boy Scout's uniform becomes a symbol as sacred as the "sign of the compass" sewn into the breast of the sacred undergarments their Scout Masters wear. Rather than transferring into English-speaking congregations*, Latin American Mormons wish to increase the level of spirituality in their own Spanish-speaking congregations so that they can catch up and even surpass the level of spirituality in English-Speaking congregations. Spanish-speaking congregations that wish to rise to English-speaking congregations' level of righteousness often come to see a successful scouting program as a key indicator of that rise. Peruvian Mormons in Utah are extremely proud of their children who have achieved the Eagle Scout designation, especially if they have done so within a Spanish-speaking congregation's very own scouting program. Scouting often involves multi-troop camp-outs where scouts from these Spanish-speaking congregations (who tend to prefer English) and their leaders (who sometimes cannot speak English) compete with scouts from English-speaking congregations in all kinds of outdoor events, such as getting back into a capsized canoe from the middle of a deep pond, that most Spanish-speaking scouts, coming from inner cities in Utah, have not exactly had occasion to practice. The end result is that scouts from Spanish-speaking congregations perform dismally in most of these areas. One of the ways their leaders have them compensate for these humiliations is by not humiliating themselves further through sloppy uniforms. The Spanish-speaking leaders become extremely strict and knowledgeable in uniform regulations, including and especially the treatment of the U.S. flag patch that must go in a certain place and in a certain orientation (certainly not upside-down) on a particular one of each scouts' shoulders. One Peruvian Mormon scout master who saw the rise of Spanish-speaking scouting in Northern Utah, became emotional in an interview with the contributor as he described what the scouting uniform meant to him and how he always taught his scouts to not throw their uniform on the ground with the rest of the dirty laundry as if it were just any old shirt. This scout master was the aforementioned Basilio Corimayta. Since the BSA uniform includes a U.S. flag patch, and since, if a U.S. flag touches the ground it must be ceremonially burned, he taught his scouts to treat their entire uniform like a U.S. flag and never let it touch the ground. Incidentally, during the contributor's fieldwork in 2018, Peru's national team made it into the FIFA World Cup for the first time in 35 years. This was a huge deal among the Peruvian Mormon community in Utah, and Basilio, an avid soccer fan and proud Peruvian, often wore a Peruvian national team jersey in support. The jersey had a Peruvian flag patch sewn into it. One day, as the contributor was taking photos of Basilio's home decor as part of this project (see photo) he noticed that among the clothing on the floor around the washing machine lay Basilio's Peruvian national team jersey. Apparently, he did not hold the Peruvian flag as sacred as he held the U.S. flag despite the fact that, at the time, he was an undocumented alien as far as the U.S. government was concerned. This is all to say that scouting's role in the Utah instantiation of Peruvian Mormonism has made the U.S. flag an explicitly sacred object. As a result of the BSA's welcoming of homosexual scout masters, the church announced its schism from scouting. It later announced that it would begin its own youth program in 2020 that would not

resemble scouting, and, as such, be available to youth all over the world. Perhaps it realized that trying to be a global organization while holding onto an explicitly U.S. exceptionalist program was hurting its multicultural image, especially in Latin America. However, its elimination of scouting has left many Latin American Mormons in Utah floundering to find what the mark of full inclusion into Anglo Mormonism is now supposed to be. After working for decades to finally bring their scouting programs up to the level of the English-speaking programs in Utah, the church pulled the entire program out from under them. *The contributor knows of many Peruvian Mormons in Utah who have transferred to English-speaking congregations only to return to their Spanish-speaking congregation one year later. The reasons these Peruvian Mormons return to their Spanish-speaking ward include never being given a "calling" or responsibility within the English-speaking ward, rarely being greeted or spoken to in the English-speaking ward, being the victim of constant microaggressions in the English-speaking ward, being the victim of overt racism in the English-speaking ward, and being told by the bishop of the English-speaking ward, "I feel prompted to tell you that you should attend the Spanish-speaking ward." For more information about Spanish-speaking Mormon congregations in the U.S., see the works of Ignacio Garcia, such as his book *Chicano While Mormon: Activism, War, and Keeping the Faith*. Also see the following book chapters: Garcia, Ignacio M. 2015. "A Barrio Perspective on Building Zion in the Twenty-First Century." In *A Book of Mormons: Latter-Day Saints on a Modern-Day Zion*, edited by Emily W. Jensen and Tracy McKay-Lamb, 69-75. I Speak for Myself. Ashland, Oregon: White Cloud Press. Garcia, Ignacio M. 2018. "Empowering Latino Saints to Transcend Historical Racialism: A Bishop's Tale." In *Decolonizing Mormonism: Approaching a Postcolonial Zion*, edited by Gina Colvin and Joanna Brooks, 139-60. Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: female chastity and clothing, enforcing the nuclearization of family, delegitimizing all family models associated with people of Color,

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: all non-marital sexual practices and homosexual practices are sin. Up until 2015 at least, the official church considered interethnic marriage ill advised.

Notes: There was a short time in the late 80's when the official church published in its Handbook of Instructions that oral sex within marriage was sinful.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Another of the questions to which Mormons must answer affirmatively if they are to receive or renew their "temple recommend" card required for temple entry is, "are you honest in all your dealings with your fellow man."

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: Part of the temple rite known as the endowment involves many oaths. God takes the breaking of these very seriously. The officiator in the ceremony himself states, "God will not be mocked."

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: There are plenty of scriptures in the Mormon canon that focus on Puritanical time thrift, such as this one: "the day of this life is the day for men to perform their labors. And now, as I said unto you before, as ye have had so many witnesses, therefore, I beseech of you that ye do not procrastinate the day of your repentance until the end; for after this day of life, which is given us to prepare for eternity, behold, if we do not improve our time while in this life, then cometh the night of darkness wherein there can be no labor performed."

[https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/scriptures/bofm/alma/34.32,33?](https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/scriptures/bofm/alma/34.32,33?lang=eng&clang=eng#p32,33)

lang=eng&clang=eng#p32,33 As Anglo Mormons often associate laziness with indigeneity and blackness, they have written an entire curriculum called the Self-Reliance Initiative that they piloted in Latin America and Africa. The entire thrust of this curriculum is to make its students feel guilty about three principal things: 1) every moment they waste not trying to earn money, 2) every time they are unpunctual, and, 3) every time they depend for financial help on their "extended family" or (God forbid) their church. Members of Perifericos Ward in Arequipa, Peru in 2018, including the contributor, were required by their local church leaders to sign up for one of 4 Self-Reliance course offerings. Many members who applied for church financial assistance in this ward were required to first present a diploma from one of these 12-week courses before their assistance was granted. The hope behind adding this prerequisite for financial help was that, after finishing what amounted to a 12-week guilt trip, members would blame their financial situation on their own laziness and no longer have the gall to ask for help.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: Contention is of the devil.

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
– Yes

Notes: This is one fourth of the four fold mission statement of the church.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
– Yes

Notes: Yes, but not that much. Heavenly Father seems to care much more about protecting his church from moochers than he does about distributing the immense stores of His church's wealth equitably.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
– Yes [specify]: genealogy, statistics, preserving textual history.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:
– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:
– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The punishment of greatest emphasis in the afterlife is phrased to outsiders as if it were a reward. Mormon missionaries tell potential converts that they can be rewarded with the opportunity to be with their loved ones after death if they will do what is necessary to become worthy to enter the temple and be ritually "sealed" to them. People who grew up Mormon in the highly Mormon society of Utah often go out into the broader world thinking that Mormons are the only ones who know about the possibility of being together with family members after death. In reality, most Christians believe that being with loved ones after death is simply the default state, not a reward or anything that has to be earned. This means the Mormon idea of "forever family" is actually a punishment when phrased negatively: "If you do not get 'sealed' with your loved ones, your punishment is that you will not be with them in the afterlife." As the current president of the church declared in 2019 in what many U.S. Mormon feminists have dubbed the "Sad Heaven" speech, Love songs perpetuate a false hope that love is all you need if you want to be together forever. And some erroneously believe that the Resurrection of Jesus Christ provides a promise that all people will be with their loved ones after death. In truth, the Savior Himself has made it abundantly clear that while His Resurrection assures that every person who ever lived will indeed be resurrected and live forever, much more is required if we want to have the high privilege of exaltation. Salvation is an individual matter, but exaltation is a family matter. (Nelson 2019, 89) Then, speaking to all those who know that they must make covenants in the temple in order to seal the Anglo-defined family, but who, for whatever reason, have not yet made those covenants, Nelson continued, they have chosen not to make covenants with God. They have not received the ordinances [one-time rites] that will exalt them with their families and bind them together forever ... They need to understand that while there is a place for them hereafter—with wonderful men and women who also chose not to make covenants with God—that is not the place where families will be reunited and be given the privilege to live and progress forever. That is not the kingdom where they will experience the fulness of joy—of never-ending progression and happiness. Those consummate blessings can come only by living in an exalted celestial realm with God, our Eternal Father; His Son, Jesus Christ; and our wonderful, worthy, and qualified family members ... as you choose not to make covenants with God, you are settling for a most meager roof over your head throughout all eternity ... If you truly love your family and if you desire to be exalted with them throughout eternity, pay the price now. (Nelson 2019, 90) Nelson, Russell M. 2019. "Come Follow Me." *The Ensign of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints*, May 2019.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

Notes: This is not considered punishment necessarily, it is considered more to be the natural consequence of actions. All humans will be resurrected to a certain degree of glory in a human form. All these degrees of glory will seem like "rewards" compared to the way humans are living now. However, there will be degrees of glory that will be inferior to others with no chance of leveling up. This could eventually, after one had an eternity to think about it, be considered a punishment.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]
– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Notes: When bad things happen to Mormons in this life, they are often considered the natural consequences of actions rather than deliberate, divine punishments. Sometimes they are also considered part of a God-given trial meant to make the recipient stronger. Mormons often say that God chastises most the people he loves most. At the same time, when bad things happen to non-Mormons in this life, Mormons often see these things as divine punishments, especially when they happen to groups of people who have heard about Mormonism but have largely rejected it, such as African Americans.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
– Yes

Notes: Mormonism, as a U.S. religion, always considers the U.S. to be on the side of righteousness in any war. In this view, losing a war against the U.S. can be seen as a punishment for wickedness.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
– Yes

Notes: Especially if those journeys happen on Sunday when one should not be traveling. However, Mormons focus far more on the blessings that come from keeping the commandments than they do on the punishments that come from breaking them.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
– Yes

Notes: Assuming mild sensory displeasure is the natural consequence of breaking a

commandment, such as becoming addicted to an illicit drug, then punishment could include this.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
– Yes
Notes: Mormon scriptures are replete with such punishments.

↳ Other [specify]
– Yes
Notes: A punishment in this life could consist of not having one's Patriarchal Blessing promises fulfilled. Those who grew up Mormon often undergo a ritual wherein a priesthood-holding man puts his hands upon their head and pronounces upon them a blessing acting as the mouthpiece for Jesus Christ. This blessing is then typed up (lately it is digitized). One copy is given to the recipient and the other is curated at church headquarters in Salt Lake City, Utah. In these blessings, Jesus promises certain things that are contingent upon the recipients' faithfulness. Often Mormons are promised that they will live to see the Second Coming, that they will be able to serve a mission in a foreign language, or that they will have many children. If and when these promises are not fulfilled, it can be interpreted as a punishment for not following through with some aspect of "faithfulness." This can be especially psychologically damaging in the case of childlessness.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:
– No

Notes: Sometimes they are done by what is considered the natural consequence of the action.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:
– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
– Yes

↳ Done randomly:
– No

Notes: Good things randomly happen, but these would not be considered a reward from Heavenly Father. Mormons believe that there are certain specific blessings, known only to God, that are attached to certain acts of righteousness such that if a person keeps a certain commandment "God is bound" to grant the blessing He had previously attached to that commandment. God has no choice but to reward the person, even if they do the action with ulterior motives, such as testing God to see if he really exists. This sort of logic is not extended to punishments in the same way. Bad things are only suspected of being divine punishments. Good things are almost sure to be divine rewards. Tithing is the prime example of this. Almost every Peruvian Mormon has a tithing story akin to this hypothetical story: "I was on my last cent, but I decided to pay tithing instead of buy food for my family. When I got home, I happened to put my hand in my pocket and there was 100 soles that had not been there before." Windfalls are often seen as the blessing that God has attached to the act of paying tithing.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Becoming a god.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Prosperity theology is not deliberate, but very strong in Mormonism. Wealth is seen as a supernatural reward for righteousness and proper living.

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– No

Notes: Good luck exists, but the benefits that come from it would not be considered supernatural rewards.

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Notes: Early Anglo Mormon origin myths of settling Utah are replete with such reward stories.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Many mission presidents all over the world promise their male, full-time missionaries that the strictness with which they obey the mission rules will equate to the beauty of their future spouse.

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
 - Notes: This is actually the canonized reward for obeying the Word of Wisdom.

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The Bible is replete with such promises, and Mormons not only believe in the Bible, they ritually connect their lineages to the Biblical ones with the highest propensity for fertility. This is done through a ritual called the Patriarchal Blessing wherein Mormons are told their fortune, which usually includes some mention of reproductive success, and ascribed to a specific tribe of Israel.

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Yes
 - Notes: Reward in this life consists of "love at home" in a nuclear family consisting only of a conjugal couple and their minor children living in a suburban, single-family home.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: resurrect the dead

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: If Jesus comes again during this lifetime, then yes.

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– Yes

Notes: There is a much speculation about this in Mormonism. Some believe that Mormons must usher in the millennium by sending missionaries to every single country. Others think it will be accomplished by getting a certain percentage of the proxy "temple work" finished for the world's global dead.

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Yes

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– Yes

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: Mormons are often saying things like, "I think we will be surprised at how many Mormons don't survive the calamities of the end times."

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: There was a mini-eschaton on the American continent when Jesus died according to the Book of Mormon. Many people were killed, but the "more righteous among them" were not. Some Mormons take heart in this because it does not say "the most righteous among them." It is important to understand that Mormons believe the final eschaton will happen after Jesus Christ has reigned personally on the earth for 1000 years (the millennium), meaning that those who will be destroyed are only going to be those who openly rebel against His supernatural reign.

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Other survival condition:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: If the field knew, we'd tell you about it so you could prepare!

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

Notes: This distinction is the culture versus doctrine distinction which is unclear to most Peruvian Mormons, but crystal clear to most Anglo Mormons. As mentioned in a previous entry, Anglo Mormons use the fact that this distinction is unclear to Peruvian Mormons as evidence that Peruvian Mormons are not fit for self-government.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:
– Yes

Notes: Especially those involving gender, which is not considered a metaphysical concept, but a biological one.

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):
– Yes

Notes: There is a sense that sin accumulates and stains as if it were an impersonal cosmic substance.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:
– All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):
– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):
– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

Notes: This above all.

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - Yes
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - Yes
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - Yes [specify]: self-reliance

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: In fact, to be considered a full person in the cultural sense in this religious society, you have to be heterosexually married.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Notes: Though Mormons are famous for polygamy (mostly polygyny), the Church of Jesus Christ Latter-Day Saints, since the 1920's, generally excommunicates members who practice polygamy in this life. In the afterlife, however, polygyny (but not polyandry) will exist. A male may be "sealed" for time and all eternity to only one wife in the temple. However, when that wife dies, the male may marry another wife for time and all eternity in the temple. In the afterlife, this male will remain "sealed" to both of these wives. For example, the current president of the church, Russel Nelson has two wives sealed to him for eternity, but one is living with him now and the other is waiting for him in the spirit world. The continued existence of the doctrine of celestial polygyny within a tradition that demonizes other sects of Mormonism for their terrestrial polygyny causes much cognitive dissonance and spiritual trauma among some Mormon women, largely Anglo Mormon women (see attached article). Most Peruvian Mormon women are not aware of their church's history with polygamy much less its continuation of the doctrine. One Peruvian Mormon woman from Arequipa who had served as a church historic site missionary in Salt Lake City, Utah reported to the contributor that she was often asked uncomfortable questions from anti-Mormons who would take her tour through Temple Square. One of these anti-Mormons told her all kinds of things about how Joseph Smith practiced polygyny and even sent other men away on missions so that he could marry their wives (essentially forcing these wives to practice polyandry). She was so distraught over this information, which she classified as lies, that she was unable to leave her apartment the next day and almost left her mission. She recovered, but she still characterizes these things as lies. She does not know, or does not want to know, that they are historically accurate facts about Joseph Smith.

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: No sex before marriage, no extramarital sex during marriage, and no homosexual sex ever. The church's stance on masturbation, something it has mostly related to males, has relaxed over the years, but was once (especially in the 1970's and 80's) staunchly prohibited (see attached article and this YouTube video <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QD7mAyAypQo>).

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: No sex before marriage, no extramarital sex during marriage, and no homosexual sex ever. Added to these blanket constraints are whatever constraints a woman's husband decides to add assuming the woman was "endowed" in the temple prior to 2019. The endowment is a lengthy

temple rite wherein, prior to 2019, females, married or unmarried, were required to vow to hearken to the voice of their husband even as he hearkened to the voice of Heavenly Father. The temple rite has since changed (<https://religionnews.com/2019/01/03/major-changes-to-mormon-temple-ceremony-especially-for-women/>) but the vow still remains in place for each woman who made it (depending on her interpretation of the past vow and how it relates to the change in the current temple rite), meaning that her husband or future husband (even if he is not a Mormon) is the middleman between her and God.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

— No

Notes: However, there have been instances of bishops in the early settler-colonial period of Utah castrating young men as punishment for offenses related to diminishing the pool of plural wives available to the bishops (see <https://www.yearofpolygamy.com/year-of-polygamy/year-of-polygamy-southern-utah-polygamy-orderville-santa-clara-cedar-city-and-violence-episode-48/>)

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

— Yes

Notes: The first Sunday of each month is traditionally "Fast Sunday" in Mormonism. Members are encouraged to go without food and drink for two meals and then donate the money saved to the ward's "fast offerings" fund that then goes to ward members in need. In Utah, young men ages 11-14 (not young women) often go door to door to everyone in their ward asking for these fast offerings on Fast Sunday as part of these young men's priesthood duty as "deacons" (the first level of the preparatory priesthood called the Aaronic priesthood). This does not happen in Peru because the houses of the congregants in a ward are not usually within walking distance of each other. It also does not happen for Peruvian Mormons in Utah who go to Spanish-speaking wards. Utah has such a high concentration of English-speaking Mormons that the English-speaking "ward boundaries" are drawn around extremely small areas on the map. This means that each neighborhood is its own "ward" or congregation. On the other hand, for Mormons who attend one of Utah's 160+ Spanish-speaking congregations, ward boundaries can include areas too vast for 12-year-old boys to cover on foot, especially if those boys are fasting. Still, Spanish-speaking congregations in both Peru and Utah are encouraged to fast and simply bring the fast offering to church. The "sacrament meeting" (similar to mass) on a Fast Sunday, rather than consisting of the usual prepared speeches by ward members and leaders who have been specifically invited to speak, consists instead of an open mic sharing of spiritual stories, thoughts and anecdotes. This special, monthly sacrament meeting is called "fast and testimony meeting." Fasting is thought to make the sharing of spiritual stories more powerful. Since fasting weakens the body, it heightens the senses of the spirit, which can connect to the Holy Ghost, a male member of the God Head who does not have a body. The Holy Ghost lets Anglo Mormons know what is true or not by making them emotional. This often makes Anglo Mormons cry a lot during Fast and Testimony meetings, assuming that a lot of truth is being spoken. Peruvian Mormons, on the other hand, have a different epistemology that relies less on the Holy Ghost and do not often cry during their Fast and Testimony meetings. Another difference between Peruvian and Anglo Mormon Fast and Testimony meetings is that Peruvian Mormons (both in Peru and Utah) never let a second go by between speakers. There is always a line to go up to the mic. Anglo Mormons Fast and Testimony meetings, on the other hand, often include extremely long spaces of awkward silence between speakers. When the next speaker does eventually come up to the mike, she will often mention how The Spirit (Holy Ghost) "worked" on her during the silence to get her to come up and "bear her testimony." Another difference is that Peruvians as a demographic have more years of formal education than the U.S. population at large and much of that education involves oratory instruction. This means that Peruvian Mormon impromptu speech at these open mic meetings (even from children), is usually much more coherent, original and engaging from the audience's perspective than Anglo Mormon speech (even from adults), which tends to include the same pat phrases that have become the fodder for much Mormon parody: "I'd like to bear my testimony. I know this church is true. I love my family. Namajesuschrisamen."

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: See the aforementioned health code called the Word of Wisdom.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: However, there was a time in early Anglo Mormonism in Utah called "The Reformation" when a concept called "blood atonement" was practiced. It was thought that there were certain sins that could only be erased through killing the sinner. (see <https://www.yearofpolygamy.com/year-of-polygamy/year-of-polygamy-polygamy-and-blood-atonement-episode-38/>)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Part of the temple ritual known as the endowment requires members to be willing to sacrifice all things, "even their own lives if necessary" for the building up of "Zion." Though these oath-takers must be willing to make these sacrifices, they have not been called on to actually go through with them as of yet. All members, regardless of whether they have received temple ordinances, are required to pay a full ten percent of their monthly gross income to the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints headquartered in Salt Lake City. This payment can now be made directly to church headquarters online.

↳ To other in-group members:

– No

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– No

Other:

– Yes [specify]: to the quasi-metaphorical concept of "establishing Zion."

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Mormons do not usually just attend whatever church meeting they happen upon each Sunday. They belong, every day, to a tight-knit congregation wherein they usually have a significant responsibility that often involves organizing and participating in mid-week activities. Since Peruvian Mormons in Peru have often had to sacrifice belonging in what remains a largely Andean Catholic society that involves ritual drunkenness (prohibited by Mormonism) and cyclical responsibility in sponsoring extremely expensive patron saint festivals (see photo), they tend to turn to their Mormon congregation for more aspects of daily sociability than their Anglo Mormon counterparts do in Utah. Peruvian Mormon congregations become "ward families" in a much more real sense than English-speaking congregations in Utah. Perifericos ward in Arequipa had some sort of class, activity, dance, party, talent night, missionary farewell, pollada (chicken cook-off fundraiser), dance practice for the annual multi-congregation Andean dance contest (see photo), FIFA World Cup showing, reenactment of the Anglo Mormon Great Plains pioneer crossing (see photo), or Executive Committee planning meeting nearly every night during the contributor's fieldwork. It is the contributor's estimation that adult Peruvian Mormons in Peru and Utah spend an average of 20 hours per week on church-related activities where as Anglo Mormons in Utah spend 6 hours. If Perifericos ward's WhatsApp group feed is any indication, the time that ward members spent on church-related activities (though now online) actually increased during the height of the COVID-19 disaster in Arequipa.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Notes: Peruvian Mormons in the past have had to take significant physical risks in order to get to the places where the family-binding rituals can be performed. Only families bound together in this form of ritual kinship can be whole families in the afterlife. The only places these rituals can happen are the holy temples, and Peru did not receive its first temple until 1986. Prior to this, the only temple in South America was in Sao Paolo, Brazil. Many Peruvian Mormons have harrowing stories filled with miracles about their trip to the Sao Paolo temple. Before the Arequipa temple was dedicated in December 2019, Peruvian Mormons in Arequipa had to travel the 16 to 18 hours on bus to get to the closest temple in Lima. For many of the elderly members, this involved significant physical risk. Also, bus travel in Peru is not all that safe. A member of Perifericos ward died in 2019 in a bus accident coming back from Lima (it was not a temple trip).

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Notes: In Peruvian Mormonism, this largely revolves around Mormonism's alcohol and idolatry prohibitions. Alcohol and patron saint worship are an integral part of Andean Catholicism, a popular form of Catholicism in Arequipa, Peru (especially among a growing minority of recent migrants from Puno and Cuzco). When Peruvians become Mormons, they are often no longer invited to festivals and parties that involve casual drinking, ritual drunkenness or patron saint worship (not that they would attend even if they were invited). Since these festivals involve communal indebtedness and reciprocity, no longer being able to fully participate in them through drinking alcohol often means losing

membership in the community entirely. As alcohol is strongly associated with dancing in Peru, many Peruvian non-Mormons are shocked to find out that Mormons can have one without the other. That Mormons can dance but not drink does not compute in the Andean Catholic mindset. Be that as it may, dancing is extremely important for Peruvian Mormons even though alcohol is extremely prohibited (see video). Sharing large quantities of food and Inca Kola (instead of alcohol) in close proximity with each other is also extremely important (see photo).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The field doesn't know because this is completely up to personal preference and chance. There are many small-scale rituals in Mormonism that are not requisite or regular. Personal prayer is supposed to be done at least daily, but could happen multiple times per day as well. Receiving a blessing of health by the laying on of hands and anointing of consecrated olive oil is a small-scale ritual that is only performed when there is a health problem.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 150

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 168

Notes: 168 is the number of hours in a week. The most regular, large ritual in which Mormons participate involves their weekly Sunday meetings. In 2019, the church changed its Sunday schedule world wide from 3 hours to 2 hours. From an anthropological perspective, the entire 2 hours involve a complex ritual, only part of which, the blessing, passing and taking of the sacrament (Eucharist), is what Mormons themselves would consider an "ordinance" or ritual. The sacrament ritual lasts about 10 minutes and is performed approximately 48 Sundays each year in each congregation.

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Yes, Mormonism is an extremely bureaucratic and U.S. centric religion, so of course there are checks and balances on everything. This is especially the case in Peruvian Mormonism because the Anglo leaders of the church suspect Peruvians, and all people in what they consider the "underdeveloped" Global South, of corruption and ineptitude. This is why many positions of prominence in the church in Arequipa, Peru, such as the position of "mission president" are held

by Anglo Mormons flown in from Utah.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– No

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: There is a pamphlet that Anglo-controlled church committees in Utah produce called For the Strength of Youth. One focus of the pamphlet is personal hygiene and modesty in dress. New editions come out every few years, but many past editions included specific standards for hair and beards. The current online edition simply encourages Mormon youth to avoid "extreme" hairstyles (see attached). Many Peruvian Mormons take this pamphlet very seriously and use it as a manual for everyday life. The pamphlet is very similar to colonial guidelines established in Peru in order to "deindianize" the people and make them more docile and comely so that they could be more easily convinced to part with their land, labor and lifeways.

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: See above. Also see the entire For the Strength of Youth pamphlet here: <https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/manual/for-the-strength-of-youth?lang=eng> Also see the entire 2011 edition of the pamphlet attached.

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

Notes: One of the most common, optional markers of Mormon membership is a ring with a CTR emblem that stands for Choose The Right. Another common, quasi mandatory marker of Mormon membership is the complete absence of tattoos. As the contributor likes contradictions, he personally has a tattoo of the CTR emblem on his right shoulder.

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

Notes: This is not something that most Peruvian Mormons know about, but there was a small movement when Anglo Mormons first arrived in Utah to build a new society complete with a new alphabet, currency, etc. Here is a web page dedicated to the alphabet:
<http://www.deseretalphabet.org/>

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: there is an ability called "modar" that allows Mormons to spot a fellow Mormon in a crowd.

Notes: "Modar" (Mormon radar) is facilitated by the fact that Mormons who have gone through the temple ritual called the endowment have to wear special undergarments forever after. The bottom garment goes down to just above the knee and the top garment covers the shoulders. In order to cover these garments, Mormons have to wear, at the very least, shorts that go to the knee and shirts that cover the shoulders. On a hot day on a Southern California boardwalk (Orange County, California has a large concentration of Mormons) most people will be wearing very little clothing. Therefore, if you see someone wearing a full t-shirt and capris, there is a good chance that person is Mormon. However, depending on individual preference and individual interpretation of the oath taken upon accepting the garments, many Mormons do not wear them while exercising, swimming, or engaging in other activities to which they do not find them amenable. This lessens the accuracy of "modar." Furthermore, in certain societies, such as Arequipa, Peru wherein most people cover up most of their bodies regardless of religious preference, "modar" is even less effective. In fact, most Peruvian Mormons have not heard of modar. One venue wherein modar is commonly used is U.S. airports. In airports, people tend to dress comfortably, and Anglo Mormons tend to wear the bare minimum to cover up their garments, thus leaving them slightly visible if seen from the right vantage. As people tend to have the time to people-watch at airports, some Mormons find it fun to try to zero in on other Mormons by using all the clues above and then confirming their hypothesis with a discrete peak under the suspected target's clothing. Another characteristic that will cause a Mormon's modar to ping, even in a Peru, is the sight of a very young couple wherein the mother is carrying an infant, the father is pushing a double stroller containing a 1-year-old and a 2-year-old and they are being followed by a three-year-old on a tricycle and a four-year-old on a bicycle. Peruvian Mormons tend to have quite a few more kids than the norm for their society and they also tend to marry extremely young. In Arequipa it is ideal to get married around age 30 among non-Mormons. Among Mormons, on the other hand, if one is unmarried at 30 one has almost lost hope of ever getting married. The ideal age for Mormon marriage in both Peru and Utah is 21 for males and 19 for females.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: In every Mormon congregation the contributor has joined around the world (Bolivia, Mexico, Canada, U.S, Taiwan, China, Japan, Turkey, Peru) Mormons address each other with the

title Brother or Sister. They do not consider these "fictive" kin titles since, according to Mormon cosmology, all humans are literally spirit siblings born of the same two heavenly parents (though there is the possibility that Heavenly Father practices polygyny, meaning some of us are mere half-siblings to others of us).

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Notes: It is extremely common, but again, it is not fictive from an emic point of view.

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: In fact, to be considered a full person in the cultural sense in this religious society, you have to be heterosexually married.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Notes: Though Mormons are famous for polygamy (mostly polygyny), the Church of Jesus Christ Latter-Day Saints, since the 1920's, generally excommunicates members who practice polygamy in this life. In the afterlife, however, polygyny (but not polyandry) will exist. A male may be "sealed" for time and all eternity to only one wife in the temple. However, when that wife dies, the male may marry another wife for time and all eternity in the temple. In the afterlife, this male will remain "sealed" to both of these wives. For example, the current president of the church, Russel Nelson has two wives sealed to him for eternity, but one is living with him now and the other is waiting for him in the spirit world. The continued existence of the doctrine of celestial polygyny within a tradition that demonizes other sects of Mormonism for their terrestrial polygyny causes much cognitive dissonance and spiritual trauma among some Mormon women, largely Anglo Mormon women (see attached article). Most Peruvian Mormon women are not aware of their church's history with polygamy much less its continuation of the doctrine. One Peruvian Mormon woman from Arequipa who had served as a church historic site missionary in Salt Lake City, Utah reported to the contributor that she was often asked uncomfortable questions from anti-Mormons who would take her tour through Temple Square. One of these anti-Mormons told her all kinds of things about how Joseph Smith practiced polygyny and even sent other men away on missions so that he could marry their wives (essentially forcing these wives to practice polyandry). She was so distraught over this information, which she classified as lies, that she was unable to leave her apartment the next day and almost left her mission. She recovered, but she still characterizes these things as lies. She does not know, or does not want to know, that they are historically accurate facts about Joseph Smith.

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: No sex before marriage, no extramarital sex during marriage, and no homosexual sex ever. The church's stance on masturbation, something it has mostly related to males, has relaxed over the years, but was once (especially in the 1970's and 80's) staunchly prohibited (see attached article and this YouTube video <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QD7mAyAypQo>).

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: No sex before marriage, no extramarital sex during marriage, and no homosexual sex ever. Added to these blanket constraints are whatever constraints a woman's husband decides to add assuming the woman was "endowed" in the temple prior to 2019. The endowment is a lengthy temple rite wherein, prior to 2019, females, married or unmarried, were required to vow to hearken to the voice of their husband even as he hearkened to the voice of Heavenly Father. The temple rite has since changed (<https://religionnews.com/2019/01/03/major-changes-to-mormon-temple-ceremony-especially-for-women/>) but the vow still remains in place for each woman who made it (depending on her interpretation of the past vow and how it relates to the change in the current temple rite), meaning that her husband or future husband (even if he is not a Mormon) is the middleman between her and God.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: However, there have been instances of bishops in the early settler-colonial period of Utah castrating young men as punishment for offenses related to diminishing the pool of plural wives available to the bishops (see <https://www.yearofpolygamy.com/year-of-polygamy/year-of-polygamy-southern-utah-polygamy-orderville-santa-clara-cedar-city-and-violence-episode-48/>)

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: The first Sunday of each month is traditionally "Fast Sunday" in Mormonism. Members are encouraged to go without food and drink for two meals and then donate the money saved to the ward's "fast offerings" fund that then goes to ward members in need. In Utah, young men ages 11-14 (not young women) often go door to door to everyone in their ward asking for these fast offerings on Fast Sunday as part of these young men's priesthood duty as "deacons" (the first level of the preparatory priesthood called the Aaronic priesthood). This does not happen in Peru because the houses of the congregants in a ward are not usually within walking distance of each other. It also does not happen for Peruvian Mormons in Utah who go to Spanish-speaking wards. Utah has such a high concentration of English-speaking Mormons that the English-speaking "ward boundaries" are drawn around extremely small areas on the map. This means that each neighborhood is its own "ward" or congregation. On the other hand, for Mormons who attend one of Utah's 160+ Spanish-speaking congregations, ward boundaries can include areas too vast for 12-year-old boys to cover on foot, especially if those boys are fasting. Still, Spanish-speaking congregations in both Peru and Utah are encouraged to fast and simply bring the fast offering to church. The "sacrament meeting" (similar to mass) on a Fast Sunday, rather than consisting of the usual prepared speeches by ward members and leaders who have been specifically invited to speak, consists instead of an open mic sharing of spiritual stories, thoughts and anecdotes. This special, monthly sacrament meeting is called "fast and testimony meeting." Fasting is thought to make the sharing of spiritual stories more powerful. Since fasting weakens the body, it heightens the senses of the spirit, which can connect to the Holy Ghost, a male member of the God Head who does not have a body. The Holy Ghost lets Anglo Mormons know what is true or not by making them emotional. This often makes Anglo Mormons cry a lot during Fast and

Testimony meetings, assuming that a lot of truth is being spoken. Peruvian Mormons, on the other hand, have a different epistemology that relies less on the Holy Ghost and do not often cry during their Fast and Testimony meetings. Another difference between Peruvian and Anglo Mormon Fast and Testimony meetings is that Peruvian Mormons (both in Peru and Utah) never let a second go by between speakers. There is always a line to go up to the mic. Anglo Mormons Fast and Testimony meetings, on the other hand, often include extremely long spaces of awkward silence between speakers. When the next speaker does eventually come up to the mike, she will often mention how The Spirit (Holy Ghost) "worked" on her during the silence to get her to come up and "bear her testimony." Another difference is that Peruvians as a demographic have more years of formal education than the U.S. population at large and much of that education involves oratory instruction. This means that Peruvian Mormon impromptu speech at these open mic meetings (even from children), is usually much more coherent, original and engaging from the audience's perspective than Anglo Mormon speech (even from adults), which tends to include the same pat phrases that have become the fodder for much Mormon parody: "I'd like to bear my testimony. I know this church is true. I love my family. Namajesuschrisamen."

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

— Yes

Notes: See the aforementioned health code called the Word of Wisdom.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

— No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

— No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

— No

Notes: However, there was a time in early Anglo Mormonism in Utah called "The Reformation" when a concept called "blood atonement" was practiced. It was thought that there were certain sins that could only be erased through killing the sinner. (see <https://www.yearofpolygamy.com/year-of-polygamy/year-of-polygamy-polygamy-and-blood-atonement-episode-38/>)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

— No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

— No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Part of the temple ritual known as the endowment requires members to be willing to sacrifice all things, "even their own lives if necessary" for the building up of "Zion." Though these oath-takers must be willing to make these sacrifices, they have not been called on to actually go through with them as of yet. All members, regardless of whether they have received temple ordinances, are required to pay a full ten percent of their monthly gross income to the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints headquartered in Salt Lake City. This payment can now be made directly to church headquarters online.

↳ To other in-group members:

– No

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: to the quasi-metaphorical concept of "establishing Zion."

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Mormons do not usually just attend whatever church meeting they happen upon each Sunday. They belong, every day, to a tight-knit congregation wherein they usually have a significant responsibility that often involves organizing and participating in mid-week activities. Since Peruvian Mormons in Peru have often had to sacrifice belonging in what remains a largely Andean Catholic society that involves ritual drunkenness (prohibited by Mormonism) and cyclical responsibility in sponsoring extremely expensive patron saint festivals (see photo), they tend to turn to their Mormon congregation for more aspects of daily sociability than their Anglo Mormon counterparts do in Utah. Peruvian Mormon congregations become "ward families" in a much more real sense than English-speaking congregations in Utah. Perifericos ward in Arequipa had some sort of class, activity, dance, party, talent night, missionary farewell, pollada (chicken cook-off fundraiser), dance practice for the annual multi-congregation Andean dance contest (see photo), FIFA World Cup showing, reenactment of the Anglo Mormon Great Plains pioneer crossing (see photo), or Executive Committee planning meeting nearly every night during the contributor's fieldwork. It is the contributor's estimation that adult Peruvian Mormons in Peru and Utah spend an average of 20 hours per week on church-related activities where as Anglo Mormons in Utah spend 6 hours. If Perifericos ward's WhatsApp group feed is any indication, the time that ward members spent on church-related activities (though now online) actually increased during the height of the COVID-19 disaster in Arequipa.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Notes: Peruvian Mormons in the past have had to take significant physical risks in order to get to the places where the family-binding rituals can be performed. Only families bound together in this form of ritual kinship can be whole families in the afterlife. The only places these rituals can happen are the holy temples, and Peru did not receive its first temple until 1986. Prior to this, the only temple in South America was in Sao Paulo, Brazil. Many Peruvian Mormons have harrowing stories filled with miracles about their trip to the Sao Paulo temple. Before the Arequipa temple was dedicated in December 2019,

Peruvian Mormons in Arequipa had to travel the 16 to 18 hours on bus to get to the closest temple in Lima. For many of the elderly members, this involved significant physical risk. Also, bus travel in Peru is not all that safe. A member of Perifericos ward died in 2019 in a bus accident coming back from Lima (it was not a temple trip).

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Notes: In Peruvian Mormonism, this largely revolves around Mormonism's alcohol and idolatry prohibitions. Alcohol and patron saint worship are an integral part of Andean Catholicism, a popular form of Catholicism in Arequipa, Peru (especially among a growing minority of recent migrants from Puno and Cuzco). When Peruvians become Mormons, they are often no longer invited to festivals and parties that involve casual drinking, ritual drunkenness or patron saint worship (not that they would attend even if they were invited). Since these festivals involve communal indebtedness and reciprocity, no longer being able to fully participate in them through drinking alcohol often means losing membership in the community entirely. As alcohol is strongly associated with dancing in Peru, many Peruvian non-Mormons are shocked to find out that Mormons can have one without the other. That Mormons can dance but not drink does not compute in the Andean Catholic mindset. Be that as it may, dancing is extremely important for Peruvian Mormons even though alcohol is extremely prohibited (see video). Sharing large quantities of food and Inca Kola (instead of alcohol) in close proximity with each other is also extremely important (see photo).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The field doesn't know because this is completely up to personal preference and chance. There are many small-scale rituals in Mormonism that are not requisite or regular. Personal prayer is supposed to be done at least daily, but could happen multiple times per day as well. Receiving a blessing of health by the laying on of hands and anointing of consecrated olive oil is a small-scale ritual that is only performed when there is a health problem.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 150

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 168

Notes: 168 is the number of hours in a week. The most regular, large ritual in which Mormons participate involves their weekly Sunday meetings. In 2019, the church changed its Sunday schedule world wide from 3 hours to 2 hours. From an anthropological perspective, the entire 2 hours involve a complex ritual, only part of which, the blessing, passing and taking of the sacrament (Eucharist), is what Mormons themselves would consider an "ordination" or ritual. The sacrament ritual lasts about 10 minutes and is performed approximately 48 Sundays each year in each congregation.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Yes, Mormonism is an extremely bureaucratic and U.S. centric religion, so of course there are checks and balances on everything. This is especially the case in Peruvian Mormonism because the Anglo leaders of the church suspect Peruvians, and all people in what they consider the "underdeveloped" Global South, of corruption and ineptitude. This is why many positions of prominence in the church in Arequipa, Peru, such as the position of "mission president" are held by Anglo Mormons flown in from Utah.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– No

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: There is a pamphlet that Anglo-controlled church committees in Utah produce called For the Strength of Youth. One focus of the pamphlet is personal hygiene and modesty in dress. New editions come out every few years, but many past editions included specific standards for hair and beards. The current online edition simply encourages Mormon youth to avoid "extreme" hairstyles (see attached). Many Peruvian Mormons take this pamphlet very seriously and use it as a manual for everyday life. The pamphlet is very similar to colonial guidelines established in Peru in order to "deindianize" the people and make them more docile and comely so that they could be more easily convinced to part with their land, labor and lifeways.

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: See above. Also see the entire For the Strength of Youth pamphlet here: <https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/manual/for-the-strength-of-youth?lang=eng> Also see the entire 2011 edition of the pamphlet attached.

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

Notes: One of the most common, optional markers of Mormon membership is a ring with a CTR emblem that stands for Choose The Right. Another common, quasi mandatory marker of Mormon membership is the complete absence of tattoos. As the contributor likes contradictions, he personally has a tattoo of the CTR emblem on his right shoulder.

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

Notes: This is not something that most Peruvian Mormons know about, but there was a small movement when Anglo Mormons first arrived in Utah to build a new society complete with a new alphabet, currency, etc. Here is a web page dedicated to the alphabet: <http://www.deseretalphabet.org/>

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: there is an ability called "modar" that allows Mormons to spot a fellow Mormon in a crowd.

Notes: "Modar" (Mormon radar) is facilitated by the fact that Mormons who have gone through the temple ritual called the endowment have to wear special undergarments forever after. The bottom garment goes down to just above the knee and the top garment covers the shoulders. In order to cover these garments, Mormons have to wear, at the very least, shorts that go to the knee and shirts that cover the shoulders. On a hot day on a Southern California boardwalk (Orange County, California has a large concentration of Mormons) most people will be wearing very little clothing. Therefore, if you see someone wearing a full t-shirt and capris, there is a good chance that person is Mormon. However, depending on individual preference and individual interpretation of the oath taken upon accepting the garments, many Mormons do not wear them while exercising, swimming, or engaging in other activities to which they do not find them amenable. This lessens the accuracy of "modar." Furthermore, in certain societies, such as Arequipa, Peru wherein most people cover up most of their bodies regardless of religious preference, "modar" is even less effective. In fact, most Peruvian Mormons have not heard of modar. One venue wherein modar is commonly used is U.S. airports. In airports, people tend to dress comfortably, and Anglo Mormons tend to wear the bare minimum to cover up their garments, thus leaving them slightly visible if seen from the right vantage. As people tend to have the time to people-watch at airports, some Mormons find it fun to try to zero in on other Mormons by using all the clues above and then confirming their hypothesis

with a discrete peak under the suspected target's clothing. Another characteristic that will cause a Mormon's modar to ping, even in a Peru, is the sight of a very young couple wherein the mother is carrying an infant, the father is pushing a double stroller containing a 1-year-old and a 2-year-old and they are being followed by a three-year-old on a tricycle and a four-year-old on a bicycle. Peruvian Mormons tend to have quite a few more kids than the norm for their society and they also tend to marry extremely young. In Arequipa it is ideal to get married around age 30 among non-Mormons. Among Mormons, on the other hand, if one is unmarried at 30 one has almost lost hope of ever getting married. The ideal age for Mormon marriage in both Peru and Utah is 21 for males and 19 for females.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: In every Mormon congregation the contributor has joined around the world (Bolivia, Mexico, Canada, U.S, Taiwan, China, Japan, Turkey, Peru) Mormons address each other with the title Brother or Sister. They do not consider these "fictive" kin titles since, according to Mormon cosmology, all humans are literally spirit siblings born of the same two heavenly parents (though there is the possibility that Heavenly Father practices polygyny, meaning some of us are mere half-siblings to others of us).

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Notes: It is extremely common, but again, it is not fictive from an emic point of view.

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: Famously so. See attached article for just one of thousands of examples.

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: However, this is predominantly through its university, Brigham Young University, which only has campuses in Utah, Idaho, Hawaii, and Jerusalem. There are still a few church-run primary and secondary schools in a few countries around the world such as (to the contributor's knowledge) Mexico and New Zealand, but there never were any in Peru. There are a few primary schools in Peru that were begun by Peruvian Mormons, such as Brigham Young Academy in Juliaca, Peru, however these were never officially endorsed by the church and most are no longer under Mormon management (though they still retain their Mormon names). Many non-Mormons in Peru find it unconscionable that the church does not have its own primary and secondary schools in Peru. Non-Mormon school administrators do not like having to

deal with Mormons (and their demands) in their schools. One bone of contention is Sunday. Catholics technically believe in keeping the sabbath day holy, but Mormons come off as significantly "holier than thou" in this respect. Mormons in Peru tend to be very strict about what they can and cannot do on Sunday, and school activities are often on the list of what they cannot do. Schools in Peru, however, often have required activities on Sundays, many of which begin with a shortened version of Catholic mass. In Peru, formal education is so infused with the Catholic religion (though, officially, it is not supposed to be) that most other religions have taken the hint and started their own schools. Mormons have not. Peruvian Mormons would love to send their kids to Mormon-run schools if such were available, but they also point to the many advantages of having their children be the sole Mormons in their classrooms. It is a great missionizing opportunity. In fact, one Peruvian Mormon youth spoke at a special event leading up to the dedication of the Arequipa temple about how he was able to convince his teacher to take their entire class on a field trip to the temple open house (the only time when non-Mormons and "unworthy" Mormons may enter a temple).

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: Temple Square in Utah has its own security force. There also used to be, or perhaps still is, an internal intelligence agency in the church involved in keeping tabs on potential apostates.

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: Not anymore, but they used to.

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: The church owns large farms in a number of disclosed and undisclosed locations, largely in the U.S.

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: But it used to have its own alphabet.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Mormons in the U.S. are often very militaristic and tend to support the most war mongering of the two political parties. In fact, Mormons are the most predominantly Republican of any other U.S. religious group. Many Anglo Mormons who fought in WWII have more U.S. iconography on their headstones than Mormon iconography. The contributor's own grandfather, a staunch Anglo Mormon, BYU professor, and former bishop, had nothing at his burial that would indicate he was a Mormon, yet he had a military brigade come in and do a 21-gun salute because he was a veteran.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)
- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The institution of consumer capitalism provides Peruvian Mormons with the majority of their food in both Peru and Utah. However, Peruvian Mormons in Utah do occasionally obtain processed food under the church's label, Deseret, which the church produces in its food factories in Utah and provides free of charge for church welfare recipients at its "bishop storehouses" throughout Utah that are set up like normal grocery stores. Deseret brand food is rarely available in Peru, though sometimes, with much fanfare, it is donated to Peruvian grocery stores. The contributor has eaten Deseret brand bottled salsa in the homes of many Peruvian and Mexican Mormons in Utah. It is quite good.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Usually the church is not the only source of famine relief to those it relieves from famine.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Many Peruvians who were Mormon during the time of Peru's Shining Path guerrilla war in the 1990's have stories about trying to proselyte in the crossfire between Peru's national military and the Shining Path (Sendero Luminoso) headquartered in Ayacucho. This is evident in the following transcribed conversation excerpt between two Peruvian Mormon former missionaries (Delia and Salvador) and the contributor that took place in 2018. DELIA: We were surprised because in Ayacucho [Sendero headquarters], it was the most difficult place in all of Peru, but they always had the most baptisms. And the missionaries who left to serve in Ayacucho were very fearful. I remember when we'd have our returned missionary reunions, many of them would tell stories and they'd say, "Oye, do you remember in the plane how you cried, 'why Ayacucho? Why!?' " But they were mixed feelings: I am willing to serve the Lord, but that doesn't take away the terror that I feel, right? Because the missionaries that served in Ayacucho, well, they knew that no matter what, they were going to hear the bombs and the fire fights. We had two mission companions who were first jailed and then forced into military service. JASON: For the Sendero? DELIA: No, no. What happened was that Elder Huamán committed an error. He didn't regularize his documentation before leaving for his mission, so when he got to Ayacucho, he had his companion, Giraldo, and every day there would be draft raids [batidas]. When it came time to see Elder Huamán's documents, they saw an irregularity, "since your documents are bad, which is your own fault, you are going to have to do military service. Alright?" Obviously the missionaries protested, "But, no way! Why? No." Immediately they conscripted him. And to his companion they said, "you can leave." "No, I can't leave because we are companions and they told me not to leave him." "Ah, alright then, you get in there as well." And they conscripted him too. By the time the zone leaders [young missionaries in charge of multiple companionships] called Lima, the documentation was already entered and they were--- SALVADOR: ---Soldiers. DELIA: Soldiers. When the mission president's assistants finally came, they found them with uniforms and shaved heads [laughs] and for two months they were serving their country, doing drills, everything, but they were also preaching the gospel to many soldiers and they had baptisms in there as well. But something very special happened with all of this because President Openshaw was

still there. I was assigned to Cuzco at the time and he traveled to Cuzco very worried and told us, "their two months of basic training are almost up. If we don't get them out of the army fast, they are going to enter the battlefield." And since they were young men in Ayacucho itself, well, it was practically a death sentence. In those two months the church did all kinds of paperwork, but they were always denied, it was terrible. And Giraldo wasn't about to abandon his companion [laughs]. He had that very clear. So when president Openshaw arrived in the Cuzco zone we had a kneeling prayer, "Today we must start fasting," he said, "from this very moment. We are going to fast and we are going to pray." We prayed and the blessing was given because with only one day to spare before they went into--- SALVADOR: ---the infantry--- DELIA: ---With one day to spare, the leaders from Lima arrived in Ayacucho, president Openshaw obviously couldn't go himself, being a North American. They couldn't find anyone to speak with, but suddenly a car pulls up right next to them and out walks one of the generals. The area leader goes up to him, "we have a problem, people know us as the Mormons, and we have two missionaries"--- "What? What? You are the Mormons? I had a Mormon friend, an excellent guy. I admire you people, you know that? I owe you a lot. Which young men are you're looking for?" And the general himself signs them out. That same day both missionaries were discharged. So when the president returned to Cuzco, he said, "our prayers were answered—cutting it a little too close for my taste—but He got the missionaries out." And Elder Huamán went on to become my zone leader, so that is how I know all about his experiences. JASON: And his companion was a Peruvian as well? DELIA: Yes, both of them, extremely Peruvian [laughing]. They didn't send North Americans to Ayacucho. Many experiences like that happened, that's for sure. And this year we are going to have a South Mission reunion in Ayacucho, August 30, to remember the old times. A lot of people will be there, even Giraldo will be there because he lives in the United States now, but he and all the rest will come to visit.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

— Yes

Notes: Each congregation's bishop is known as a "judge in Israel."

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

— Yes

Notes: However, it is extremely difficult for people who need it to access this relief especially in Peru. The leaders of the church in Peru, be they Anglo or Peruvian, think that developing a dependency on welfare is more dangerous than poverty itself. If the church wanted to, it has enough funds to permanently eliminate poverty in the entire country of Peru.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Notes: Not any more, but they did during the presidency of Brigham Young.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Notes: But, again, they used to.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Notes: Not any more, but they used to.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: In the form of deportation.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

|

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:
– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:
– Yes

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: Famously so. See attached article for just one of thousands of examples.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Usually the church is not the only source of famine relief to those it relieves from famine.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: However, it is extremely difficult for people who need it to access this relief especially in Peru. The leaders of the church in Peru, be they Anglo or Peruvian, think that developing a dependency on welfare is more dangerous than poverty itself. If the church wanted to, it has enough funds to permanently eliminate poverty in the entire country of Peru.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: However, this is predominantly through its university, Brigham Young University, which only has campuses in Utah, Idaho, Hawaii, and Jerusalem. There are still a few church-run primary and secondary schools in a few countries around the world such as (to the contributor's knowledge) Mexico and New Zealand, but there never were any in Peru. There are a few primary schools in Peru that were begun by Peruvian Mormons, such as Brigham Young Academy in Juliaca, Peru, however these were never officially endorsed by the church and most are no longer under Mormon management (though they still retain their Mormon names). Many non-Mormons in Peru find it unconscionable that the church does not have its own primary and secondary schools in Peru. Non-Mormon school administrators do not like having to deal with Mormons (and their demands) in their schools. One bone of contention is Sunday. Catholics technically believe in keeping the sabbath day holy, but Mormons come off as significantly "holier than thou" in this respect. Mormons in Peru tend to be very strict about what they can and cannot do on Sunday, and school activities are often on the list of what they cannot do. Schools in Peru, however, often have required activities on Sundays, many of which begin with a shortened version of Catholic mass. In Peru, formal education is so infused with the Catholic religion (though, officially, it is not supposed to be) that most other religions have taken the hint and started their own schools. Mormons have not. Peruvian Mormons would love to send their kids to Mormon-run schools if such were available, but they also point to the many advantages of having their children be the sole Mormons in their classrooms. It is a great missionizing opportunity. In fact, one Peruvian Mormon youth spoke at a special event leading up to the dedication of the Arequipa temple about how he was able to convince his teacher to take their entire class on a field trip to the temple open house (the only time when non-Mormons and "unworthy" Mormons may enter a temple).

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: Temple Square in Utah has its own security force. There also used to be, or perhaps still is, an internal intelligence agency in the church involved in keeping tabs on potential apostates.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: Each congregation's bishop is known as a "judge in Israel."

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Notes: Not any more, but they did during the presidency of Brigham Young.

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Notes: But, again, they used to.

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Notes: Not any more, but they used to.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

|

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:
– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:
– Yes

Notes: In the form of deportation.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:
– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:
– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:
– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:
– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:
– No

Notes: Not anymore, but they used to.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– Yes

Notes: Mormons in the U.S. are often very militaristic and tend to support the most war mongering of the two political parties. In fact, Mormons are the most predominantly Republican of any other U.S. religious group. Many Anglo Mormons who fought in WWII have more U.S. iconography on their headstones than Mormon iconography. The contributor's own grandfather, a staunch Anglo Mormon, BYU professor, and former bishop, had nothing at his burial that would indicate he was a Mormon, yet he had a military brigade come in and do a 21-gun salute because he was a veteran.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– Yes

Notes: Many Peruvians who were Mormon during the time of Peru's Shining Path guerrilla war in the 1990's have stories about trying to proselyte in the crossfire between Peru's national military and the Shining Path (Sendero Luminoso) headquartered in Ayacucho. This is evident in the following

transcribed conversation excerpt between two Peruvian Mormon former missionaries (Delia and Salvador) and the contributor that took place in 2018. DELIA: We were surprised because in Ayacucho [Sendero headquarters], it was the most difficult place in all of Peru, but they always had the most baptisms. And the missionaries who left to serve in Ayacucho were very fearful. I remember when we'd have our returned missionary reunions, many of them would tell stories and they'd say, "Oye, do you remember in the plane how you cried, 'why Ayacucho? Why!?' " But they were mixed feelings: I am willing to serve the Lord, but that doesn't take away the terror that I feel, right? Because the missionaries that served in Ayacucho, well, they knew that no matter what, they were going to hear the bombs and the fire fights. We had two mission companions who were first jailed and then forced into military service. JASON: For the Sendero? DELIA: No, no. What happened was that Elder Huamán committed an error. He didn't regularize his documentation before leaving for his mission, so when he got to Ayacucho, he had his companion, Giraldo, and every day there would be draft raids [batidas]. When it came time to see Elder Huamán's documents, they saw an irregularity, "since your documents are bad, which is your own fault, you are going to have to do military service. Alright?" Obviously the missionaries protested, "But, no way! Why? No." Immediately they conscripted him. And to his companion they said, "you can leave." "No, I can't leave because we are companions and they told me not to leave him." "Ah, alright then, you get in there as well." And they conscripted him too. By the time the zone leaders [young missionaries in charge of multiple companionships] called Lima, the documentation was already entered and they were--- SALVADOR: ---Soldiers. DELIA: Soldiers. When the mission president's assistants finally came, they found them with uniforms and shaved heads [laughs] and for two months they were serving their country, doing drills, everything, but they were also preaching the gospel to many soldiers and they had baptisms in there as well. But something very special happened with all of this because President Openshaw was still there. I was assigned to Cuzco at the time and he traveled to Cuzco very worried and told us, "their two months of basic training are almost up. If we don't get them out of the army fast, they are going to enter the battlefield." And since they were young men in Ayacucho itself, well, it was practically a death sentence. In those two months the church did all kinds of paperwork, but they were always denied, it was terrible. And Giraldo wasn't about to abandon his companion [laughs]. He had that very clear. So when president Openshaw arrived in the Cuzco zone we had a kneeling prayer, "Today we must start fasting," he said, "from this very moment. We are going to fast and we are going to pray." We prayed and the blessing was given because with only one day to spare before they went into--- SALVADOR: ---the infantry--- DELIA: ---With one day to spare, the leaders from Lima arrived in Ayacucho, president Openshaw obviously couldn't go himself, being a North American. They couldn't find anyone to speak with, but suddenly a car pulls up right next to them and out walks one of the generals. The area leader goes up to him, "we have a problem, people know us as the Mormons, and we have two missionaries"--- "What? What? You are the Mormons!? I had a Mormon friend, an excellent guy. I admire you people, you know that? I owe you a lot. Which young men are you're looking for?" And the general himself signs them out. That same day both missionaries were discharged. So when the president returned to Cuzco, he said, "our prayers were answered—cutting it a little too close for my taste—but He got the missionaries out." And Elder Huamán went on to become my zone leader, so that is how I know all about his experiences. JASON: And his companion was a Peruvian as well? DELIA: Yes, both of them, extremely Peruvian [laughing]. They didn't send North Americans to Ayacucho. Many experiences like that happened, that's for sure. And this year we are going to have a South Mission reunion in Ayacucho, August 30, to remember the old times. A lot of people will be there, even Giraldo will be there because he lives in the United States now, but he and all the rest will come to visit.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

— No

Notes: But it used to have its own alphabet.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: The church owns large farms in a number of disclosed and undisclosed locations, largely in the U.S.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The institution of consumer capitalism provides Peruvian Mormons with the majority of their food in both Peru and Utah. However, Peruvian Mormons in Utah do occasionally obtain processed food under the church's label, Deseret, which the church produces in its food factories in Utah and provides free of charge for church welfare recipients at its "bishop storehouses" throughout Utah that are set up like normal grocery stores. Deseret brand food is rarely available in Peru, though sometimes, with much fanfare, it is donated to Peruvian grocery stores. The contributor has eaten Deseret brand bottled salsa in the homes of many Peruvian and Mexican Mormons in Utah. It is quite good.

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Peruvian Mormons, Aikau, Hokulani K. A Chosen People A Promised Land: Mormonism and Race in Hawaii'. University of Minnesota Press, 2012.